

66th ESReDA Seminar

**Transformative safety and resilience models in a smart
digital and sustainable world**

May 22th - 23th, 2025

University of Salento, Lecce, Italy

Edited by

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ESReDA: European Safety, Reliability & Data Association

Association internationale sans but lucratif, régis par la loi Belge du 27 Juin 1921-Titre III (Registration N°: 0452522618 - Siret:E00005802)

Headquarter: ESReDA, rue Gachard 88 Bte 14, B-1050 Bruxelles, Belgium

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The 66th ESReDA Seminar

Transformative safety and resilience models in a smart
digital and sustainable world

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European Safety, Reliability & Data Association (ESReDA)

European Safety, Reliability & Data Association (ESReDA) is a European Association established in 1992 to promote research, application and training in Reliability, Availability, Maintainability and Safety (RAMS). The Association provides a forum for the exchange of information, data and current research in Safety and Reliability.

ESReDA membership is open to organisations, privates or governmental institutes, industry researchers and consultants, who are active in the field of Safety and Reliability.

ESReDA Project Groups (PG) are open to all engineers, researchers and consultants from academia or industry who are active in the field of Safety and Reliability, whether they are ESReDA members or not.

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ESReDA: European Safety, Reliability & Data Association

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Abstract

These proceedings are the outcome of the 66th ESReDa Seminar hosted by University of Salento, in Lecce from 22nd to 23rd May 2025.

The main target of the seminar was to point out what is the current contribution of digital technologies for supporting transformative safety design and management processes in several operational domains.

The seminar has outlined that digitalization is characterized by a transformative capability mainly oriented to improve operational performance, reduce accidents and increase system reactivity through several ways. However, new emerging risks, e.g. due to the massive use of intelligent robotics systems interacting directly with humans (like collaborative robots), to the use of decision support systems (e.g. based on algorithmic management) that provide automatic feedback to humans, e.g. workers as well as safety managers and/or analysts, must be also evaluated through innovative models.

This seminar has involved different stakeholders, from researchers to industry and national institution experts, interested in discussing about innovative models, case studies and legislation analysis about different safety domains from process to manufacturing and service industries. The proceedings include 3 plenary speeches, 1 industry talk, 1 special session, and 16 full papers or extended abstracts and the results of the interactive section that was performed during the first day of the seminar.

Mariagrazia.Gnoni

Associate Professor

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About ESReDA

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For more information and available ESReDA proceedings please consult <http://www.esreda.org/>

About University of Salento

The research group of University of Salento involved in the seminar organization is an interdisciplinary team: its main research activities are focused on designing innovative organizational and technological models for supporting lean OSH management systems in complex firms and developing and assessing performance of digital solutions in the safety domain, e.g. for supporting accident prevention at workplace as well as dynamic risk analysis models. The research group is involved in several national and international projects in the safety sector focusing on evaluating how digital technologies could be adopted in a sustainable way in the industrial sector, about dynamic risk analysis based on evaluating knowledge extracted from weak signals, and on developing tools for measuring safety culture of industrial organizations through near miss management systems.

Introduction

These proceedings are the outcome of the 66th ESReDa Seminar hosted by University of Salento, in Lecce from 22nd to 23rd May 2025.

The seminar has pointed out how digital technologies could transforming risk assessment and management as well as resilience in several industrial sectors as well as from different perspectives, such as from company point of views to researchers and institutions. Discussions have moved from the contribution of digital technologies in improving risk assessment and resilience models and in supporting prevention of industrial accidents; furthermore, studies about how to develop more human centric digital solution were also discussed and analysed in different industrial and service sectors. A special session was dedicated to the “Collaborative intelligence and human in the loop for the future of safety critical systems. A human centred perspective.”

The purpose of the seminar was to reflect upon the following topics:

- Digital technologies for supporting resilience and business continuity.
- Tools and models for managing safety data for preventing accidents.
- Human centric approaches for designing digital technologies applied for safety and resilience.
- Digital technologies for predict and mitigate potential hazards.
- Digital tools and new models for supporting analysis of early warning signals.
- Resilience of cyber-socio-technical systems.
- Digital Technologies for Resilient and Socially Sustainable Systems.
- Digital twins technologies for supporting safety.
- Cyber physical systems for dynamic risk analysis.
- Models and tools for integrating sustainability in safety and resilience impact analysis models.
- Models for supporting safe human and robot collaboration especially in hazardous environments.
- Algorithmic management in the safety domain:
- Risk assessment of complex socio-technical systems.

- AI for maintenance management and failure diagnosis and prognosis.

The seminar shared 16 contributions in oral sessions, 4 of which were Key Notes:

- Prof. Roberto Setola, Rome Campus Biomedico, Italy
- Prof. Riccardo Patriarca, University of La Sapienza, Italy
- dr. Paolo Bragatto, Rome Campus Biomedico, Italy

and one Industry Talk by:

- Dr. Javier Sordo, beXReal, Spain.

Acknowledgements

The authors are very thankful for the time and attention from ESReDA Board of Directors and in particular to the ESReDA President Dr. Mohamed Eid, the General Secretary Prof. Antonio Guillen and the Treasurer prof. Micaela De Michela for their continuous support in organizing the seminar.

A grateful thanks is due to all authors, keynote speakers and participants that have contribute to the 66th Seminar: every contribution and discussion have provided an increase in current knowledge about the seminar topic. The seminar was also a wonderful occasion to meet, starting new scientific relationships and consolidating old ones.

Authors thanks also to the Technical Committee for the effective support in the review process.

An expression of appreciation is hereby extended to Fondazione Puglia for its partial support of the seminar's financial organization.

Mariagrazia.Gnoni

Chair of the 65th ESReDA Seminar

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Keynote Presentations

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Resilience as a framework to manage Emergent Risks

By Prof. Roberto Setola

Complex Systems & Security Laboratory

www.coseritylab.it

ESReDA

European Safety, Reliability & Data Association

66th ESReDA Seminar
Transformative safety and resilience models in a smart digital and sustainable world

Resilience as a framework to manage Emergent Risk

Prof. Roberto Setola

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Italy

Lecce, 22 May 2025

Energy Transition

New interferences

03/06/2025

www.coseritylab.it

Climate changes

Figure 1: Insured losses since 1970
in billion (in 2021 prices)
Click on the chart to zoom in/
hover/touch chart for details

Extreme events

Source: Swiss Re www.swissre.com
www.coseritylab.it

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03/06/2025

NaTech

NaTech events can be defined as technological accidents—such as fires, explosions, and toxic releases—that occur within industrial facilities or along distribution networks as a consequence of **natural disasters**

eNatech Database

Technological accidents triggered by a natural hazard or disaster which result in consequences involving **hazardous substances** (e.g. fire, explosion, toxic release) are commonly referred to as **Natech** accidents. The aim of this database is to **systematically** collect information on Natech accidents that occurred **worldwide** and allow the **searching and analysis** of Natech accident reports for **lessons-learning** purposes.

<https://enatech.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

lightning-triggered accident occurred at an oil storage terminal in Matanzas Bay, Cuba (6/08/22)

03/06/2025

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Digital transformation

Figure 2: Average Lines of Software Code in Modern Luxury Vehicle Compared to Types of Aircraft

Source: Battelle. | GAO-18-350

With the best Software Engineering techniques actually there is a bug rate of about 0,1 defects per KLOC

<https://www.mayerdan.com/ruby/2012/11/11/bugs-per-line-of-code-ratio>

Consequences of a cyber event

2025 – Spain and Portugal

2023 – US and Canada

These are not cyber attacks

CrowdStrike 2024

Technology

1 minute read · November 3, 2022 11:01 PM GMT+1 · Last Updated 5 months ago

Danish train standstill on Saturday caused by cyber attack

European oil facilities hit by cyber-attacks

3 February 2022

Australia ports operator suffers 'cybersecurity incident', suspends operations

11 Nov 2023 (Updated)

<https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-60250956>

US officials find weak security practices at water plants breached by pro-Russia hackers

By Sean Lyngaas, CNN
5 minute read · Published 10:15 AM EDT, Wed May 1, 2024

Iran petrol stations hit by cyberattack, oil minister says

Reuters
December 18, 2023 7:38 PM GMT+1 · Updated 18 days ago

<https://www.reuters.com/world/middle-east/software-problem-disrupts-iranian-gas-stations-fars-2023-12-18/>

Cybersecurity Hackers Breached Colonial Pipeline Using Compromised Password

By William Turton and Kartikay Mehrotra
4 giugno 2021, 21:58 CEST

03/06/2025

ICS
SCADA
DCS
PLC

Typical Industrial Network Architecture: Purdue Model

Critical Infrastructure: Commission accelerates work to build up European resilience

14 october 2022

With the increasing interdependence of physical and digital infrastructures, **malicious cyber activities targeting critical areas may result in disruption or damage to physical infrastructure**, while sabotage of physical infrastructure may render digital services inaccessible.

[EU Recommendation on resilience of IC (proposal)]

Triton: hackers take out safety systems in 'watershed' attack on energy plant

Sophisticated malware halts operations at power station in unprecedented attack which experts believe was state-sponsored

<https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2017/dec/15/triton-hackers-malware-attack-safety-systems-energy-plant>

SIS Safety Instrumented System

A safety instrumented system (SIS) consists of an engineered set of hardware and software controls to perform to failsafe or maintain safe operation of a process when unacceptable or dangerous conditions occur.

advanced persistent threat

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CYBERSECURITY &
INFRASTRUCTURE
SECURITY AGENCY

AMERICA'S CYBER DEFENSE AGENCY

APT

<https://www.cisa.gov/topics/cyber-threats-and-advisories/advanced-persistent-threats-and-nation-state-actors>

- APT is an adversary that **possesses sophisticated levels of expertise and significant resources** which allow it to create opportunities to achieve its objectives by using **multiple attack vectors** (e.g., cyber, physical, and deception).... for purposes of **exfiltrating information, undermining or impeding critical aspects of a mission, program, or organization**; or positioning itself to carry out these objectives in the **future**

The advanced persistent threat:

- pursues its objectives repeatedly over an extended period of time;
- adapts to defenders' efforts to resist it;
- is determined to maintain the level of interaction needed to execute its objectives.

Geopolitical cyber attacks 2009 - 2019

World governments are investing more and more capital on both offense and defense-related cyber tools, tactics, and strategies

<https://www.fintechnews.org/is-cyberwarfare-as-threatening/>

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Interdependencies

<1990

Ogni infrastruttura era un ente autonomo verticalmente integrato e gestito da operatori nazionali monopolistici

>2000

Le differenti infrastrutture sono operate da una pluralità di soggetti e esse appaiono interoperanti sotto molteplici aspetti

No operator is able to **independently** guarantee the ability to provide its essential services to the population, as it depends on the provision of services by third parties

Bologna, S., & Setola, R. (2005, November). The need to improve local self-awareness in CIP/CIIP. In *First IEEE International Workshop on Critical Infrastructure Protection (IWCIPO5)* (pp. 6-pp). IEEE.

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03/06/2025

Emergent Risk

These are risks which we are unable to see because they are outside our experience or mind set, so we don't know that we should be looking for them.

They are “unknown unknowns,” which are things that we do not know but where we are unaware of our ignorance.

Emergent Risk

- The term **Emergent Risk** is used to describe risks that are **poorly understood**, but are expected to grow greatly in significance.
- Completely **new** risks that have never been seen before
- Previously known risks that are evolving in **unexpected** ways with **unanticipated** consequences
- Unlike other risks, **emergent risks do not have a track record** which can be used to estimate likely probabilities and expected losses.

Setola – Rischi Emergenti

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Reasoning under uncertainties

Inference, swans and elephants

Three types of unexpected events

White Swans result from the 'Normal' randomness of a Gaussian Distribution

Grey Swans result from circumstances where Power Law (Fractal or Fat Tailed) randomness occurs

Black Swans result from all those forms of nonlinear randomness that we do not know about

Easily predictable!

Somehow predictable!

Resilience is the ability to continue to provide service if a disruptive event occurs

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Two new EU directives (in force by 2022)

Revised Directive on Security of Network and Information Systems (NIS2)

New directive to enhance the resilience of critical entities CER (former ECI)

Resilience

<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/revise-directive-security-network-and-information-systems-nis2>

https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/news/commission-proposes-new-directive-enhance-resilience-critical-entities-providing-essential_en

All-hazards approach

All-hazard : naturally occurring event, human induced events (both **intentional and non-intentional**) and **technology caused events** with potential impact on organization, community or society and environment on which it depends

Incident: any act or circumstance that produce consequences

[ISO/CD 22300]

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"I was gonna put candles on your birthday cake, mom, but dad said it was a fire hazard!"

Two new EU directives (in force by 2022)

Revised Directive on Security of Network and Information Systems (NIS2)

New directive to enhance the resilience of critical entities CER (former ECI)

A company must consider cyber risk related to **third part**, i.e. suppliers

A company have to consider in the impact assesment the consequences of **dependencies**

Resilience -> time dimensions

Dynamic Risk Assessment (DRA)

$$R(t) = P(t) * C(t)$$

ISO 31050

TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION	ISO/TS 31050
	First edition 2023-10-27
Risk management — Guidelines for managing an emerging risk to enhance resilience	
<i>Management du risque — Lignes directrices relatives à la gestion des risques émergents afin d'améliorer la résilience</i>	
Reference number ISO/TS 31050:2023(E)	
© ISO 2023	

continual scanning across multiple aspects of the organisational context for changes that can signify an early warning or an indicator of threats or opportunities to organisational objectives

DRIVERS is an innovative platform that combines data-driven and experience-driven approaches to transform safety into a **strategic advantage**, protecting operations more effectively and **proactively**.

The intelligent platform is designed to be a corporate **Safety Information** tool, enabling the ability to:

- **Monitor** the emergence of risks from different information sources
- **Predict** critical phenomena through an **early-warning** system
- **Support** informed decisions through integrated **data management**

Nobili, M., Fioravanti, C., Guarino, S., Ansaldo, S. M., Milazzo, M. F., Bragatto, P., & Setola, R. (2023, June). DRIVERS: A platform for dynamic risk assessment of emergent cyber threats for industrial control systems. In *2023 31st Mediterranean Conference on Control and Automation (MED)* (pp. 395-400). IEEE.

Piattaforma DRIVERS

Dashboard

Impianti

Column visibility

Nome Impianto	Rischio Cyber	Rischio Operativo	Rischio Strategico	Rischio Climatico	Organizzazione
2	0	0	0	0	ucbm
Impianto di prova	6,9	4,1	0	0	ucbm
Impianto di Genova	0	0	0	0	genova

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 entries

6/3/2025

Flussi di informazioni

Tool di *Inventory Assessment*: programma sviluppato nel contesto del progetto in grado di riconoscere ed enumerare:

- gli hardware e i software di una rete di tecnologia operativa

dispositivi interconnessi all'interno della rete.

API esterne: vengono richiamate dalla parte di logica e gestione della piattaforma (back-end) per ottenere le informazioni su:

- Rischio **climatico**
- Rischio **cyber**

How to estimate the

We have multiple cascading events that may contribute to one or more critical top events?

We want to compute:

$$P(PLC|Web_server) = \frac{P(Web_server|PLC)P(PLC)}{P(Web_server)}$$

Limitations:

1. Assumes direct relationship between PLC Access and Web server
2. Does not account for intermediate dependences
3. Does not account for causal dependences between intermediate variables

→ 2^k dependences!

Bayesian Attack Graph: setting up

Vulnerability scanning in
the industrial network

The following are identified:

1. Attacker's targets
2. Vulnerabilities
3. Security states of the devices connected to the network

Bayesian network presentation

Continuous BAG

GOAL: search for

1. Time when a CVE was reported
2. Time when an exploit for that CVE was reported

The CPT measures the probability of having an exploitation of the CVE before a certain point in time.

*R. Sato, H. Kawaguchi and Y. Nakatani, "A Stochastic Model for Calculating Well-Founded Probabilities of Vulnerability Exploitation," 2022 IEEE 22nd International Conference on Software Quality, Reliability, and Security Companion (QRS-C), Guangzhou, China, 2022, pp. 34-43, doi: 10.1109/QRS-C57518.2022.00015.

Cyber

CVE identifiers: clicking opens the descriptive page of the CVE.

Area where the device impacted by the CVE is located: clicking opens the descriptive page of the element

The **vulnerability** of a CVE is calculated as its intrinsic vulnerability score (**CVSS**) **minus a remediation percentage** set by expert operators monitoring the facility

Color code:

- Green → low risk
- Yellow → medium risk
- Red → high risk

Id	Area	Registrazione	Vulnerabilità	Cvss	Risoluzione (%)	Aggiorna
CVE-2007-4360	SERRATOI STOCCAGGIO di GNL	28/05/2024 08:58:11	4.3	4.3	0	Aggiorna
CVE-2007-4360	TORCIA	28/05/2024 08:58:53	4.3	4.3	0	Aggiorna
CVE-2009-1298	SERRATOI STOCCAGGIO di GNL	28/05/2024 08:56:11	7.8	7.8	0	Aggiorna
CVE-2009-3080	SERRATOI STOCCAGGIO di GNL	28/05/2024 08:56:11	7.2	7.2	0	Aggiorna
CVE-2009-3547	SERRATOI STOCCAGGIO di GNL	28/05/2024 08:56:11	6.9	6.9	0	Aggiorna
CVE-2009-3612	SERRATOI STOCCAGGIO di GNL	28/05/2024 08:56:11	2.1	2.1	0	Aggiorna

Climate

Grandezze misurate tramite le funzionalità di <https://open-meteo.com>

Soglie impostate dagli utenti per l'area in esame

Valore massimo riportato e livello di vulnerabilità riportato per codifica colore:

- Verde → basso rischio
- Giallo → medio rischio
- Rosso → alto rischio

Impatto	Soglia inferiore	Soglia superiore	Vulnerabilità
Grandine	0.1	0.5	0
Pioggia	1	2	0
Temperatura	10	15	21.2
Vento	5	50	10.8

Unità di misura: Pioggia e grandine (mm); Vento (km/h); Temperatura (°C).

Showing 1 to 4 of 4 entries

Previous 1 Next

ProActive Cybersecurity

Pro-active Cybersecurity

PACY – ProActive Cybersecurity (2024-2027)

Funding institution: Google.org

Scope: The project, funded by Google.org, aims to develop a platform that supports small and microenterprises in managing all elements related to the cyber world. Specifically, the platform will be responsible for identifying possible solutions to be implemented in the prevention phase. During the incident phase, it will identify the nature of the incident and provide indications on the actions needed to mitigate the damage and restore services, covering all aspects: technical, legal, and communication.

Third part cyber attack monitoring

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the VUCA model?

BiteSize Learning

Volatility

A key aspect of your work is subject to major, unpredictable peaks and troughs.

Uncertainty

The future is unknown, but external events are likely to be impactful.

Complexity

Many interconnected factors influence one another, in ways that are challenging to model confidently.

Ambiguity

Conflicting, noisy or insufficient data makes it difficult to assess what's really going on.

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Graphing the whispers: Weak signal insights via advanced knowledge modelling and reasoning

By prof. Riccardo Patriarca

Patriarca, R. (2025)

Graphing the whispers: Weak signal insights via advanced knowledge modelling and reasoning

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Lecce, 22/05/2025 - 66th ESReDA Seminar

Patriarca, R. (2025)

My background

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Keywords: resilience, risk, safety, operations management,
socio-technical systems, knowledge management, system modeling

Europaeus Doctor (EU PhD) Industrial and Management Eng.
at Sapienza (Italy) in collaboration with Lund University (Sweden)

PhD Researcher at Eurocontrol (Belgium)

MSc Aeronautical Engineering / **BSc** Aerospace Engineering

Number of industrial accidents over time [1]

[1] European Union Joint Research Center (JRC), eMARS database, <https://emars.jrc.ec.europa.eu/en/emars/content>

On the need for
knowledge management

Safety perspective

ACCIDENTS

INCIDENTS

NEAR MISSES

DIKW

Weak Signals: Working definition

*“A seemingly random or disconnected piece of information that at first appears to be background noise but can be recognized as part of a **significant pattern** by viewing it through a different frame or connecting it with other pieces of information.”*

(Schoemaker & Day, 2009)

Weak Signal vs Indicator

Indicator (Strong signal)

Regular

Clearly visible

Precise and predictable

Clear and measurable

Stable

Weak signal

Random

Low visibility

Not predictable

Ambiguous

Variable

The need for a model

An example: The RE-SET project

Resilience Engineering for Safe Energy Transitions

The RESET project involves developing analysis and evaluation tools to assist **establishments in Seveso sector** towards energy transition, prioritizing **interventions** and identifying **actions for improvement**

STAMP

- Safety is a dynamic *control problem* *failure prevention problem*
- Accidents and incidents result from inadequate control or enforcement of safety related constraints on the development, design, and operation of the system

Patriarca, R. (2025)

STAMP atomic elements

- **Control actions** affect a controlled process
- **Feedback** may be used to monitor the controlled process
- **Process model** (beliefs) formed based on feedback and other sources
- **Control algorithm** determines appropriate control actions given current beliefs

STAMP control structure

Exemplary model

STAMP model of the Seveso Directive

...they look *very weak* signals
...if any

The need for an ontological approach

- Analyze the Directive's SCS
- Ontology's definition
 - Eight classes to label information
 - Four relationships between classes
 - No attributes nor sub-classes
- Translation of SCS into a KG

From the STAMP model to the knowledge graph

Exemplary results

- Which is the system element who sends the higher number of feedback?
- How many systems provide this value as a feedback?
- Which is the shortest sequence of elements to be informed to send a control action from a controller?
- etc.

Are these ones
the only **weak signals** available?

Link prediction (inductively)

Link prediction (inductively)

- ◆ Facility_A — STORES → Ammonium Nitrate
- ◆ Ammonium Nitrate — HAS_HAZARD → Explosion
- ? Facility_A — ? → Explosion (Missing link)

AI Predicts:
 Since similar facilities storing Ammonium Nitrate are at explosion risk...
 → Facility_A is likely at risk too.

Link prediction (simple logic)

Illustrative example of Multilayer perceptron, a Feedforward neural network

$$FL(p_t) = -(1 - p_t)^q \log(p_t)$$

$$BS = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N (f_t - o_t)^2$$

Source AIML.com Research

The need for further ontologies

Exemplary results: better decision-making!

- A facility would require shorter inspection intervals given it handles substance X under conditions C
- A facility that handles ammonia and stores it in conditions similar to others already linked to a “toxicity hazard” may be predicted to have the same hazard, even if it's not currently documented.
- Inspection 2024_XX is likely to detect non-compliance at Facility YYY
- Etc.

weak signals in other domains

The screenshot shows the SKYbrary website interface. The main article title is "Weak Signals Approach to ANSP Safety Performance". The introduction text reads: "Creating foresight, anticipating future threats and how to be prepared for possible future surprises are fundamental issues in managing today's complex socio-technical systems. Traditional safety approaches use after-the-event data to evaluate the organisation's safety level. This is based on the theoretical understanding that safety is seen as the absence of unwanted consequences. Consequently, managing safety is seen as the avoidance or elimination of negative outcomes. This safety approach follows the credo of improving safety by learning from errors and mishaps. Organisations with this understanding may learn from past events, but hardly pro-actively anticipate future threats. In the current complex socio-technical systems, traditional theories of safety that follow a structural view and focus only on the negative limit the understanding of the interactive complexity and dynamics are inherent in such systems. Only finding and counting human errors, failures or breakdowns is no appropriate way to get a better insight of how today's systems work and possibly fail. A better understanding of the interactions and couplings of system components is necessary. The following presentation illustrates the traditional approach of managing safety."

Article Information:
Category: Organisation and Human Performance
Content source: SKYbrary
Content control: SKYbrary

Weak Signals, (hopefully) strong message!

"A seemingly random or disconnected piece of information that at first appears to be background noise but can be recognized as part of a significant pattern by viewing it through a different frame or connecting it with other pieces of information."

(Schoemaker & Day, 2009)

🧠 KGs help us not only see what's there, but guess what should be there.

🚨 In Seveso oversight, that can mean identifying silent risks before they become loud disasters.

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Integrity Inspections at Industrial sites in the time of digital transition

By dr. Paolo Bragatto

Integrity Inspections at Industrial sites in the time of digital transition

Paolo Bragatto

Università Campus Biomedico Roma

66th ESReDA Seminar

May 22nd– 23rd 2025,

University of Salento, Lecce (Italy)

Summary

- i. Permanently installed Inspection systems
- ii. Systems with Autonomous Motion Capability
- iii. Strengths Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats.
- iv. New Inspection Techniques and Risk management

Overcome time limits

Overcome space limits

Overcome time limits

1. Permanently installed systems

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Permanently installed systems to measure anytime

the probability
of detection
PoD

NDT sensor miniaturized and connected

Reduce the time between inspections

Inspection anytime, anywhere

Automated process

Increasing PoD *probability of detection*

Early warning

Decrease fault Likelihood

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Continuous vibration monitoring

Vibration sensors, rotation sensors, and other specialized transducers are the most commonly used and effective options for this purpose

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5

Continuous corrosion monitoring with sensors plugged into pipes or vessels

UT sensors

AE sensors

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6

May, Z.; Alam, M.K.; Nayan, N.A. Recent Advances in Nondestructive Method and Assessment of Corrosion Undercoating in Carbon-Steel Pipelines. *Sensors* 2022, 22, 6654.

Wright, R. F., Lu, P., Devkota, J., Lu, F., Ziomek-Moroz, M., & Ohodnicki Jr, P. R. (2019). Corrosion sensors for structural health monitoring of oil and natural gas infrastructure: A review. *Sensors*, 19(18), 3964.

Bragatto, P., & Ansaldo, S. M. (2022). Cyber physical systems for occupational safety at industrial sites: opportunities and challenges. *Serbian Journal of Management*, 17(2), 451-461.

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Overcome space barriers

2. Systems with Autonomous Motion Capability

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Systems with Autonomous Motion Capability to measure at **impossible** positions

Reduce risks for operators

Entering where the operator will never be able to enter

Getting where the operator can't get

Measure from the inside

Increasing PoD *probability of detection*

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ii Systems with autonomous motion capability

PIG Pipeline Inspection Gauge

UT

MFL

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Classic Weels Caterpillar Suckers Little legs Worm Screw

Inspection Drones (Renewable Energy Windpower)

UAV
Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

ii systems with autonomous motion capability

1. Manual inspection 3 people 4-6 hours High PoD High Risk
2. Drone Inspection 1 Person 45 Minutes High PoD Low Risk
3. Ground Inspection 1 Persons 3-4 Hours Low Low PoD Low Risk

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Inspection Drones (Renewable Energy Photovoltaic farm)

UAV
Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

ii systems with autonomous motion capability

Shafiee, M.; Zhou, Z.; Mei, L.; Dinmohammadi, F.; Karama, J.; Flynn, D. Unmanned Aerial Drones for Inspection of Offshore Wind Turbines: A Mission-Critical Failure Analysis. Robotics 2021, 10, 26.

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ii systems with autonomous motion capability

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Images in the visible, thermal,
in microwaves etc.

Image processing

Feature Recognition

Deep Learning

Damage Detection

Omara, A.; Nasser, A.; Alsayed, A.; Nabawy, M.R.A. Remote Wind Turbine Inspections: Exploring the Potential of Multimodal Drones. *Drones* 2025, 9, 4.

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ii systems with autonomous motion capability

Drones for Inspections (fossil energy)

UAV Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

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Inspection robots

UT or MFL on-board sensors

Interior Tanks in stop emptied and cleaned

ii systems with autonomous motion capability

ROV Remotely Operated Vehicle

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**Marine
environment**

Visual and
instrumental
control

For oil and gas
pipelines,
platforms,
FSRUs, etc.

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ii systems with autonomous motion capability

Robotic
inspection of
atmospheric
storage tank
bottom in
service

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Ancione, G., Mennuti, C., Bragatto, P., Milazzo, M. F., & Proverbio, E. (2022). Application of statistical analysis for the identification of critical bottom areas due to corrosion in atmospheric storage tanks. *Chemical Engineering Transactions*, 90, 13-18.

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UT

MFL

2010

Every 10 years

Every 10 years

3	E	13.3	13.0	12.9	13.0	13.2	13.0	13.1	13.2
	D	13.5	13.5	13.4	13.3	13.5	13.9	13.7	13.6
	C	13.8	13.6	13.8	13.5	13.3	13.5	14.2	13.9
	B	13.6	13.1	13.5	13.4	12.6	13.5	14.0	13.6
	A	13.1	12.7	12.8	13.1	16.2	12.8	13.3	13.0
2	E	15.7	15.6	15.8	15.7	15.9	15.7	16.0	16.0
	D	15.8	15.8	15.9	15.7	15.8	15.7	16.0	16.0
	C	16.0	17.3	16.0	16.1	16.4	16.1	16.7	16.3
	B	16.1	17.6	16.0	16.3	16.0	16.1	16.6	16.2
	A	15.5	15.5	15.3	15.7	15.8	15.7	15.6	15.8
1	E	18.3	18.7	18.5	19.0	18.7	18.3	18.7	18.7
	D	19.0	19.4	18.5	19.5	19.1	19.0	19.1	19.2
	C	19.4	19.8	18.7	19.6	19.3	19.3	19.5	19.5
	B	19.2	19.4	18.6	19.5	19.1	19.0	18.8	19.5
	A	18.4	18.4	18.0	19.2	18.4	17.6	18.2	18.6

2025

Every year

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3. Strengths Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats.

Bragatto, P., Bemporad, E., Marrazzo, R., & Vallerotonda, M. R. (2024). Opportunities from Digital Transition for Integrity Inspection and Control of Major Accident Hazard. *Chemical Engineering Transactions*, 111, 61-66.

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Much More frequent Inspections

Inspections that would otherwise be very difficult or almost impossible

Lower costs,

Higher probability of damage detection

Early detection of damage,

Less failures and accidents

Less occupational risks

Growing Market

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Weaknesses

(Only for permanent systems) Positioning criticalities, in the Design phase

Reliability of electronic and mechanical systems

Interference, falls (for all mobile systems)

Human Robot collaboration (for all mobile systems)

ATEX problem (especially for drones)

Vulnerability for possible cyberattacks

Opportunities

Much more data to exploit in industrial practice

Integration with predictive modeling

Improved maintenance program, safe extension of useful life

Much more data to exploit in research

Edge Computing

Integration with other data

Advanced Analytics Method

Virtual and augmented reality

Augmented Reality

Virtual Reality

Ancione, G., Saitta, R., Bragatto, P., Fiumara, G., & Milazzo, M. F. (2023). The Use of Augmented Reality for the Management of Equipment Ageing with a Virtual Sensor. *Applied Sciences*, 13(13), 7843.

Treats

Not yet a standard to follow (UNI efforts)

Not yet recognized by regulators and competent authority

Not yet a shared approach to risk assessment and management

Possible effect on employment

4. New Inspection Techniques and Risk management

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How to account new Technologies in Risk Analysis?

FMECA Failure Mode Effect and Criticality Analysis

$$\text{Risk Priority Number (RPN)} = \text{O} \cdot \text{S} \cdot \text{D} \quad (1-1000)$$

S Severity severity of failure consequences
S=1 no discernible effect => S = 10 very Severe

O Occurrence likelihood of failure occurrence
F = 1 remote => F = 10 almost inevitable

D Detectability likelihood of failure detection
D =1 manifest damage => D = 10 Undetectable damage

D	chance to detect a potential cause mechanism and subsequent failure	
1	Almost Certain	99.9%
2	Very high	99.5%
3	High	99.0%
4	Moderately high	95.0%
5	Moderate	90.0%
6	Low	90.0%
7	Very low	80.0%
8	Remote	40.0%
9	Very Remote	20.0%
10	Absolutely Uncertain	0.0%

Item	Failure mode	Cause	Effect	S	O	D	RPN pre	Action taken	S	O	D	RPN post

*according to 60812 IEC:2006

Item	Failure mode	Cause	Effect	S O D			RPN pre	Action taken	S O D			RPN post
				S	O	D			S	O	D	
8 inches Insulated pipeline	casual rupture	CUI corrosion	loss of a material major accident	8	5	9	360	UT sensors on a critical point	8	5	3	120
								Fiber sensors	8	5	1	40

Item	Failure mode	Cause	Effect	S O D			RPN pre	Action taken	S O D			RPN post
				S	O	D			S	O	D	
40 inches crude oil external pipeline	casual rupture	erosion-corrosion	loss of a material major accident	6	5	8	240	PIG periodical inspections	6	5	2	60

Item	Failure mode	Cause	Effect	S	O	D	RPN pre	Action taken	S	O	D	RPN post
Atmospheric Storage Tank	Bottom casual rupture	Water, corrosion pitting trough-holes	loss of material environmental pollution	4	8	7	224	MFL sensors + Tank Inspection Rover	4	8	1	32

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Item	Failure mode	Cause	Effect	S	O	D	RPN pre	Action taken	S	O	D	RPN post
Flare	Misfunction,	thermal fatigue, fouling	accident in emergency	6	5	8	240	IR camera + drone	6	5	2	60

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Item	Failure mode	Cause	Effect	S	O	D	RPN pre	Action taken	S	O	D	RPN post
Furnace	cracking creep	thermal fatigue stress corrosion	rupture explosion	9	4	8	288	EC sensors + Climbing Robot	9	4	2	72

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Item	Failure mode	Cause	Effect	S	O	D	RPN pre	Action taken	S	O	D	RPN post
Compressor	blockage	fatigue wear	loss of material, discontinuity	4	8	4	96	Vibration Monitoring	4	8	1	32

Item	Failure mode	Cause	Effect	S	O	D	RPN pre	Action taken	S	O	D	RPN post
Compressor	blockage	fatigue wear	loss of material, discontinuity	4	8	4	96	Vibration Monitoring	4	8	1	32
8 inches Insulated pipeline	casual rupture	CUI corrosion	loss of a material major accident	8	5	9	360	UT pervasive sensors on a critical point	8	5	1	40
40 inches crude oil external pipeline	casual rupture	erosion-corrosion	loss of a material major accident	6	5	8	240	PIG periodical inspections	6	5	2	60
Furnace	cracking creep	thermal fatigue stress corrosion	rupture explosion	9	4	8	288	EC sensors + Climbing Robot	9	4	2	72
Atmospheric Distillation Tower	casual rupture	sulfidation stress corrosion	rupture major accident	9	3	7	189	EC sensors + Climbing Robot	9	2	1	36
Atmospheric Storage Tank (bottom)	casual rupture	pit corrosion trough-holes	loss of material major accident	4	8	7	224	MFL sensors + Tank Inspection Rover	4	8	1	32
Flare	misfunction	thermal fatigue, fouling	accident in emergency	6	5	8	240	IR camera + drone	6	5	2	60

Conclusions

Exponential development of digital inspection techniques is driven by the development of artificial intelligence

Artificial intelligence also provides the means for the enormous mass of data that is made available thanks to digital inspection techniques.

Some sensors, as we have seen, become so pervasive that they become one with the material.

Conclusions

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Renewable energy and digital inspections are an inseparable combination

Digital techniques are also essential for the problem of aging

The role of regulators and authorities is essential

Data engineering + Maintenance Engineering

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Grazie per l'attenzione

Thank you for your attention

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Plenary presentations

A framework for evaluating intralogistics safety through Discrete-Event Simulation

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Abstract

Internal logistics activities involve the coexistence of humans and mechanical vehicles, whose interactions may pose occupational safety risks. For instance, forklift operations may lead to incidents, among which the collisions between forklifts and pedestrians. Such incidents may cause serious injuries or even deaths. It follows that evaluating the risk and safety of intralogistics activities is fundamental. Discrete-Event Simulation (DES) is a popular technique for risk and safety assessment thanks to its flexibility and ability to incorporate other factors into the analysis (e.g., production schedule). However, in the context of intralogistics safety, DES is primarily used for preventing deadlocks and collisions of automated systems. Little interest has been devoted to evaluating risk and safety indicators in scenarios where humans are also present. This work wants to fill this gap by developing an approach that allows to estimate the number of human-vehicle and vehicle-vehicle collisions and near misses through DES. This evaluation technique can be used to evaluate weaknesses and opportunities for improvement in case safety requirements are not satisfied.

1. Introduction

The safety of internal logistics activities is a prominent topic. Indeed, there are several works dealing with obstacle recognition and path planning of autonomous or automated vehicles [1–3]. The former works may also deal with deadlock and congestion avoidance. Other studies include human operators or human-operated vehicles in the safety or risk assessment [4–6]. In the context of intralogistics, DES can be adopted to conduct safety or risk assessment. DES allows to obtain high flexibility and include several aspects influencing the logistics operations (e.g., production schedule). Most of the DES-based works consider non-human operated vehicles, such as [7,8]. Human operators are usually neglected, even though they are considered in non-DES studies. Similarly, near misses are commonly overlooked in a DES environment, and they are rarely considered in non-DES studies. The present work wants to cover the previous gaps.

2. Methodology

The present work considers three main elements moving in a logistic environment: i) human operators, ii) forklifts, and iii) trucks. The elements are usually forced to move along pre-determined paths (e.g., roads for trucks or pedestrian pavements). The paths may form intersections, which cause interferences among elements. For instance, different elements may cross the same intersection at the same moment leading to a collision. A different kind of interference is the near miss, which means that two elements are crossing the intersection almost at the same time. Collisions and near misses are the two risk events that are included for the safety assessment in the present study.

It is worth noting that the hazardousness of a given intersection is strongly related to the elements crossing them. For instance, an intersection formed by two paths both travelled by human operators is not hazardous. Vice versa, an intersection is regarded as hazardous if a truck moves along a path and the other path is travelled by a human operator. Indeed, collisions between a truck and a human operator may cause injuries or even deaths of the human operator. Based on the former considerations, it is fundamental to identify different intersection categories depending on the elements crossing them. The intersection categories considered in the present study are illustrated in Figure 1.

In addition to the intersection categories identified based on the crossing elements, the intersections can be classified according to the angle formed between the paths. In the present study, only cross-intersections (90° angle between the paths) are considered. These are intersections associated with high risk of collisions and, thus, they were selected [9].

Figure 1. Intersection categories included in the present study.

2.1 Intersection modelling

Each path forming an intersection is divided into different segments, identified through stations [10,11]. These stations are fundamental for conducting the risk assessment since they are used to estimate the number of accidents and near misses. The stations alongside the paths are shown in Figure 2. The meaning of each station is as follows:

1. $StartVisibV_i$: from this station, the element crossing the intersection is visible
2. $LastStopV_i$: from this station, the element crossing cannot stop and avoid the accident as mentioned in other studies [12].
3. $StartInterfV_i$: from this station, there may be interference between the vehicles crossing the intersection.
4. $EndInterfV_i$: from this station, there cannot be interference between the vehicles crossing the intersection.

The distance between the station $StartInterfV_i$ and $EndInterfV_i$ is set equal to the length of the element that is moving alongside the paths. In case a path is associated with a human operator, the distance between the former two stations is given by the width of the other element crossing the intersection (i.e., width of the truck or forklift). It is also assumed that only one element at a time may be present between $LastStopV_i$ and $EndInterfV_i$.

To estimate the risk indicators and perform the safety assessment (i.e., the number of collisions and near misses) a set of binary variables is introduced. First, the variable $TransV_iVisible$ indicates if the element crossing the intersection alongside the i -th path is visible or not. It is set equal to 1 if the element is visible, while it is 0 otherwise. The variables $TransV_iNotLastStop$ specifies whether the elements travelling the i -th path is between $StartVisib_i$ and $LastStop_i$. Similarly, $TransV_iOccupV_i$ defines if the element of the i -th path is between $LastStopV_i$ and $EndInterf_i$. Both the former variables are equal to 1 if the element is between the respective stations and 0 otherwise. The variable $TransV_iInterf$ is set equal to 1 if the element of the i -th path is between $StartInterf_i$ and $EndInterf_i$. Finally, the variable $TransV_iStopped$ indicates whether the elements has stopped at $LastStop_i$. Based on the values assumed by the former variables, the number of collisions and near misses are determined. The main difference between accidents and near misses is related to the counting process. There is an accident if both the elements are between $StartInterf_i$ and $EndInterf_i$, which means that $TransV_iInterf$ is equal to 1 for both elements. On the other hand, if an element stops before entering the interference area because another element is already present, the number of near misses is incremented.

Figure 2. Stations characterising the paths of an intersection.

2.2 Principles of the developed library

The former aspects must be introduced in a DES environment. To this end, a library is developed for Rockwell Arena®. The library is integrated with existing in-built libraries that allow to generate logistic paths travelled by different elements. The paths form intersections, to which the developed library is applied. The developed library is composed of a main template, named “CrossMachMach”, and two data structures: “TransporterEntOn” and “CrossDistances”. The first data structure includes the elements to model (i.e., trucks, forklifts, and humans), while the second data structure defines the distances between stations. The relationship among the former elements and the main outputs of the library are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Relationship among the key elements of the developed library.

3. Results

To demonstrate the application of the methodology and the insights that can be obtained, it is tested on a case study. The case study is the end part of a production part that includes four production lines (PLs). Each production line is dedicated to a different product family. A schematic representation of the plant is shown in Figure 4. The end part of the production plant is quite complex in terms of logistics flows. Indeed, there are several paths that each production

line generates. First, each production line is operated by an operator. Moreover, the products realised by a production line are transported to nearby buffers (i.e., B1 and B2 of Figure 4) or to an external warehouse. These activities may be conducted through trucks or forklifts. In both cases, there are additional humans that drive the trucks or forklifts.

Figure 4. Schematic representation of the layout of the considered case study.

Depending on which production line is operating, different intersections are formed. To generate the simulation model, production data are acquired, and the typical production schedule is generated in the simulation environment. The production schedule triggers movements of operators, trucks, and forklifts. This, in turn, may lead to accidents or near misses where the paths of two elements intersect each other. A year of operations (i.e., 8,760 hours) is simulated through four independent simulation runs. Then, the average values of accidents and near misses of each intersection are calculated.

Through the average number of accidents and near misses, the intersections are ranked based on criticality. Regarding the accidents, only few intersections were characterised by them. The intersection characterised by the highest number of accidents is a forklift-forklift intersection, and it experiences about 9 accidents per year. On the other hand, most of the intersections were characterised by near misses as shown in Figure 5. Intersection M is characterised by the average highest number of near misses and accidents.

Different categories of criticality can be determined by defining threshold values over which the number of near misses is considered unacceptable. Given a set of intersections with a criticality level exceeding the thresholds, different countermeasures can be adopted. First, different paths may be planned. This is the best option for avoiding interferences, but it is not always viable. If the former option is unfeasible or too complex, it is possible to reduce the

speed limits of vehicles. The reduction in speed limit may lead to reduction in accidents. To verify that, a new simulation must be conducted to assess whether the risk is below the threshold values.

4. Conclusions

It is fundamental to guarantee the safety of internal logistics. To this end, the present work presents an approach to estimate the risk as the number of accidents and near misses. This task is conducted in a DES environment. The present study provides also a library in Rockwell ARENA[®] to facilitate the transition from theory to practice.

From a theoretical perspective, this work includes near misses in the evaluation of logistics safety. Similarly, it provides a new framework to evaluate the safety of internal logistics activities, involving also human operators. From a practical perspective, managers are provided with a tool and a DES library to assess the risk of the intralogistics operations.

The present paper has also limitations. For instance, only one kind of intersection is considered. Thus, future studies may extend the approach to other intersections. Similarly, the library was developed for a single DES software. Therefore, future works may reproduce the library for other simulation software.

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Bijection Mapping of Probabilistic Discrete Variables to Support Decision Making – A case study

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Abstract

Within the operational context of airports' customs and passengers' bags inspection, the intrusive inspection decision is required to be rationalised and based on risk assessment methods supported by advanced non-intrusive detection technologies, data processing sciences, and AI techniques.

A smart probabilistic model is proposed in this paper to perform a bijective mapping between two dependent sets of data of different sizes. The dependence between elements in both sets is governed by a well-defined probabilistic transfer function. The concerned sets are two photo-sets of suit bags. The first set comprises the photos of bags annotated as risky after their passage through X-scanners in the conveyor zone, on arrival. The second set comprises the photos of bags arrived in the carousel zone to be delivered to the passengers.

An automatic matching assessment between the two photos sets is applied to reidentify the risky bags on its delivery in the carousel zone and produces a matching correspondence between the photos in both sets. The proposed probabilistic mapping (/correspondence) model is designed to determine the best correspondence between the photos in both sets.

The customs decision of intrusive inspection will be based on the best matching mapping determined by the proposed model. A downscaled case is presented to illustrate how the model determines the best bijective mapping.

1. Introduction

The WCO (World Customs Organisation) recommends that luggage intrusive inspections should be limited. A Risk Management Guide has, then, been developed by the WCO, (WCO, 2003, [1]). It defines risk management as “the **systematic** determination of risk management **priorities** by **evaluating** and **comparing** the **level of risk** against **predetermined standards, target risk-levels** or other criteria”, (WCO, 2003b).

In line with WCO's recommendations, the European Commission released a Communication on the EU Strategy and Action Plan for customs risk management entitled “Tackling risks, strengthening supply chain security and facilitating trade”, on 21 August 2014 (COM-2014 527 final, [2], and COM-2014 527 final-Annexe-1, [3]). The detailed EU action plan is given in (COM – 2014 527 final-Annexe1, [3]). Three monitoring progress reports on “the Implementation of the EU Strategy and Action Plan for Customs Risk Management” have been published following the COM – 2014 527, (1st Prog Rep in 2016 [4], 2nd Prog Rep in 2018 [5], and 3rd Prog Rep in 2021, [6]).

A smart probabilistic model is proposed in this technical paper to perform a bijective mapping between two dependent sets of data of different sizes. The dependence between elements in both sets is governed by a well-defined probabilistic transfer function. The transfer function is called the matching scores function.

The most probable correspondence between the data elements in both sets is required to make the best rational inspection decision. The best decision is based on the most probable bijective mapping from one set to the other.

Then, a smart probabilistic model is proposed in this technical paper to perform a bijective mapping between two dependent sets of data of different sizes. The concerned sets are two photo-sets of suit bags. The first set comprises the photos of bags annotated as risky after their passage through X-scanners in the conveyor zone, on flight arrival. The second set comprises the photos of bags on arrival in the carousel zone to be delivered to the flight passengers.

The case presumes a decision that should be taken by customs officers to intercept and intrusively inspect risky bags. Risky bags are annotated as risky by an X-scanner and their 1st photos are thus taken in the conveyor zone and collected in a first set of photos to be used for bags identification. Second photos of all bags are taken on arrival in the carousel zone and collected in a second set of photos to be used for the reidentification of risky bags. An IA system determines matching scores between risky bags in the first set of identifying photos and the photos in the second set of reidentifying photos.

The proposed case is down-scaled so that it preserves the didactic objective of this technical paper. The proposed case considers only five identifying photos of risky bags to be reidentified using only eight reidentifying photos.

2. Mathematical Background

In a general decision-making problem, the issue is to make the best trade-off between an initial dataset whose data elements are $\{D_i, i \in [1, N_D]\}$ and another searched outcome dataset $\{O_j, j \in [1, N_O]\}$. The elements in the datasets $\{D_i\}$ and $\{O_j\}$ are generally not mutually exclusive, within each set. The N_D and N_O are the total numbers of data elements in each set. The bijective likelihood between the datasets $\{D_i\}$ and $\{O_j\}$ is determined through a transfer-scores matrix $\{s_{i,j}, j \in [1, N_O], i \in [1, N_D]\}$. Higher is the score $s_{i,j}$ higher will be the bijective correspondence between D_i and O_j .

This problem can be classified as a bijective mapping between two dependent datasets $\{D_i, i \in [1, N_D]\}$ and $\{O_j, j \in [1, N_O]\}$. The dependence between the two datasets is determined by a probability transfer matrix $\{s_{i,j}, j \in [1, N_O], i \in [1, N_D]\}$. The probability space is then well defined by the triplite (D, O, S) . The issue is then to find out the most likely bijective mapping and to assess its global likelihood.

The decision-maker need then to determine:

- The best bijective correspondence between the sets $\{D_i\}$ and $\{O_j\}$, and
- A performance indicator of the decision-making process

The “probabilistic mapping between two dependent datasets” is met through different system-engineering fields, such as: “the analysis of failure patterns, their effects and criticality”, diagnosis & prognosis, risk analysis (complex systems engineering, financial engineering, decisional processes) ...etc.

In this technical note, the authors present a case study, inspired from objects identification & recognition using photos matching correspondences.

Although the methodology used is fully based on the probability theory and applied statistics, it is inspired by the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method regarding the scoring procedure. The AHP was developed by T. L. Saaty in 1971- 1975 (Wharton School – University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia), (T.L. Saaty, 1987), [7]. Besides, one may recommend other two papers (Pereyra -Rojas, M., 2017, [8]), and (L. Hammadi et al., 2016,[9]) that are written in didactic manner.

More details about this work are given in (Lamia Hammadi et al., 2025,[10]).

3. Investigated Case

The presented case is related to the identification of risky bags that should be intrusively inspected by customs officers in airports. On flights arrival, suit bags are transferred to the bags' delivery zone through a series of conveyors before joining the carrousel belts that are leading to the right delivery zone. In the conveyors zone, suit bags' contents are non-intrusively examined by sniffer-dogs and/or X-scanners, just before or after being photographed. If a suit bag's examination revealed the presence of doubtful contents, the concerned suit bag's photo is annotated as risky one. All the suit bags (risky or not) are re-photographed once more during its trajectory to the customs control zone. An automatic photos' matching process, between the 1st set of photos of the risky bags and all the photos of the 2nd set, is systematically carried out. The risky suit bags should be reasonably reidentified on arrival in the customs control zone. Then, customs' officers may decide to intercept the bag and go through the intrusive inspection. The automatic identification process should be quick and reliable using modern AI techniques and tools.

A smart probabilistic model is proposed to assess & optimise the customs intrusive inspection decision making process based of the IA photos-matching process between two photos-sets of suit bags taken in the conveyers' zone and near to the customs control zone.

The proposed model is developed by the LMN – INSA Rouen (France).

3.1 Case Modelling & Input Data

A didactic academic case is proposed to demonstrate the methodology applied by the bijective mapping model to determine the most likely bijective mapping in risky bags. We recall that two dependant photos sets' matching is assessed using AI techniques and tools whose results are the probabilistic matching scores, given in Table 1. The Table represents the fact that one identified risky bag (in the 1st photos-set) may match with more than one photo in the 2nd photos-set, and vis-versa.

The proposed case is a reduced case to preserve the didactic aspect of the technical note. Subsequently only five risky bags are to be reidentified using eight reidentifying photos. The scalability of the model to real field cases is straight forward.

Table 1 : Matching scores* between the 1st photos-set (conveyor zone) and the 2nd photos-set (carrousel zone)

1 st photos-set	2 nd set photo-A	2nd set photos-B	2nd set Photos-C	2nd set photo-D	2nd set photo-E	2nd set photo-F	2nd set photo-G	2nd set photo-H
Risky_Bag_1	20%	5%	80%		30%	5%		
Risky_Bag_2		20%		70%	15%			75%
Risky_Bag_3	60%			30%		90%	70%	
Risky_Bag_4	50%		10%		10%	60%	20%	10%
Risky_Bag_5		10%	30%	15%			65%	15%

*The Matching scores are the matching probabilities estimated by an AI data analysis algorithm

3.2 Determination of the Most Likely Bijective Mapping

Amongst the 2nd set of 8 photos {A,B,C,D,E,F,G} only five photos should fit with the five risky bags identified in the 1st set of photos (in the vicinity of the X-scanner – in the conveyor zone). To extract only five photos out of eight, one should choose amongst 56 possible subsets of only five photos ($\binom{8!}{(5!)(3!)} = 56$). All these 56 possible subsets are not equiprobable. Then, one can rationally choose the most probable set amongst the 56 subsets.

The process of identifying the most probable bijective mapping is described through the algorithm given in Table 2.

Table 2 : The algorithm of the determination of the most probable bijective mapping

1.	Get the probabilistic matching score's values ($\pi_{ij}, i \in [1,5], j \in [1,8]$), see Table 1, above
2.	Continue
3.	Determine for each photo j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, 8$) the probability of non-matching with any of the five bags Q_j , as following:
	$Q_j = \prod_{i=1}^5 (1 - \pi_{ij})$
4.	Determine the probability of matching with at least one bag P_j for each photo j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, 8$), such as:
	$P_j = 1 - Q_j$
5.	Determine the photo J_{max} that corresponds to either the highest matching probability P_j or the lowest non-matching probability Q_j .
6.	Determine for each bag i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$) (amongst the potential 5 bags) the probability of non-matching with any of the eight photos Q_i , as following:
	$Q_i = \prod_{j=1}^8 (1 - \pi_{ij})$
7.	Determine the probability of matching with at least one photo P_i for all the bags ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$), such as:
	$P_i = 1 - Q_i$
8.	Determine the bag I_{max} that corresponds to either the highest matching probability P_i or the lowest non-matching probability Q_i .

9. Then, the most likely matching is at the cross of Bag_ I_{max} (row I_{max}) and Photo_ J_{max} (column J_{max}) with a matching score $\pi_{I_{max}J_{max}}$
10. Store Bag_ I_{max} and Photo_ J_{max} with the matching score $\pi_{I_{max}J_{max}}$
11. Switch to zero all the scores in row I_{max} and column J_{max}
12. Goto step 13 if no bags left without re-identification **OR** if no reidentifying photos left
Otherwise Goto2
13. Report
 - 13.1 If no bags left (msg: "There are photos for non-identified bags"), or
 - 13.2 If no photos left (msg: "There are identified bags without reidentifying photos"), or
 - 13.3 (msg: "All bags have been re-identified").
14. End
15. Stop

3.3 The numerical application

We recall that the proposed case is purposely reduced to five risky-bags photos in the first photos set and eight reidentifying photos in the second photos set, table 1.

The application of the above algorithm to determine the most probable bijective mapping is presented step by step, below in Tables (3-a,-b,-c,-d,-e).

Table 3-a : 1st Step – the most likely bijective correspondence is Risky_Bag_3 → Photo-F (90%)

1 st photos-set	2 nd set photo-A	2 nd set photos-B	2 nd set Photos-C	2 nd set photo-D	2 nd set photo-E	2 nd set photo-F	2 nd set photo-G	2 nd set photo-H	At Least One Photo Matches
Risky_Bag_1	20.0%	5.0%	80.0%		30.0%	5.0%			89.9%
Risky_Bag_2		20.0%		70.0%	15.0%			75.0%	94.9%
Risky_Bag_3	60.0%			30.0%		90.0%	70.0%		99.2%
Risky_Bag_4	50.0%		10.0%		10.0%	60.0%	20.0%	10.0%	88.3%
Risky_Bag_5		10.0%	30.0%	15.0%			65.0%	15.0%	84.1%
At Least One Bag Matches	84.0%	31.6%	87.4%	82.2%	46.5%	96.2%	91.6%	80.9%	

Table 3-b : 2nd Step – the most likely bijective correspondence is Risky_Bag_2 → Photo-H (75%)

1 st photos-set	2 nd set photo-A	2 nd set photos-B	2 nd set Photos-C	2 nd set photo-D	2 nd set photo-E	2 nd set photo-F	2 nd set photo-G	2 nd set photo-H	At Least One Photo Matches
Risky_Bag_1	20.0%	5.0%	80.0%		30.0%				89.4%
Risky_Bag_2		20.0%		70.0%	15.0%			75.0%	94.9%
Risky_Bag_3									0.0%
Risky_Bag_4	50.0%		10.0%		10.0%		20.0%	10.0%	70.8%
Risky_Bag_5		10.0%	30.0%	15.0%			65.0%	15.0%	84.1%
At Least One Bag Matches	60.0%	31.6%	87.4%	74.5%	46.5%	0.0%	72.0%	80.9%	

Table 3-C : 3rd Step – the most likely bijective correspondence is Risky_Bag_1 → Photo-C (80%)

1 st photos-set	2 nd set photo-A	2 nd set photos-B	2 nd set Photos-C	2 nd set photo-D	2 nd set photo-E	2 nd set photo-F	2 nd set photo-G	2 nd set photo-H	At Least One Photo Matches
Risky_Bag_1	20.0%	5.0%	80.0%		30.0%				89.4%
Risky_Bag_2									0.0%
Risky_Bag_3									0.0%

Risky_Bag_4	50.0%		10.0%		10.0%		20.0%		67.6%
Risky_Bag_5		10.0%	30.0%	15.0%			65.0%		81.3%
At Least One Bag Matches	60.0%	14.5%	87.4%	15.0%	37.0%	0.0%	72.0%	0.0%	

Table 3-D : 4th Step – the most likely bijective correspondence is Risky_Bag_5 → Photo-G (65%)

1 st photos-set	2 nd set photo-A	2 nd set photos-B	2 nd set Photos-C	2 nd set photo-D	2 nd set photo-E	2 nd set photo-F	2 nd set photo-G	2 nd set photo-H	At Least One Photo Matches
Risky_Bag_1									0.0%
Risky_Bag_2									0.0%
Risky_Bag_3									0.0%
Risky_Bag_4	50.0%				10.0%		20.0%		64.0%
Risky_Bag_5		10.0%		15.0%			65.0%		73.2%
At Least One Bag Matches	50.0%	10.0%	0.0%	15.0%	10.0%	0.0%	72.0%	0.0%	

Table 3-E : 5th Step – the most likely bijective correspondence is Risky_Bag_4 → Photo-A (50%)

1 st photos-set	2 nd set photo-A	2 nd set photos-B	2 nd set Photos-C	2 nd set photo-D	2 nd set photo-E	2 nd set photo-F	2 nd set photo-G	2 nd set photo-H	At Least One Photo Matches
Risky_Bag_1									0.0%
Risky_Bag_2									0.0%
Risky_Bag_3									0.0%
Risky_Bag_4	50.0%				10.0%				55.0%
Risky_Bag_5									0.0%
At Least One Bag Matches	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	10.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	

Three photos are rejected: Photo_B, Photo_D, and Photo_E. The most likely bijective mapping is then given in Table 4, below.

Table 4 : the most probable bijective mapping pattern between the 5 risky bags and the 8 photos of the 1st and the 2nd lists

Identifying Photo	Reidentifying Photo	Score	Comments
Risky_Bag_1	Photo_C	80%	
Risky_Bag_2	Photo_H	75%	
Risky_Bag_3	Photo_F	90%	
Risky_Bag_4	Photo_A	50%	Bag_4 may fit with photo F with a score 60%. But photo F does most likely fit with Bag_3 with a higher score of 90%
Risky_Bag_5	Photo_G	65%	

4. Conclusion

A smart probabilistic model is proposed in this paper to perform a bijective mapping between two dependent sets of discrete data of different sizes. The dependence between elements from both sets is governed by a well-defined probabilistic transfer function. The most probable correspondence between the data elements in both sets is required to make the best rational decision. The best decision is based on the most probable bijective mapping from one set to the other. A down-scaled case is used to illustrate how the proposed model is applied. The proposed case is down-

scaled so that it preserves the didactic objective of the paper. The proposed case considers only five identifying photos of risky bags to be reidentified using only eight reidentifying photos.

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Risk identification in logistic cyber-social-technical systems

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Introduction

Risk identification is the first step in the risk assessment procedure according to ISO 31000:2018. It aims to define all relevant adverse events that should be subject to risk assessment analyses. The procedure result should be a structured list of adverse events considering the present risk's source and nature.

This paper aims to present a new framework for the risk identification process in cyber-social- technical systems, using the example of a selected logistics system. The proposed approach considers the new conditions for realising logistics processes increasingly handled by cyber- socio-technical systems. These new conditions for the realisation of logistics processes critically affect the risks present in the studied systems, which need to be considered at all stages of their assessment.

A new approach to risk identification in cyber-socio-technical systems

The complexity of CST logistics systems means that four types of layers can be distinguished that affect the correctness and continuity of the assigned tasks. These layers are (1) human factors, (2) technical, (3) digital, and (4) environmental. The risk identification process should include an analysis of each of the highlighted layers that may represent a source of occurrence of an adverse event in the planning and execution phase of the process.

Based on the analytical context defined in this way, the risk identification process should consider the matrix arrangement of layers shown in Figure 1

Fig.1. Matrix arrangement of analytical layers as a context for the conducted risk identification

The framework of the risk identification process based on the indicated matrix layout is based on a 5-step procedure: STEP 1: Process analysis of the implementation phase. STEP 2: Decision making analysis of the planning phase. STEP 3: Identification of adverse events. STEP 4: Classification of adverse events according to the analytical layers STEP 5: Categorisation of adverse events according to the nature of the risk

Case study

This paper will present the adverse event identification process results for a selected CST logistics system handling material flows at a manufacturer in the automotive sector. The identification process was carried out according to the proposed risk identification framework described in Section 2.

Soft Sensor For The Prediction Of The Composition Of The Atmosphere In The Flammable Liquid Tank

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Abstract

In the process industry, large quantities of flammable liquids are stored in tanks. To keep the tanks safe, the internal atmosphere is made non-flammable with the addition of an inert gas. But in case of malfunction the air can enter making the atmosphere flammable. In these cases it is essential to know the composition of the internal atmosphere.

In these cases, direct measurement of composition may be impractical or unreliable. For this reason, the development of a soft sensor is presented in this article. The soft sensor measures a series of variables estimating the composition of the atmosphere.

The developed soft sensor uses neural networks to estimate the composition. The prediction quality was tested in several examples of reservoir operation.

1. Introduction

The storage of flammable liquids is a common practice. There are several solutions that can be used for safe storage, one of which is blanketing. Blanketing is a common technique in the industry for storing flammable liquids safely (De Paola and Messina, 1984, Crow and Louvar, 2002). An inert gas, typically nitrogen, is introduced into the tank to prevent the headspace from becoming flammable. A balance valve maintains pressure control within the tank. If pressure drops (e.g., during emptying without inert gas flow), the valve allows air to enter. Conversely, if pressure rises (e.g., during filling), the valve releases excess vapor, functioning similarly to a Pressure Safety Valve (PSV).

Prolonged air ingress can render the tank's atmosphere flammable (Baldissone et al., 2022, Baldissone et al., 2020). Therefore, understanding the vapor phase composition is crucial for safe operation.

Direct measurement of the tank's atmosphere would necessitate equipment designed to operate in potentially explosive environments. Additionally, due to the tank's size and lack of mixing or convection, a single point measurement might not accurately represent the composition in other areas. This could lead to hazardous conditions.

An alternative to direct composition measurement, which necessitates equipment suitable for potentially flammable environments, is a soft sensor. This sensor estimates composition based on measurements of other variables.

A soft sensor uses measurements of other variables and a mathematical model to predict the value of a specific variable (Fortuna et al. 2007). Soft sensors have been applied in safety-critical areas, such as monitoring hazardous gases in industrial plants. One example is the work of Xibilia et al. (2020), who developed a soft sensor for this purpose.

Soft sensors can be based on different types of mathematical models. One the more used mathematical model is the Neural Network.

In this paper, a first example of the development of a soft sensor for the estimation of the internal composition of a tank containing methanol is presented. The developed soft sensor uses neural networks for the estimation of the composition. A dynamic first-principles model of the tank was used to develop the soft sensor, both for the training of the neural networks and for the confirmation of the measurements.

2. Case study

The case study involves a cylindrical tank used to store methanol (**Figure 5**). The tank has a capacity of 100 m³ and is approximately 5.3 m tall. Methanol is continuously removed from the tank at a rate of 245 kg/h to be used in a downstream process. Nitrogen is added at a rate around of 0.31 kg/h to maintain the desired pressure. When the methanol level drops below 30%, the tank is refilled to 80% of its capacity. A balance valve is installed to prevent overpressure (above 7 kPa) or under pressure (below 1 kPa).

Figure 5. Tank scheme

2.1 Dynamic model

In the tank model are used the dynamic global mass balance Eq. (1).

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{dN^L}{dt} = N_{L,in} - N_{L,out} - A \cdot \phi \\ \frac{dN^V}{dt} = N_{Nit,in} + N_{Air,in} + A \cdot \phi - N_{V,out} \\ V_{TOT} = V_L - V_V \\ V_L = A \cdot l \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

The variables in the equation are defined as follows: N^l is the number of moles of liquid in the tank, $N_{L,in}$ and $N_{L,out}$ are the flow rates of liquid methanol entering and leaving the tank, A is the tank area, Φ is the mass transfer rate between the liquid and gas phases, N^V is the number of moles of gas in the tank, $N_{Nit,in}$ and $N_{Air,in}$ are the flow rates of nitrogen and air entering the tank, $N_{V,out}$ is the flow rate of gas leaving the tank, V_{TOT} is the total tank volume, V_L is the liquid volume, V_V is the gas volume, and l is the liquid level.

The composition of the atmosphere inside the tank is evaluated using Eq. (2).

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dN_{Nit}^V}{dt} = N_{Nit,in} + N_{Air,in} \cdot y_{Air,Nit} - N_{V,out} \cdot y_{Nit} \\ \frac{dN_{Ox}^V}{dt} = N_{Air,in} \cdot y_{Air,Ox} - N_{V,out} \cdot y_{Ox} \\ \frac{dN_{Met}^V}{dt} = A \cdot \phi - N_{V,out} \cdot y_{Met} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Where N_{Nit}^V , N_{Ox}^V , and N_{Met}^V are the number of moles of nitrogen, oxygen, and methanol in the gas phase, respectively. $y_{Air,Nit}$, $y_{Air,Ox}$, y_{Nit} , y_{Ox} , and y_{Met} are the concentrations of nitrogen, oxygen, and methanol in the air and in the tank gas phase.

The ideal gas equation is used for the pressure (P) evaluation Eq. (3):

$$P \cdot V_L = N^V \cdot R \cdot T \quad (3)$$

The Eq. 4 is used to evaluate the vapor flow between the liquid and gas phases.

$$\phi = k_{Met}^V (y_{Met}^* - y_{Met}) \quad (4)$$

where k_{Met}^V is the mass transfer coefficient between liquid and gas phase, y_{Met}^* is the equilibrium concentration of methanol in the gas phase.

The gas and air flow rate through the relief valve is calculated using the API 12000:1998 standard.

2.2 Soft sensor

The developed soft sensor is based on the use of two neural networks, one that models the composition of nitrogen and the other of methanol vapors in the atmosphere inside the tank. The structure of the soft sensor is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Soft sensor structure

Each neural network consists of a hidden layer formed by 10 nodes. Each neural network uses as input variables the incoming and outgoing liquid methanol flow rates, the incoming nitrogen flow rate and the liquid level. One neural network returns the fraction of nitrogen in the atmosphere and the other the concentration of methanol vapors. The neural networks return the average compositions of the atmosphere, value in line with what can be physically measured. In future evolutions of the sensor, it will be refined to have an indication of the most critical conditions as well.

The prediction quality is estimated through Eq. 5 that evaluate the mean prediction error (e_i) and the maximum prediction error (E_i), these values are estimated for both methanol and nitrogen concentration.

$$\begin{cases} E_i = \max_{0 \leq t \leq m} (|x_{i,m}(t) - x_{i,p}(t)|) \\ e_o = \frac{\sum_{t=0}^m |x_{i,m}(t) - x_{i,p}(t)|}{m} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $x_{i,m}$ is the component i concentration measured in percentage, $x_{i,p}$ is the component i concentration predicted in percentage.

2.3 Training set

The neural network was trained using a data set of 125,000 data points, with methanol (120 – 370 kg/h) and nitrogen (0 – 0.5 kg/h) flow rates varying within specific ranges and undergoing step changes (Figure 7). The dynamic model described earlier (Eq. 1-4) was used for the development of the training set. Due to the system's inertia, it was not feasible to use random input sequence generation. Instead, a pre-defined data set was employed as a training criterion.

Figure 7. Methanol and nitrogen input flow in the training data set

In the case of training data set the soft sensor model the two concentration (Figure 8) in the correct way. For the nitrogen the maximum prediction error is 1.22% and the mean error 0.03% also for the methanol the maximum prediction error is around 0.09% and the mean error around 0.003%.

Figure 8. Methanol and nitrogen concentration in the tank atmosphere for the training dataset

2.4 Confirmation case

As example the case of the step change reduction to the 40% 0.12 kg/h of nitrogen flow rate. Figure 9 show the input flow used for the soft sensor test.

Figure 9. Methanol and nitrogen input flow in the case study data set

Figure 10 show the concentration trend for the methanol and nitrogen, the soft sensor present a correct trend for the two concentration. The Figure 10 show also the prediction error trend for both the concentration in the tank atmosphere, for the methanol vapor the mean prediction error is around 0.003% and maximum around 0.10% and the for the nitrogen concentration the mean error is around 0.038% and the maximum error is around 0.51%.

Figure 10. Methanol and nitrogen concentration in the tank atmosphere and prediction error

As shown in Figure 10, the soft sensor correctly predicts the composition of the tank's internal atmosphere in a case study different from the training data set. This demonstrates the soft sensor's ability to provide an acceptable prediction even during discontinuities in the input values.

3. Conclusion

In this paper, a soft sensor is presented to estimate the composition of the internal atmosphere of a tank containing a flammable liquid. The soft sensor performs this estimation starting from the values of liquid flow rate (input and output), nitrogen flow rate and liquid level. In this way, it is possible to estimate the reaching of dangerous conditions in case of air entering. The proposed soft sensor has been tested in a case study concerning a methanol tank. In this case, the soft sensor proves to accurately predict the composition of the internal atmosphere of the tank in several cases. An alternative to the soft sensor is the direct measurement of the composition of the atmosphere inside the tank. However, this would require equipment capable of operating in potentially explosive environments. Additionally, given the size of the tanks and the lack of mixing or convective motions, point measurements may not be representative of the composition at other locations, which could lead to hazardous conditions. Currently, the proposed soft sensor offers an estimate of the average composition of the atmosphere inside the tank. The data provided by the soft sensor is more reliable than that obtained through point measurements, as it is less susceptible to local conditions."

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Towards the adoption of a systemic perspective for safe inspections at industrial sites

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1. Introduction

Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UASs) are defined as any aircraft that operate, or are designed to operate, autonomously or to be piloted remotely without a pilot on board [1]. Currently, they are employed in a variety of use cases for several purposes, including the medical good delivery and building inspection [2]. The use of these vehicles also facilitates non-destructive explorations and the acquisition of high-quality data of equipment conditions, enabling the execution of inspections at industrial sites. It prevents workers from entering hazardous spaces, and increases activity efficiency [2]. However, integrating UASs in industrial settings introduces emergent air and ground risks that should be properly managed to achieve tolerable safety levels. To this end, the technical, human, and organisational elements continuously interacting with each other for the conduction of the operations should be taken into account and modelled. The complex socio-technical nature of these systems necessitates the adoption of systemic approaches to accurately operationalise the safety risk management process. In line with modern risk management initiatives, this field has been investigated also by means of system-theoretic approaches (e.g., Pappot and de Boer [3], Milerová et al. [4], Stádník et al. [5], and Go et al. [6]). Yet, this type of investigation remains limited and no evidence is published about assessing risks related to the inspection design and operations in areas within industrial systems via UASs. Therefore, this contribution aims at embracing a systemic perspective to develop a Safety Control Structure (SCS) to represent the process for designing and conducting safe inspections by means of UASs in a generic industrial plant.

2. Methodology

Among the available systemic approaches, System-Theoretic Accident Model and Processes (STAMP) is an accident causality model based on systems theory that considers safety as a continuous control task managed by a control structure embedded in an adaptive socio-technical system [7, 8]. In STAMP, systems are comprised of interrelated components that are maintained in a state of dynamic equilibrium by feedback loops of information and control. The SCS is the underlying element of STAMP: it is a hierarchical system representation that maps all the agents involved in a system, and captures their functional interactions in terms of control actions and feedback loops among controllers and controlled processes. Specifically: (i) a *control action* is an information exchange between agents to modify the behaviour of the second agent, (ii) a *feedback* is an information exchange between agents to make the second agent aware of some information possessed by the first one, (iii) a *controller* is an agent imposing a control action on another agent (i.e., controlled process), (iv) a *controlled process* is an agent subjected to the control action of another agent (i.e., controller). We developed the SCS representing an industrial plant during the design and conduction of safe inspections through UASs by analysing existing rules and regulations on UASs, and the scientific literature and existing methodologies for safety risk assessment about the UAS operations (e.g., Specific Operations Risk Assessment - SORA [9]).

3. Results and discussion

Figure 1 shows the SCS of any industrial plants during the design and conduction of safe inspections by means of UASs. The downward and upward arrows represent control actions and feedback loops, respectively. The boxes indicate the different agents composing the system: (i) authority agents (red boxes), (ii) U-space, i.e., a system of services and procedures to manage UAS traffic (orange box), (iii) agents involved in the plant management and operations (green boxes), (iv) agents linked to the UAS design, manufacturing, and operations (blue boxes), (v) UAS (purple box).

European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) is the controller at the top level of the SCS: it establishes rules, regulations, and certification bases about the roles and responsibilities of different agents (e.g., Civil Aviation Authority - CAA, U-space, UAS designer and manufacturer, UAS operator, pilot), who, in turn, should demonstrate their compliance with such regulatory and certification framework. These agents are both controlled processes and controllers in the SCS. For instance, CAA is a controlled process receiving control actions from EASA, and a controller of the plant operator: it releases an operational authorisation to the plant operator, when the latter provides the Concept of Operations and the outcomes of the risk assessment and management processes. We assumed that industrial inspections via UASs do

not constitute a “standard scenario”, and they fall under the Specific Category since they are typically Beyond Visual Line Of Sight (BVLOS) operations conducted in proximity to structures, which could create risks to people on the ground. Accordingly, the plant operator may perform the risk assessment based on the SORA methodology, and thus identify Operational Safety Objectives (OSOs), and develop a Comprehensive Safety Portfolio. CAA also represents a controller for other agents: e.g., it releases the certification of operations to UAS operator and the license to the pilot, while both UAS operator and pilot should demonstrate their compliance with the requirements. The pilot, as well as the UAS ground operations manager, undergoes training and procedures from the UAS operator. The UAS operator also interacts with the UAS designer and manufacturer (i.e., the former is informed about UAS technical features, receives documentation on UAS use and maintenance, reports any occurrences and/or failures), and collaborates with the plant operator to assure safe UAS operations. The plant operator is also responsible of communicating the UAS uses and risk assessment outcomes to the plant managers, defining operational procedures addressing normal, abnormal, and emergency situations, and coordinating the various activities. Based on the inspection findings provided by the UAS operations, the plant operator should identify actions and measures to be implemented at the industrial site, which are processed by the plant managers. Among these managers, the operations one coordinates production and maintenance processes, by interacting with the workers, UAS ground operations manager, and pilot, providing them with procedures, instructions, and plans. In addition, the operations manager should inform the pilot on the inspection missions, durations, locations, and flight modes, and receive inspection reports detailing the status of equipment. The pilot continuously collaborates with the UAS ground operations manager by sharing ground operations planification, operating and environmental conditions, any changes or modifications, plant and UAS data. Finally, both the pilot and UAS ground operations control the UAS by performing (e.g.) status, and pre- and post- flight checks.

Figure 11. SCS for safe inspections at industrial sites via UASs.

4. Conclusions

The obtained SCS emphasises the roles and interactions among the various actors involved in the regulation and certification definition, plant management, UAS design and operations. These results represent a key step towards the adoption of a systems-theoretic approach for analysing the safe usage of emerging technologies in industrial settings. The proposed approach should not be considered as alternative to recommended methodologies for risk assessment (e.g., SORA), but rather as a holistic system perspective (integrating current methods) for further enhancing the safety management of industrial plants adopting UASs in their operations. This system-theoretic view represents a common staging area for designing systemic risk management processes that account for uncertainty and provide representative analyses for future operations.

Acknowledgements

This work is part of the research activities developed by the authors within the framework of PNRR: CN4 “Sustainable Mobility Center” - SPOKE 1 “Air Mobility” (E.S., R.P.) and SPOKE 7 “CCAM (Cooperative, Connected Automated Mobility), Connected Networks and Smart Infrastructure” (G.D.G.) - CN_00000023 - CUP B83C22002900007.

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List of abbreviations and definitions

BVLOS	Beyond Visual Line Of Sight
CAA	Civil Aviation Authority
EASA	European Aviation Safety Agency
OSO	Operational Safety Objective
SCS	Safety Control Structure
SORA	Specific Operations Risk Assessment
STAMP	System-Theoretic Accident Model and Processes
UAS	Unmanned Aircraft System

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Data Association

Special session

Human AI teaming & Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical Systems

By Micaela Demichela, Maria Chiara Leva, Ammar Abbas

Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical systems

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Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical systems

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COLLABORATIVE INTELLIGENCE AND HUMAN IN THE LOOP FOR THE FUTURE OF SAFETY CRITICAL SYSTEMS

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66th ESReDA Seminar
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Reeling through the last three/four years

Survey: Human-AI Collaboration in Safety-Critical and Industrial Systems

Automation vs Collaboration

*“Organizations that use machines merely to displace workers through automation will miss the full potential of AI... Tomorrow’s leaders will instead be those that embrace collaborative intelligence, transforming their operations, their industries and –no less important– their workforces.”**

*Daugherty, P.R.&Wilson, H.J., 2018. Human+Machine: Reimagining Work in the Age of AI. Harvard Business Press.

Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical Systems

5

Human in the loop configuration for collaborative safety critical intelligence applications

Ramos, I. F., Gianini, G., Leva, M. C., & Damiani, E. (2024). Collaborative Intelligence for Safety-Critical Industries: A Literature Review. *Information*, 15(11), 728.

The CISC Living Labs:

Schedule

14.45	Session Introduction: Human AI teaming & Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical Systems By Micaela Demichela, Maria Chiara Leva, Ammar Abbas
14.55	Analysing "Human-in-the-Loop" for Advances in Process Safety: Key Factors and Lessons Learned in control room scenario Presented By Chidera Winifred Amazu, Joseph Mietkiewicz, Ammar N. Abbas, Houda Briwa, Andres Alonso Perez,
15.20	Using physiological signal to provide insight into mental workload and operators engagement. Use of ML for helping to move towards real time EEG signal feedback Presented By Milos Pusica,
15.30	Enhancing Human Capabilities in Painting Defect Detection in automation and decision support system for anomaly detection Presented By Carlos Albarrán Morillo, Doaa Almhaitawi, Devesh Jawa
15.45	Evaluating the Impact of Collaborative Intelligence Technologies on Worker Wellbeing in the EU Manufacturing Landscape Presented By Naira López Cañellas
15.55	Title: Exploring Adaptive Human-Robot Collaboration: collaborative intelligence for cobotics and telerobotics Presented By Aayush Jain, Shakra Mehak, Ines Filipa Ramos, Carlo Caiazzo
16.15	Engaging end user in collaborative intelligence: what are the strength and weakness and opportunities for future applications and research Presented by Ammar Abbas, Micaela Demichela, Maria Chiara Leva

Telerobotic and Human-system interaction and interface design considerations

Evaluation data:

- ✔ **Task performance data**, such as task completion time, workpiece cut quality and collision rate.
- ✔ **Operator state data**: objective metrics, including mental workload, task engagement and arousal level, estimated from physiological sensor data, including a consumer-grade mobile EEG-cap and eyetracker mounted on a monitor, and subjective metrics gathered from user questionnaires.
- ✔ **Human-system interaction data**, to assess interaction efficiency and effectiveness.

LIVE LAB 1 B: Naturalistic learning in cobotics

A model to also support the human on the loop: what does the robotic system expect from the human member of the team? What does the human expect as feedback from robotic team?

Evaluate interface on the basis of failed attempt and subjective feedback, also using physiological measures (pupillometry)

LIVE LAB 1 C: Workload evaluation in cobotics

Adjustable lighting

Working instruction

Time measurement

TV/Monitor

- **Common company Workstation**
- **Preparation 60-70%**
- **Poka Yoke Station**
- **Starting neuroergonomic/ergonomic testing**
- **Model for assembling**
- **Job rotation**

Cobot introduction

Kinect

Touchscreen computer

Working area

Adjustable legs

Data collection evaluation metrics

USER STATE	USER BEHAVIOR	USER PERFORMANCE	DATA COLLECTION TOOL	DATA	METRIC
			<p>Wireless EEG</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EEG indexes • Pupil diameter • Blinks • Gaze fixation • Gaze movement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mental workload • Task Engagement • Arousal
			<p>Screen Eye-tracker</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-assessment Manikin • NASA-TLX • Engagement Questionnaire 	
			<p>Questionnaires</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Controller input • Robot path and velocity • Visual interface use (gaze and interaction) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remote control awareness • Efficiency of control • Operator skill • Visual attention
			<p>Human-robot interface</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task quality and performance assessment tools • Questionnaire 	
			<p>Task quality and performance assessment tools</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task completion time • NASA TLX and Usability questionnaire 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objective and subjective task performance • Human-system interaction performance

Heatmap of Passes Completion Cost/Unit

Color scale: 0 to 100

LIVE LAB 2 HP support in automotive tasks

1: Visual inspection at IVECO plant

2: Led Light tool to support Visual inspection at IVECO plant

Latent Spaces to support detection of paint defect

Support the human operator, through the use of **Latent Space**, in the painting defect detection with a **low cost** system, that can **improve the detection** and **decrease the work overload** on the operator

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ML for Anomaly detection

New features need to be made from the Statistics obtained from these 2 datasets: for example, the ratio (for each type of error) of = no. of errors on a given day / average no. of errors

Collaborative intelligence in control room scenarios.

Live lab 3

Count of Alarms per 10 min

The graph illustrates the rate of alarms per 10 min over the period from 17 January to 21 February in a UK based Oil and Gas facility.

Clustering of alarms

Identification of **clusters of alarms** to identify **scenarios**.

Possibility of **Grouping the alarms** base on high correlation to **reduce number of alarms** shown to the operator

These **groups of alarms** can be linked to a known cause and **labeled** using **expert knowledge**. The model can then display the causes of the alarms and assist in decision making in case of cognitive overload.

Figure: Correlation map between alarms of the wellheads. Lighter colors denotes higher correlations

Prediction of Trips

Table: Message of the alarms and probability of trip of the wellhead. In orange the Trip .
The analysis can suggest possible point of no return or point where an intervention is critical

Message	Probability of Trip			
039K2V007 010V001 MEZZ DIC PV = 72/2.48 A HI Recover	0.00358		009SDM6 5026B001 RG INLET PV = 1 TRIP	0.99977
003XZV004 003WXT001 FWV PV = 2 TRIP	0.01699		026BV071 MPC Hot Bypass Valve PV = 2 TRIP	0.99971
004XZV004 004WXT001 FWV PV = 2 TRIP	0.05624		026BZ077 026BX002 TO 025X001 PV = 2.5 % LO	0.99986
008XZV004 008WXT001 FWV PV = 2 TRIP	0.19153	←	020PIC061 020V001 OUTLET PV = 63.0 barg HI	0.99991
010XZV004 010WXT001 FWV PV = 0 TRIP	0.42373		030P1062 030P002B DISCH PV = 65.2 barg HI	0.99997
026BF1064 MPC SUCT SECCALC FLOW PV = 127.7 mbar IOP	0.84256		003ZA08 003HCV008 DISC. ALARM ALM	0.99998
026BZ1073 MPC ASURGE VLV POS FB PV = 0.3 % HI	0.86807		004ZA08 004HCV008 DISC. ALARM ALM	0.99999
026BF1064_CA mbar to MMb/d Convert CPV = 0.0 % IOP	0.97143		008ZA08 008HCV008 DISC. ALARM ALM	0.99999
026BF1064_MP CSUCT SECCALC FLOW PV = 75.7 MMb/d IOP	0.99583		014P2048 014P001 TO 020V001 PV = 65.1 barg HI	1
026BFD1003 PROC GAS LP SUCT VLV DP PV = 4.60 barg HI	0.9947		014P2048 014P001 TO 020V001 PV = 65.1 barg HH	1
026BZ1002 026BV001 INLET PV = -0.0 % LO	0.99708		020P2097 020V001 PV = 65.1 barg HI	1
026BF1047 026BV002 PV = 66.0 barg HI	0.99966		020P2097 020V001 PV = 65.1 barg HH	1
026BZ1050 026BV002 OUTLET PV = 0.0 % LO	0.99981		020P2097_HH FIRST UP ALM	1
004Z1061 004WXT001 WASHWATER PV = 0.6 % LO	0.99987		APU SYSTEM020A TRIP ALM	1
003Z1061 003WXT001 WASHWATER PV = 0.5 % LO	0.99993		GPN310011 PROC AREA CELL DK PV = 74.1 dBA HI	1
008Z1061 008WXT001 WASHWATER PV = 4.6 % LO	0.99996		GPN310011 PROC AREA CELL DK PV = 74.1 dBA HH	1
026BZ1031 026BV002 INLET PV = 3.4 % LO	0.99992		GPN310011 PROC AREA CELL DK PV = 71.0 dBA HH Recover	1
003Z1061 003WXT001 RG INLET PV = -0.1 % LO	0.99994		GPN310011 PROC AREA CELL DK PV = 71.0 dBA HI Recover	1
026BBDV002 026BV001 INLET PV = 0 TRIP	0.99992		0201062 020V001 WTR OUTLET PV = 0.8 % LO	1
026BBDV031 026BV002 INLET PV = 1 TRIP	0.9999		003XZV003 003WXT001 UMV PV = 2 TRIP	1
026BBDV052 026BBDV031 EQUALISE PV = 0 TRIP	0.99987			
026BBDV077 026BX002 TO 025X001 PV = 1 TRIP	0.99983			
026BBDV090 026BBDV077 BYP PV = 0 TRIP	0.99979			
026BBDV091 026BBDV002 EQUALISE PV = 0 TRIP	0.99973			

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Experiment: alarm management & intervention simulator

Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical systems

Live Lab 3 : Decision making support in control room

Factors varied: Alarm design
(Investigating problem 1)

Seq	Event	Priority	Time	Type	Level	Handled	Event	Priority	Time	Tag	St	
1	Active	1	00:01:07	FAL11	Heat_Recovery			1	Active	00:01:37	FAL11	H
2	Active	1	00:01:41	CAL20	Absorber			1	Active	00:04:38	TAH17	A
3	Active	1	00:05:43	FAL20	Absorber			1	Active	00:05:43	FAH08	H
4	Active	1	00:05:43	FAL20	Absorber			1	Active	00:05:41	CAL20	A
5	Active	1	00:05:54	TAH12	Absorber			1	Active	00:05:53	FAL20	A
6	Active	1	00:05:54	TAH12	Heat_Recovery			1	Active	00:06:02	FAL16	A
7	Active	1	00:06:04	TAH18	Reactor			1	Active	00:06:06	FAL08	H
8	Active	1	00:06:11	TAH03	Heat_Recovery			1	Active	00:06:26	TAH18	A
9	Active	1	00:06:26	FAL16	Reactor			1	Active	00:06:34	TAH20	A
10	Active	1	00:06:57	TAH12	Heat_Recovery			1	Active	00:06:54	TAH12	H

Type of plant - Chemical Process Industry
(Formaldehyde production).
Alarm flood condition: present

Micaela Demichela, Gabriele Baldissone, and Gianfranco Camuncoli.
Risk-Based Decision Making for the Management of Change in Process Plants: Benefits of Integrating Probabilistic and Phenomenological Analysis. Industrial Engineering Chemistry Research 2017 56 (50), 14873-14887

This experiment is to

- investigate the **impact of decision support systems** on control room operators in safety critical status,
- analyse the **different factors** impacting *its ability to perceive and then respond* (conduct actions on the monitor) to **critical alarms**.
- There are four groups of participants (with different level of HMI support) and 3 scenarios with different level of complexity

01 Paper procedures	02 Alarm rationalization + Paper procedures	03 Alarm rationalization + Screen based procedures	04 Alarm rationalization + Screen based procedures + AI recommendation support
------------------------	---	---	---

The support Interface:

For GROUP 4 only it contains an AI generated recommendation system

The support interface will appear on the right monitor, and it shows 4 sections.

The top left, shows the list of alarms and their different characteristics (name, state, priority, time, tag, section and acknowledgement case where the participant should click to acknowledge it).

The top right, shows the procedures section. the participant should click on the specific section then the specific alarm to view its corresponding procedure.

The bottom left, is a graph that shows and the flow of water and product concentration in the absorber.

The bottom right, is the AI recommendation system

Scenario 2: Events and Task timeline

Consequences

Analysis using python in jupyter notebook

Moving towards a more pervasive assessment of the humans in the systems

- IOT, wearable technologies and AI are enhancing capacity to assess the human in the system in a way that was not possible before.

5th

Mass customization & cyber physical cognitive systems

Continuous modeling of MWL (Milos)

Ethical and Legal implications for Workers Well being

Constraints In Law-making	Limitations of Ethical Principles	Shared Shortfalls	Dangerous Omissions
Drafting (stakeholders, MS)	Hierarchy (transparency vs well-being)	Hard Operationalisation (fragmentation, imprecision)	Invasive surveillance practices & power dynamics
EU's Enforcement Capacity	Little flexibility towards geographical & sectoral differences	Room for the Responsibility Gap	Forceful/unsafe deployment of insufficiently-tested/tailored tech
Lack of Monitoring Tools	Checklist Tendency	No Obligation to Disclose Objectives, Conditions, Validation Procedures***	Effects in the quality and security of employment

Process Safety Data Modelling for Human-in-the-Loop Configurations in Process Control

Chidera Winifred Amazu, Joseph Mietkiewicz, Ammar N. Abbas, Andres Alonso Perez, Houda Briwa

The slide features a dark blue background. In the top left corner is the European Union flag. In the top right corner is a small portrait of Marie Skłodowska-Curie with the text 'Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions'. The main title 'Process Safety Data Modelling for Human-in-the-Loop Configurations in Process Control' is written in white. Below it is a quote: 'How helpful are your Alarm Response Procedures for optimal cognition, behaviour and safety?'. The authors' names are listed: Chidera Winifred Amazu, Joseph Mietkiewicz, Ammar N. Abbas, Houda Briwa, and Andres Perez Alonso. The CISC logo is on the right, with the tagline 'Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical systems' and an illustration of a robotic hand and a human hand holding a red sphere. The Politecnico di Torino logo is in the bottom left corner.

Process Safety Data Modelling for Human-in-the-Loop Configurations in Process Control

*“How helpful are your Alarm Response Procedures for
optimal cognition, behaviour and safety?”*

Chidera Winifred Amazu
Joseph Mietkiewicz
Ammar N. Abbas
Houda Briwa
Andres Perez Alonso

 Politecnico
di Torino

CISC
Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical systems

Research Team

Thank You

Chidera Amazu (ESR4)
Human-in-the-loop in Process Control
Chemical Engineering
Politecnico di Torino

Prof. Davide Fissore
Chemical Engineering
Politecnico di Torino

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Supported by:

Objective 1: Lessons Learnt

Objective 1: Solution/Methodology

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CONSTRUCTS:

- PERCEIVED WORKLOAD
- PERCEIVED/INFORMED SITUATIONAL AWARENESS
- BEHAVIOUR
- PERFORMANCE
- ALERTNESS
- LEARNING
- SEARCH DIFFICULTY

Objective 1: Procedure Impact

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To study the impact of advancing to digital alarm response procedure options on process control room operators in current HiTL configurations.

Research Questions:

RQ1: What are the *most critical factors/variables that describe the impact of procedures on operators beyond performance and for overall HiTL assessment?*

RQ2: How does the *transition from paper to digital or computerised procedure options impact operators' general behaviour, cognition, and safety?*

Alarm Response Procedures & Gaps

OPERATOR STATES

HUMAN RELIABILITY ANALYSIS (HRA)

Task Steps	Sub task	Failure type	Time	Location	Cues	New_HEP
1. Monitoring & Alarm Handling	Monitor the process (no alarm)	Diagnosis				0.001
	Identify Critical Alarm (now multiple alarms)	Diagnosis				0.955
2. Planning	Acknowledge critical alarm	Action				0.524
	Find procedure	Action				
	Click to Open Heat Recovery mimic	Action				
3. Intervention 1	Check Cooling water system mass flow rate with scale [kg/s]. Nominal value is [5.2 kg/s].	Diagnosis	1	0	0.510	
	IF flow rate below 4.8 kg/s, continue STEP 3.1.		1	1	0.501	
			1	0	0.990	
			1	1	0.501	
4. Alarm Handling	CALL supervisor in the room to ask what to do	Action				0.667
	Follow Instructions given by Supervisor	Action				0.976
5. Planning	Identify First Up Reactor Alarm	Diagnosis	1	0	0.505	
	Acknowledge Critical alarm	Action	1	1	0.545	
6. Intervention	Open reactor plant section button	Action				0.502
	Check the cooling system temperature [°C] on the meter. Cross-check with nominal temperature value [110 °C]. IF cooling system temperature below 108 [°C] or above 109 [°C], continue 6.1; ELSE, do nothing	Diagnosis	1	1	0.723	
	Monitor Max temperature graph, try to stabilise the temperature using the cooling system temperature scale. (BE VERY CAREFUL NOT TO MOVE A LOT OR TOO QUICKLY). NOTE: Temperature very sensitive to change by the cooling system! IF 'TAH13 is not recovered after 1 Minute, CALL Supervisor; ELSE CONTINUE STEP 6.2	Action	1	1	0.500	
			1	0	0.510	

GOAL 1

Effective Decision Support for the human in the loop in process control: Alarm Response Procedures

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Design of Experiment: Data Collection

Design of Experiment: Protocol

Scenario 3 Event timeline

Formaldehyde Production: Scenarios

Scenario S1	Scenario S2	Scenario S3
<p>GOAL: Recover Nitrogen in the Methanol tank</p> <p>TASK COMPLEXITY: Low</p> <p>Consequence: Tank Implosion</p> <p>Duration: 15mins.</p>	<p>GOAL: Recover Nitrogen in the Methanol tank/control the pump</p> <p>TASK COMPLEXITY: Medium</p> <p>Consequence: Tank Implosion</p> <p>Duration: 15mins.</p>	<p>GOAL: Restore cooling water in REC3 + Prevent reactor from overheating</p> <p>TASK COMPLEXITY: High</p> <p>Consequence: Overheating of reactor</p> <p>Duration: 18mins.</p>

Case study: Formaldehyde Production

1 CENTRAL DISPLAY

TIME 00:00:00

3 Scenarios

Central alarm elements
Total: 80 alarms and procedures

For supervisors only

mimics

Design of Experiment – LiveLab3

Chemical Engineering Masters Students, PhD Students, Professors

Group 1 (Group Paper (PBP) + No Alarm prioritisation)

Group 2 (Group PBP + Alarm prioritisation)

Group 3 (Group Electronic (EP) + Alarm prioritisation)

Group 4 (Group AI + EP + Alarm prioritisation)

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ESReDA

European Safety, Reliability &
Data Association

Thank You

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CISC

Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical systems

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Evaluating the Impact of Collaborative Intelligence Technologies on Worker Wellbeing in the EU Manufacturing Landscape

Naira López Cañellas

Evaluating the Impact of CI Technologies on Worker Wellbeing in the EU Manufacturing Landscape

“When collaborating with AI-powered systems in manufacturing settings, are we paying enough attention to the human and social aspects of work?”

By Naira López Cañellas, 3rd Year PhD Candidate

Research Context

Research Background

Theoretical Framework: Braverman's Labour Process Theory (LPT, 1975) argues that capitalist management continuously seeks to deskill and control workers through technological and organisational changes to maximise efficiency and maintain authority.

Focus of study: From the several categories of technologies that could fall into the category of AI-powered CI technologies, I refer to the EU-OSHA report of 2022, and focus on the three that take place on-site in manufacturing environments (the shopfloor): *advanced robotics, smart digital systems, and worker management technologies.*

Research Questions

Q1- How do **AI-powered robotics, smart digital systems and worker management technologies** influence **worker agency** and **working conditions** within EU **manufacturing** workplaces?

Q2- Who are the key **actors** trying to **influence policy and practice** regarding the introduction of these technologies in EU workplaces?

Q3 – What kinds of **interventions** could better **empower workers** in the EU industrial workplaces of the **future**?

Data Gathering

<p>1) Workers (and their representatives) from workplaces with the relevant technology. Invested in protecting workers more than they are on the technology's uptake.</p> <p>Interviewees 6, 8, 13, 15, 18, 20, 22, 16, 25, 26, 29, 33, 34, 38, 40, 41, 42, 44</p> <p style="text-align: right;">TOTAL: 18</p>	
<p>2) Implementers. Invested in the uptake of the technology more than on workers' wellbeing. Includes managers, officers, trainers, technology developers.</p> <p>Interviewees 1, 2, 3, 10, 21, 23, 24, 31, 39, 32</p> <p style="text-align: right;">TOTAL: 10</p>	<p>25</p>
<p>3) Regulatory side. Trying to balance both/other interests. Includes lawyers, policymakers, academics and interest representatives.</p> <p>Interviewees 4, 5, 7, 9, 12, 11, 19, 14, 17, 27, 28, 30</p> <p style="text-align: right;">TOTAL: 12</p>	<p>15</p>

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Preliminary Results

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Research Team

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Supported by:

Future Research Directions

- **Policy.** Advancing an integrated regulatory framework: towards a more coherent and labour-grounded EU digital policy landscape.
- **Practice.** Enhancing worker autonomy, voice, and participation.
- **Stakeholder Relations.** Fostering long-term trust along the value chain for responsible innovation.
- **Societal Trust.** Embedding social and environmental considerations into the digital transition, yielding gains in both productivity and wellbeing, through participatory and digital literacy & skills initiatives.
- **Geopolitical interests.** Securing digital competitiveness, resilience and sovereignty through European infrastructure, funding and long-term academia-industry collaborations.

Thank you very much for your attention

Looking forward to your questions!

Feel free to contact me over on:

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CISC
Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical systems

Enhancing Human Capabilities in Painting Defect Detection in automation and decision support system for anomaly detection

Carlos Albarrán Morillo

ESReDA
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LiveLab 2: Enhancing Human Capabilities in Painting Defect Detection in Automation and Decision Support System for Anomaly Detection

*"How can we improve the accuracy and well-being
during visual inspections?"*

ESR11: Carlos Albarrán Morillo

Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical systems

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IVECO

CISC project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant no. 955901

Quality Control Area Focusing on Detecting Defects in Painted Surfaces in Vehicles

IVECO

- ❖ Visual inspection catches defects missed by automation
- ❖ Operators inspect up to 181 vehicles, mainly on reflective white paint (80% workload)
- ❖ High visual focus causes fatigue, lowering accuracy and productivity
- ❖ Reducing visual demand is key for quality, safety, and well-being

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Problem-Solving Strategy

6M Cause & Effect Diagram

- **Man (People)**
- Machine
- Method
- Material
- Measurement
- Mother Nature (Environment)

"Human-Centred Design"

3

Lighting System

New LED lighting system

An operator performing surface inspection using the LED system

4

Lighting System

Luxmeter

New LED lighting system

5

Lighting System

Raw Task Load Index (RTLX) Scale: On a scale 1 (Very low) - 10 (Very High)

Mental Demand
Physical Demand
Temporal Demand
Performance
Frustration
Effort

Comfort Questionnaire: On a 7-point Likert-scale (7 indicates that the device is very comfortable)

I feel tense or edge because I am wearing the device
I can feel the device moving
The device is painful to wear
I feel strange wearing the device
The device affects the way I move
I do not secure feeling the device
Wearing the device disturbs me from my work
I can imagine wearing the device in the future
The device is too heavy
The device restricts my field of vision

Subjective Visual Fatigue (VF) Scale: On a scale between 1 (None) and 5 (Severe)

General Visual Fatigue
Blinking
Dry Eyes
Itchy Eyes
Foreign Body Sensation
Blur
Tearing
Eye Pain
Sleepy

Subjective Satisfaction Score of the general system for detecting defects

On a scale between 1 (very dissatisfaction) and 7 (very satisfaction)

Results:

- ❖ LED system showed slightly **lower workload**
- ❖ LED system had **highest satisfaction**
- ❖ Comfort issues with LED: **insecurity, limited vision, disturbance**

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Eye-Tracker Application

- **Tobii Pro Glasses 3** successfully trialed in painted surface quality control
- **Great potential** to advance the knowledge of visual fatigue and attention by objective measures

Eye movement parameters	Change with visual fatigue
Fixation frequency	↓
Total fixation duration	↑
Average fixation duration	↑
Average fixation angle: left eye	~
Average fixation angle: right eye	~
Total saccade duration	↓
Average saccade duration	↓
Average saccade magnitude: left eye	↓
Average saccade magnitude: right eye	↓
Maximum saccade magnitude: left eye	↓
Maximum saccade magnitude: right eye	↓
Blinking frequency	↑
Average blinking duration	↑
Average rotation angle: left eye	~
Average rotation angle: right eye	~
Pupil diameter	↓

↑ indicates an increase, ↓ indicates a decrease, and ~ indicates little to no change

Eye movement parameters and their expected change with visual fatigue

Eye-Tracker Application

- **Tobii Pro Glasses 3** successfully trialed in painted surface quality control
- **Great potential** to advance the knowledge of visual fatigue and attention by objective measures

Heat maps visualize attention patterns of an operator

Research Team

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Using Machine Learning and EEG to Provide Insights into Human Mental Workload: Towards Real-Time Generalized Mental Workload Estimation

Milos Pusica

Using Machine Learning and EEG to Provide Insights into Human Mental Workload: Towards Real-Time Generalized Mental Workload Estimation

“Can we develop robust, real-time, and generalized
mental workload estimation and make it work in the
real world?”

Miloš Pušica

Research Questions

Can we take advantage of real-time EEG monitoring and machine learning techniques to address key problems in mental workload (MWL) estimation:

- **Generalized** (cross-task) estimation
- Applicable in the **real-world** conditions (out of the laboratory)
- **Real-time** estimation

State-of-the-Art: Literature Review

State-of-the-Art: Literature Review

State-of-the-Art: Literature Review

- The gap implies that MWL estimation tends to be less accurate in more complex task settings, such as multitasking
- However:
 - Variability in methodologies
 - Different tasks
 - Different datasets
 - Scarcity of studies in multitasking domain

Development and Results

- We established a unique methodology for the evaluation of EEG-based MWL estimation using machine learning
- Design experiments – representatives of two categories of tasks:
 - Multitasking: MATB-II
 - Single-tasking: Manual assembly task

MATB-II T DUBLIN TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY DUBLIN

MATB-II

Experiment setup

MATB-II T DUBLIN TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY DUBLIN

MATB-II session divided into non-overlapping blocks of different task loads: PW, LL, ML, HL

- 50 subjects recorded
- Two 51 min. sessions per subject
- EEG
- Eye-tracking
- Activity logged
- Subjective MWL ratings (NASA-TLX)

		Levels			
		PW	Low	Medium	High
Subtasks	SYSM	/	10	10	20
	TRCK	/	/	On	On, faster
	COMM	/	6	10	14
	RMAN	/	5	10	20

MATB-II

MATB-II Results

Task load level classification

Subjective MWL classification

Cognitive activity detection

	Overall	SYSM	COMM	RMAN
F1 score	0.87	0.88	0.87	0.86
Precision	0.87	0.88	0.90	0.85
Recall	0.87	0.88	0.84	0.88
Accuracy	0.87	0.87	0.90	0.84

Pušica, M., Kartali, A., Bojović, L., Gligorijević, I., Jovanović, J., Leva, M.C. and Mijović, B., 2024. Mental Workload Classification and Tasks Detection in Multitasking: Deep Learning Insights from EEG Study. *Brain Sciences*, 14(2), p.149.

Manual Assembly Task

- Collaboration with Faculty of Engineering, University of Kragujevac (FINK)
- 32 subjects recorded
- Two 1.5h sessions per subject
- Activity logged
- Errors detected

Manual Assembly Task

Low complexity schemes - examples

High complexity schemes - examples

Manual Assembly Task

Manual Assembly Task Results

Pušica, M., Caiazzo, C., Djapan, M., Savković, M. and Leva, M.C., 2024, June. Towards Practical Deployment: Subject-Independent EEG-Based Mental Workload Classification on Assembly Lines. In *2024 11th International Conference on Electrical, Electronic and Computing Engineering (IcETRAN)* (pp. 1-4). IEEE.

Cross-Task Evaluation

Trained on: MATB-II, Tested on: Manual assembly line

Trained on: Manual assembly line, Tested on: MATB-II

Cross-task MWL estimation **does not work**

Key results and Conclusions

- MWL estimation performance is significantly better in single tasking compared to multitasking scenario
- Subjective MWL ratings as a promising approach for MWL labeling in the case of more complex tasks as in multitasking
- **Cognitive activity detection** was very **successful** – a promising alternative approach for MWL estimation – instead of the direct overall MWL estimation, split the complex task into elemental cognitive activities, detect it and use it to estimate overall MWL

Future Work

- Improvement of subjective MWL rating approach in multitasking –
 - New experimental design to adjust for individual differences
 - Improved MWL rating method, possibly including external experiment observers to assess MWL of participants
- Cognitive activity detection as a proxy for overall MWL – testing this approach on a different experimental task that replicates multitasking conditions with cognitively similar subtasks, enabling a robust evaluation across tasks
 - New experimental design to incorporate similar cognitive activity as in MATB-II
 - Evaluation of the method across these different tasks

Research Team

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Thank you for your
attention

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Enabling Seamless Human-Robot Collaboration

Aayush Jain, Shakra Mehak, Inês Fernandes Ramos, Carlo Caiazzo

LiveLab 1: Enabling Seamless Human-Robot Collaboration

Presenters- Aayush Jain
Shakra Mehak
Inês Fernandes Ramos
Carlo Caiazzo

Aim of LiveLab1

To investigate how humans and robots can collaborate more **naturally and effectively** by exploring innovative, intuitive **programming methods** and **optimizing interfaces** and environments with a strong focus on **human-centered design, safety, and ergonomics**.

LiveLab1 Set-Up

Irish Manufacturing Research, Ireland
Aayush Jain: Towards Reliable Robot Autonomy through Symbol Grounding.
Shakra Mehak: Human-Robotic Interaction Challenges in Teaching-by-Demonstration.

Experimental representational cutting task

Remote environment

Remote robot station

Operator station

Irish manufacturing Research, Ireland

Inês Fernandes Ramos: A Framework For Human-Machine Interface Evaluation And Operator Performance Prediction.

Faculty of Engineering, University of Kragujevac, Serbia (FINK)
Carlo Caiazzo: Neuro-ergonomic Assessment of Mental Workload in Adaptive Industrial Human-Robot Collaboration.

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Towards Reliable Robot Autonomy through Symbol Grounding

Aayush Jain

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Motivation

- Existing robot programming interfaces are **tedious** and **require programming expertise** to use.
- Each task needs to be analytically decomposed and be **hard coded** which makes them **inflexible**.
- SMEs face **high labor costs**, **unsafe tasks**, and outdated automation that's too **complex and costly**.

Off-line Programming [RoboDK, 2018]

In-flexible Programming Methods

CoBT: Collaborative Programming of Behavior Trees

- ✓ Generates behaviour trees from **one demonstration**
- ✓ Easily **deployable, reactive and modular**
- ✓ Uses combination of **data-driven machine learning** methods with **logic-based declarative learning**
- ✓ **BT** provides a high-level control structure and **DMP** enable the lower-level controller
- ✓ **Goal adaptation** module for long-horizon tasks

A. Jain, P. Long, V. Villani, J. D. Kelleher, and M. C. Leva. "CoBT: Collaborative Programming of Behaviour Trees from One Demonstration for Robot Manipulation." in *International Conference on Robotics and Automation 2024 (ICRA24)*.

To empower manufacturers by **simplifying and democratizing** the deployment of robotic technologies, enabling rapid, efficient, and accessible automation for all.

A **software package** linking robot and vision that creates task and motion plans from a **single human demonstration**

We are looking
to...

Form Strategic Partnerships

Engage Beta Testing Partners

Secure Investment Opportunities

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Robomate

Safety and security issues in the consideration of the HMI for the management of the Seveso sites

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Domenico Barone, Tecnologie Sicurezza Industriale Srl, domenico.barone.tsi@gmail.com

Abstract

The Seveso III Directive 2012/18/EU imposes an obligation to take into due consideration the human factors and the interfaces between operators, processes, and plants, as part of the implementation of the Safety Management System for Prevention of Major Accident (SMS-PMA) of industrial sites. During the control activities it is in fact necessary to verify that training programs and emergency drills are implemented to improve operator behaviour. It is therefore fundamental that in the risk analysis the human factor and the conditions in which significant activities for the safety of the establishment must be carried out. Considering the increased possibility of intentional attacks such as sabotage, terrorism, and retaliation, and the effects on the management of processes characterized by the presence of dangerous substances, with the consequent possible occurrence of major industrial accidents, adequate measures for the prevention and mitigation of Security must be taken into consideration. In this sense, although the Seveso III directive does not explicitly provide for it, the methods by which to correctly implement, in the SMS-PMA, the security issues must be explored in depth. The Security and Safety management systems in fact have different correlations and therefore can be integrated, being able to consider Security as an integral part of Safety. The possible integration between the two systems cannot ignore the consideration of the following common measures, for process plants, belonging to the areas of: Prevention (physical barriers, intrusion alarms for people/internet, automatic blocks – Security; gas/fire alarms, trigger control, automatic blocks – Safety); Mitigation (intrusion control, emergency evacuation control – Security; fire-prevention systems, fire-fighting water, loss containment, emergency plan – Safety). Based on the above considerations, it is possible to state that specific attention must be paid to the human-machine interface (HMI), meaning the system that separates the operator, who is using a machine (the control panel located in the control room in the case of the process industry), from the machine itself, while ensuring a constant connection. In close connection it is considered the prevention and assessment of human error, a fundamental aspect of process safety management. The elements indicated are thus strictly related to the correct evaluation of the vulnerability of the systems, considering the constant connection between the human element and the machine element. A good designed man-machine interface, in the control room of a process plant, allows to minimize the possibility of operator error on the panel, both during normal operating conditions and during emergency situations, throughout the process life cycle and in case of plant or process changes. The prevention of human error cannot ignore the knowledge of the potential negative consequences deriving from non-compliance with system procedures, with the possibility of a major accident. The assessment of the possibility of human error must be used in the reliability analysis to verify if the procedures and operational controls adopted to improve the behaviour of the operator or the instrumental controls give the best contribution to the safety of the system. In addition, a fundamental role is represented by training activities and emergency drills, which must be carried out according to a specific path that goes from design to critical analysis of results. In this way it will be possible to prepare any corrective actions, also in terms of response times and emergency management of the operators, to reduce the possibility of accidents related to human error. The Security prevention and mitigation measures therefore concern both the physical and IT protection of Seveso activities and the people present. The analysis of Security vulnerabilities due to intentional attacks such as sabotage, terrorism, and retaliation, allows to identify the measures for the reduction of the relative risk according to the best practices in the field.

1. Introduction

The Seveso III Directive 2012/18/EU [1], implemented in Italy by a legislative decree issued in 2015 - D.Lgs. 105/2015 [2], is aimed at the prevention of major accidents involving dangerous substances. The D.Lgs. 105/2015 covers establishments where dangerous substances may be present (e.g. during processing or storage) in quantities exceeding certain thresholds. Operators of the establishments are obliged to take all necessary measures to prevent major accidents and to limit their consequences for human health and the environment. Depending on the amount of dangerous substances present, establishments are categorized in lower and upper tiers, with different obligations. The requirements include, among others: notification of all concerned establishments; deploying a Major Accident

Prevention Policy (MAPP) through the implementation of a Safety Management System for Prevention of Major Accidents (SMS-PMA); producing a Safety Report (SR) for upper-tier establishments; producing an Internal Emergency Plan (IEP) for upper tier establishments; providing information in case of accidents. As part of the implementation of the Safety Management System, the D.Lgs. 105/2015 imposes an obligation to take into due consideration the human factors and the interfaces between operators, processes, and plants, with the correct workspace design. During the control activities, it is necessary to verify that training programs and emergency drills are implemented to improve operator behaviour. It is therefore fundamental that in the risk analysis the human factor and the conditions in which significant activities for the safety of the establishment must be carried out, giving particular attention to the interfaces between operators and processes in the phase of operational control of the plants.

2. The control activities: human factors and HMI

2.1 Human factors in the control activities

In Italy, the SMS inspections are conducted to verify the suitability of the operator MAPP carrying out a planned and systematic examination of the systems being employed at the establishment, whether of a technical, organisational or managerial nature. The human factors and the interfaces between operators, processes, and plants are specific items of interest during the SMS control activity [3]. In fact, the commission must: Verify that training and drill programs exist and are implemented to improve the behaviour of the operator; Verify that the work shifts, and the distribution of tasks have been established considering the psycho-physical stress to which the workers are subjected and that mechanisms are put in place to verify that the appropriate psycho-physical conditions are maintained. Among the tools available to the inspection commission during the documentary verification, it is possible to verify directly, also by consulting the documentation relating to the health and safety at work analysis, the compliance with the indications relating to the maintenance suitable psycho-physical conditions of the workers. During the “on-site” visit, the possible insights concern interviews with the employees both on the management methods of ordinary and extraordinary management, maintenance, emergency interventions, and on their involvement in the drafting and/or revision of the operating instructions.

2.2 The consideration of the HMI and the human error

The Italian national technical standard UNI 10616:2022 (Establishments with major-accident hazard-Safety management systems-Guidelines on implementation of UNI 10617) [4] provides guidelines for implementing a safety management system, describing the procedures and technical tools useful for achieving specific objectives for the prevention of major accidents in industrial establishments (national technical standard UNI 10617:2019) [5]. It deals with most of the hazards and major accident risks present both in simple installations and in more complex installations where the process risks can be preponderant compared to those connected to the simple loss of containment. The application of the contents of the standard must be commensurate with the specificities of the major accident hazards present in the establishment. In the standard, specific attention is paid to the human-machine interface (HMI), meaning the system that separates the operator, who is using a machine (i.e. the control panel located in the control room in the case of the process industry), from the machine itself, while ensuring a constant connection. Among the objectives for the continuous improvement of the SMS-PMA, which arise from the results of the identification of the hazards and the assessment of the risks of a major accident, the improvement of the quality of the interface between the operator and the plant/process can also be included (i.e. promptness, accuracy and punctuality in reporting anomalies). In close connection with the HMI, it is considered the prevention and assessment of human error, a fundamental aspect of process safety management. To strengthen and disseminate the culture of safety, the site manager should also operate through the implementation of a company policy which clearly and transparently identifies the criteria for distinguishing acceptable behaviour from that which cannot be considered as such, distinguishing situations involving intentional misconduct from human errors attributable to organizational causes. The awareness of the people who carry out a work activity in the plant, involved in activities relevant to safety, can in fact be verified through knowledge of the potential negative consequences deriving from a failure to comply with the specified procedures, with consequent human error, and the possibility of even a major accident. The need to verify the system procedures, on the other hand, may derive from the possible analysis of the accidents and/or near misses connected to the ascertained human error.

3. Safety and Security in the Seveso sites

3.1 Regulatory references

The D.Lgs. 105/2015 does not provide specific Security requirements and/or analyses. Intentional attacks such as sabotage, terrorism, retaliation are still possible and therefore, according to best practices in the field, adequate prevention and mitigation measures of Security must be taken into consideration.

Possible definitions of Security are [6]:

Protection of resources from dangers as well as from abuse of protected resources.

Set of measures adopted to prevent intentional acts and to protect property and people from the consequences of such acts.

Security understood as protection of resources can concern [7]:

physical or structural part of the systems (perimeters, barriers, etc.)

IT and data part (cybersecurity of OT systems, etc.)

people (employees, contractors, entry control, etc.)

Safety is the set of measures and tools aimed at preventing and reducing the consequences of events that could cause losses to people and damage to things.

Cybersecurity or information security or digital security is the practice of protecting digital information, devices and personal data. The three fundamental pillars are: confidentiality, integrity, accessibility.

3.2 Physical Security

Physical Security of plants consists of the defense of the perimeter and access by third parties to prevent and mitigate acts of sabotage, terrorism, and retaliation. It also provides limited or forbidden access areas for critical components and surveillance systems for people present in the plants.

An example of Physical Security for Seveso sites is shown in Figure 1 with protection of the external perimeter and with a limited access area for critical components [8].

Figure 12. External perimeter protection and limited access areas for critical components.

Figure 2 shows an establishment layout with the position of possible targets and the possible ADS (Adversary Sequence Diagram) attack sequences by third parties to carry out arson, armed assaults, use of explosives, attacks with vehicles and drones [9].

For example, an arson attack can occur according to the P1 sequence: the attacker enters the establishment from the personnel access gate and, once on site, reaches the administrative offices and the warehouse through the respective doors.

An explosive attack can occur according to the P2 or P3 sequences: the attacker enters the establishment from the personnel access gate, once on site he can directly reach and attack the process plants and storage (P3), or enter the control room from the relative door (P2) and attack the control and safety systems of the plants/storage.

Figure 2. Establishment layout with possible targets and attack sequences (ADS) for intentional malicious acts.

3.3 Cyber Security

DCS/SCADA control systems can be subject to cyber-attacks via the Internet and are therefore protected by specific hardware/software barriers (firewalls) as shown below [10].

Figure 3 shows the Security system in an industrial context; there are three zones.

Figure 3. Security System in an Industrial Context.

In the first zone there are three levels:

- level 0 SCADA relating to motors, pumps, valves, actuators
- level 1 SCADA relating to the PLC control system
- level 2 SCADA relating to the control panels/systems

In the second zone, communicating with encryption with levels 0,1,2 SCADA, and separated by a firewall, there is:

- level 3 (operational zone) relating to data storage and remote maintenance

In the third zone relating to the DMZ (Demilitarized zone) segmentation and segregation take place (level 3).

In the fourth zone, separated by a firewall, the system is controlled via keyboards and screens with the convergence of IT and OT systems.

In the fifth zone, separated by a firewall, the connection with the staff, the SIEM and the data center take place.

Figure 4 shows a Security system for OT where the following are highlighted:

- integrity control for levels 0-1-2
- update and hardening for level 3 DMZ
- system protection for level 4 operational network

Figure 4. Security of an OT system.

3.4 Personnel Security

To access the workplaces, plant workers and contractors are provided with badges to be used at the appropriate entrances.

Figure 5 shows the key points for personnel security [11]:

- Hiring competent personnel (suitable for role, identity confirmation, pre-employment screening)
- Determining roles (computer assignment, access codes, security policy)
- Reviews (face-to-face progress, work-life balance assessment, considering that internal accidents occur outside of normal working hours)
- Remote working (accidents generally occur from a remote location: assess the work environment and devices; schedule workdays on site)
- Managing third parties securely, third parties should follow the same regulations as internal personnel: include personnel security in the contract clauses; enforce personnel security requirements; audit third parties' compliance with the security policy
- Being present when third parties need it: ask questions about behavior change; establish processes for reporting on personnel and line management
- Following the exit procedure (remove access rights, entry cards of professionals IT who can still log in using old credentials)

The organization should track personnel security measures from the time of hire until the end of the assignment and monitor behavior changes over time.

Figure 5. Key elements of personnel security.

3.5 Security and Safety management systems

The main activities of the management systems are:

5. Security
 - (a) Prevention: physical barriers, people/internet intrusion alarms, automatic blocks
 - (b) Mitigation: intrusion control, emergency evacuation control
6. Safety
 - (a) Prevention: gas/fire alarms, trigger control, automatic blocks
 - (b) Mitigation: fire-prevention systems, fire-fighting water, leak containment, emergency plan

The two management systems, Security and Safety, have different correlations and therefore can be integrated. Security can be considered as an integral part of Safety.

4. The prevention of human error in a process plant

The prevention of human error cannot ignore the knowledge of the potential negative consequences deriving from non-compliance with system procedures, with the possibility of a major accident. The assessment of the possibility of human error must be used in the reliability analysis to verify if the procedures and operational controls adopted to improve the behavior of the operator or the instrumental controls give the best contribution to the safety of the system.

The management by the workers of operating anomalies and/or emergencies must be verified both in the actual conditions of occurrence of the events and in the simulations, to highlight any deficiencies connected to the human factor. The analysis of non-conformities relating to procedures, regulations, and operating instructions, detected because of inspections and/or accidents/near-accidents, generally linked to human error, can highlight deficiencies related to the behaviour of people, the organization, and the work environment. Such deficiencies must be subject to appropriate corrective actions.

Emergency drills are an important element of evaluation. They must be carried out according to a specific path that goes from planning to the critical analysis of the results, to prepare any corrective actions, also in terms of response times and emergency management of the operators to reduce the possibility of accidents related to human error.

5. The consideration of the human factor in the SMS

Based on the experience coming from the control activities conducted on some Seveso Italian establishments, in the following the discussion about examples and indications of particular or recurring situations are given about the consideration of the human factor in the SMS. The inspections must mainly be aimed at evaluating how much the company policy, and therefore the management system, require that human factors are taken into consideration in the conduct of the plant's activities, identifying any deficiencies.

The aspects that must be taken into consideration are the organizational elements, the policy and standards followed in the design and modification phases of the plants, the operating conditions, including problems related to process management, and the working environments [12].

As regards the design phases of new processes or operating systems, it must be evident that the company policy or the standards adopted foresee the consideration of human factors. Indicative of the fact that human factors have been considered is, for example, the evidence of the analysis of the aspects related to the spaces available to the operators, the accessibility of the equipment, the correct construction and location of the control panels and the use of prototypes and pilot plants also for the analysis and revision of the operator-plant interface.

At an operational level, information on work shifts must be acquired, for example by verifying that the available resources are distributed in a homogeneous manner, or in any case congruent with the workload, that the responsibilities have been clearly identified and are commensurate with the experience and ability of the employee to identify the cause of an error which may also cause a major accident. In fact, it must be considered that stress and fatigue can be the result of incorrect personnel management. To identify a possible deficiency in this sense, one could, for example, analyse the criteria for allocating resources within the various operational areas, verifying whether both the physical and aptitude characteristics and the degree of experience, which must be possessed by the person responsible for the critical tasks of the plant, have been specified.

Regarding the operating procedures available to operators, the main aspects to consider are that these are clear and complete, written in a language that operators can understand, that their involvement in drafting and revision has been

envisaged and, most importantly, that these procedures provide employees with all the elements that enable them to identify and manage unforeseen situations.

It should be remembered that the conditions of the working environment (lighting, temperature, exposure to noise, vibrations or chemical agents, etc.) also play a fundamental role in the employee's ability to interact with the systems and equipment. In this regard, it will be important to verify not so much that the values of these parameters are compatible with the activity carried out, but rather that national and international standards have been considered in the organization of the activity for the definition of optimal conditions in the workplace, providing, in the procedures, the analyses to establish what are the levels that allow to guarantee efficiency and safety. Finally, it should be considered that the system must provide for the periodic measurement of these parameters, to verify that the pre-established limits are respected, adopting compensatory measures in case it is not possible to respect the limit.

6. Conclusions

The consideration of the human factors and the interfaces between operators, processes, and plants, with the correct design and the distribution of workspaces, in the implementation of a safety management system must be based on:

The detection of any problems at the interfaces, thanks to the feedback information coming from both the operators and the maintenance technicians

Monitoring the status of equipment and systems. It is important that equipment is visually inspected throughout the work shift. Reading the instruments placed on the equipment makes it possible to verify the reliability of the parameters reported by the remote-control systems in the control room. Furthermore, only through visual inspections anomalous situations can be promptly identified. The information found must be recorded on special checklists which must be reviewed on a periodic basis by the supervisors so that what is reported is consistent with other data and that any anomalous situations are promptly resolved. In addition, it is good practice to have equipment checks integrated with normal operations

An adequate maintenance of work tools and equipment, including maintaining good conditions of cleanliness and order in the workplace (s.c. housekeeping)

The use of correct labelling and signalling of containers, pipes, equipment, etc., also through appropriate colour codes, to allow immediate knowledge of the risks and the identification of systems and components. Of specific importance, for example, are the methods for signalling automatic blocks to the switchboard, especially in the event of a bypass due to contingent plant requirements, with the relative operating management procedure

5) The maintenance of good lighting conditions, essential for identifying the equipment, reading the instruments and identifying possible problems

The improvement of the reliability of the operators' performances. Particular attention should be paid to the procedures for handing over deliveries between shift managers and/or switchboard operators during shift changes in the plant and in the control room, keeping adequate traces in the system documentation

The implementation of an effective system of operational controls based on procedures, permits, inspections, etc., that allows to prevent or promptly identify any human errors before they cause accidents

The functionality of the operator/process and operator/equipment interfaces to make it easier for the operator to monitor the process, identify any anomalies or emergencies and implement the foreseen intervention methods. Consider, for example, the problem of managing a maximum number of alarms on screen in the event of a generalized emergency, or the problem of assessing reliability/redundancy for critical alarms (in the event of a power failure)

The Security prevention and mitigation measures concern both the physical and IT protection of Seveso activities and the people present. The analysis of Security vulnerabilities due to intentional attacks such as sabotage, terrorism, and retaliation, allows to identify the measures for the reduction of the relative risk according to the best practices in the field.

The two management systems, Security and Safety have different correlations and therefore can be integrated, starting from the correct consideration of the HMI, according to the indications mentioned above. Security can, in this way, be considered as an integral part of Safety.

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Baseline reports in IED installations: a reference model for data elaboration

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1 The problem

Industry is responsible for the release of many pollutants, with impacts on air, soil and water and producing other emission (noise, odours, etc.). This led global institutions and governments to develop and plan regulatory activities.

The European Union established a unified legislative framework in 1996, matured with the adoption of Directive 2010/75/EU (Industrial Emission Directive - IED) [1], until to Directive 2024/1785 [2]. The IED aims at enhancing the Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control (IPPC) process, by promoting the Best Available Techniques (BAT) for industrial activities. The normative is adopted and transposed, in Italy, into national law (D.Lgs 152/2006 and subsequent amendments [3]). In this framework, soil protection has remained fragmented across various policies and strategies [4]. Nonetheless, the IED has mandated since 2010 the preparation of “baseline reports” for soil and groundwater conditions for installations seeking environmental authorization.

Only few references have been released at a European level to address soil protection and monitoring in industrial sites, such as the European guidelines on baseline reports for IED installations [5].

In Italy the Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA) provides a support to the competent Authority (Ministry of Environment and Energy Security - MASE) for IED implementation, to assess technical documents sent by Operators. Hence, ISPRA developed a systematic model to assess these baseline reports in Italy.

The study examined 15 industrial sites, primarily refineries and large chemical plants. They were selected due to the complexity of their production cycles and the presence of hazardous substances. The baseline reports, submitted by Operators of IED Installations, were reviewed to assess their compliance with environmental permit requirements. Data acquired for the study is available on MASE website [6].

The analysis of such case studies resulted in the elaboration of a checklist, where we included indicators with a closed answer “YES/NO”, divided in two key areas:

- A. Industrial cycle and hazardous substances. This category was established to assess the comprehensiveness of information provided on production processes, raw materials, chemicals used, and emissions. Particular attention was given to the identification of hazardous substances, their quantities, and potential pathways for soil and groundwater contamination.
- B. Soil and groundwater conditions. This category allowed evaluating the reference state of environmental matrices through historical data, site investigation reports, and monitoring programs.

The checklist has been proposed to offer a more systematic assessment of baseline reports, ensuring greater consistency in reviewing data. In fact, through this study, we observed a significant variability in the level of detail provided by operators, especially concerning hazardous substances and their potential environmental impact. In some cases, crucial data on waste management practices and spill prevention measures were missing or incomplete. Moreover, some issues were related to the hydrogeological assessments and contamination risk evaluations.

In our opinion, the proposed model could enhance the technical homogeneity of baseline report evaluations and supports regulatory authorities, operators, and researchers in identifying potential data gaps. Additionally, it could open pathways for further research. In fact, in literature, many research applications on data start from the use of standards to collect raw information. The potential integration of artificial intelligence techniques (e.g., k-means clustering) could be promoted by the use of our checklist and facilitate more sophisticated analyses, by identifying patterns in soil and groundwater contamination data.

Overall, it contributes to the ongoing discussion on baseline report assessments within the EU, where such reports remain a challenge in several countries [7].

However, a limitation of the study is its national focus, which may require adaptations for broader European application. Moreover, some changes could rise in the application of such model to installations subjected to IED framework at a regional level, due to differences in IPPC categories and thresholds.

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Proof testing according to IEC 61508: an efficient tool to deal with the aging of safety-related systems in process plants

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Abstract

In the process industry, Safety Instrumented Systems (SIS) are used in a low-demand mode of operation. In this operating mode, a safety system is rarely put into action. This happens once a year at most. Therefore, for about one year, the safety system has never been activated by a demand raised by the process.

To verify the status of a safety instrumented system, periodic tests of the system have to be conducted. Periodic tests are also called proof tests and refer to the whole safety system, composed of at least one sensor, one logic solver, and one final element. The main purpose of the proof tests is to find the failures undetected through internal diagnostics. But actual proof tests are not perfect, so the failures undetected through internal diagnostics cannot be completely uncovered. The failures undetected by a proof test pass on to the next proof test. If they are not found overtime, sooner or later the safety instrumented system encounters one of them, causing a safety-related accident. Therefore, it is necessary to study the influence of imperfect proof tests on the probability of failure for safety instrumented systems. The old version of IEC 61508 "Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems" (2000) does not consider the imperfection of proof tests, which is equivalent to assuming the "proof test coverage" equal to 100%. This is not reasonable. The new version of IEC 61508 (2010) points out that, when verifying the PFDavg (Probability of Failure on Demand) in low low-demand mode of operation, a "proof test coverage" smaller than 100% has to be considered.

The paper describes the imperfection of proof tests and analyses the influence of the "proof test coverage" on the probability of failure for safety instrumented systems operating in process plants, of relevance when dealing with hazardous substances such as those present in the Seveso establishments.

1 Introduction

In the process industry, Safety Instrumented Systems (SIS) are used in low demand mode of operation. In this operating mode, a safety system is rarely put into action. This happens once a year at most. Therefore, for about one year, the safety system has never been activated by a demand raised by the process.

To verify the status of a safety instrumented system, periodic tests of the system must be conducted. Periodic tests are also called proof tests and refer to the whole safety system, composed at least of one sensor, one logic solver, and one final element. The main purpose of the proof tests is finding the failures undetected through internal diagnostics. Actual proof tests are not perfect, so the failures undetected through internal diagnostics cannot be completely uncovered. The failures, undetected by a proof test, pass on to the next proof test. If they are not found over time, sooner or later, the safety instrumented system encounters one of them, causing a safety-related accident. Therefore, it is necessary to study the influence of imperfect proof tests on the probability of failure for safety instrumented systems.

The old version of the standard IEC 61508 (2000) does not consider the imperfection of proof tests, which is equivalent to assuming the "proof test coverage" equal to 100%. This is not reasonable. The new version of IEC 61508 (2010) [1] points out that, when verifying the PFDavg in low-demand mode of operation, a "proof test coverage" smaller than 100% has to be considered.

The paper describes the imperfection of proof tests and analyses the influence of the "proof test coverage" on the probability of failure for safety instrumented systems operating in process plants. This issue should be particularly considered in the context of the process establishments that fall under the Seveso III Directive (Directive 2012/18/EU aims to prevent major accidents involving dangerous substances and to limit their consequences for human health and the environment) [2], and it is increasingly analysed during SMS (Safety Management System) inspections.

2 Types of failures in safety-related systems

When a dangerous operating condition is detected, the safety system has to intervene successfully to bring the process back to a safe state. The safety system can intervene successfully only if all its components run perfectly, i.e., they are not affected by failures.

The failures in safety-related systems can be “safe” or “dangerous”. Besides being safe or dangerous, failures are also classified as “detected” or “undetected” by IEC 61508.

According to the standard, there are four types of failures:

- Safe Detected (SD) failures;
- Safe Undetected (SU) failures;
- Dangerous Detected (DD) failures;
- Dangerous Undetected (DU) failures.

Therefore, the total failure rate λ is the sum of four components:

$$\lambda = \lambda_{SD} + \lambda_{SU} + \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{DU}$$

IEC 61508 defines “safe” a failure that is either safe by design or it is a dangerous failure that is immediately detected and corrected. Safe failures are not a problem. Even dangerous detectable failures are not a problem since they are promptly detected by internal diagnostics. Internal diagnostics are usually carried out through functional tests to ensure that the specified function is working correctly.

3 Diagnostic Coverage

However, do internal diagnostics reveal all failures? Not all failures of the safety instrumented system can be completely detected through a self-diagnostic test.

Diagnostic Coverage (DC) defines the number of dangerous failures detected through internal diagnostics. DC is expressed as a percentage of the revealed failures, classified as Detected Dangerous (DD):

$$DC = \lambda_{DD} / \lambda_D \quad (1)$$

where:

- λ_{DD} is the Dangerous Detected (DD) failure rate;
- λ_D is the total failure rate: $\lambda_D = \lambda_{DD} + \lambda_{DU}$

Therefore, the Dangerous Detected (DD) failure rate can be expressed as follows:

$$\lambda_{DD} = \lambda_D DC \quad (2)$$

The Dangerous Undetected (DU) failure rate can be written using the complementary expression:

$$\lambda_{DU} = \lambda_D (1 - DC) \quad (3)$$

The calculation of the probability of failure for safety instrumented systems is based only upon the Dangerous Undetected (DU) failure rate, since a critical state is caused by dangerous failures that are not detected by internal diagnostics. After their occurrence, there is no way to detect them. They exist until the safety system is shut down to carry out “off-line tests”, known as proof tests. Performing proof tests is the only way to detect undetectable dangerous failures.

	Detected	Undetected
Safe	negligible	accepted
Dangerous	accepted since detected	

Figure 1

4 Proof tests

The standard IEC 61508 defines proof test as “a periodic test performed to detect dangerous hidden failures in a safety-related system so that, if necessary, a repair can restore the system to an ‘as new condition’ or as close as practical to this condition”. The proof test is a periodic test performed to detect dangerous failures not detectable through internal diagnostics.

The standard assumes that the safety system returns "as new" at the end of the test. This is true only if the proof test is perfect, i.e., it can reveal all the failures.

Reality is different: even if all the components of the safety system are individually tested and the test is carried out as indicated in the user manual by the manufacturer of the system, it is unlikely that 100% of dangerous failures, not detectable through internal diagnostics, are uncovered.

In simple terms, proof tests are carried out:

- to verify that all the components of a safety-related system run properly.
- to uncover the Dangerous Undetected failures hidden deep inside safety-related systems.

Proof tests can detect the dangerous failures undetected through diagnostic tests, but they cannot reveal all potential dangerous failures since they are imperfect.

4.1 Proof test interval

A good understanding of proof testing is essential for functional safety. The purpose of the proof tests is to verify that sensors, logic solvers, and final elements in Safety Instrumented Systems respond properly to hazardous conditions. The system reaction is needed to prevent process-related accidents.

By subjecting the system to proof tests, it is possible to uncover hidden failures such as valve leaks, sensor drifts, or bugs in the logic solvers, that were not noticed during normal inspections or left covered by internal diagnostics. Then, corrective actions are taken to ensure the reliability of the safety instrumented system.

Does the safety instrument system meet the required Probability of Failure on Demand (PFD)? The PFD represents the probability that the safety-related system fails to react in occurrence of a potentially dangerous situation the system is supposed to detect. The PFD is usually determined as an average probability over a time frame. The PFD_{AVG} corresponds to a measure of the system's inability to perform the safety function in a specified period, assumed equal to the proof time interval T_p .

The frequency at which the system is proof tested has a significant impact on the average Probability of Failure on Demand of the system [3]. Since the PFD_{AVG} is heavily dependent on the frequency at which a SIS and its components are tested, the proof test interval must be chosen properly. Differently, the PFD_{AVG} may be too high, and the “required SIL level” may not be met. The Safety Integrity Level (SIL) measures the effectiveness of a safety system in reducing risk. SIL is defined as four discrete levels, from SIL1 to SIL4. Each SIL value represents an order of magnitude in risk reduction: the greater the SIL value, the greater the risk reduction.

When estimating the PFD_{AVG} of a safety instrumented system, the frequency at which the system is tested has a significant impact. Therefore, if the system is not tested at the specified interval, it is likely that a dangerous undetected failure is left hidden until a demand is placed upon the system by the process, potentially leading the system not to respond when this is needed. This situation is unacceptable for functional safety.

The importance of the proof test interval can be better understood from the formula of the PFD_{AVG}. A pressure vessel

containing 300 m³ of LPG is considered as an example in Figure 2.

When the safety instrumented system, with a 1oo1 voting architecture, reacts to the demand of overpressure protection, its PFD_{AVG} can be evaluated as follows:

$$PFD_{AVG} = \lambda_{DU} T_p / 2 \tag{4}$$

where λ_{DU} is the “dangerous undetected failure rate” and T_p is the “proof test interval”.

As shown by Eq. (4), PFD_{AVG} is proportional to both “proof test interval T_p ” and Dangerous Undetected (DU) failure rate

Figure 2

The shorter the proof test interval, the lower the probability of failure for the safety instrumented system. Though a short proof test interval reduces the probability of failure for safety systems, it increases the costs of manpower and material resources, so that the choice of an affordable proof test interval is crucial for proper maintenance of safety instrumented systems in process plants. Process technicians are required to optimize the proof test interval T_p . They must evaluate the proof test interval properly to maintain the Safety Integrity Level of the system at the required level without increasing the costs too much. Although PFD tends to increase over time, performing proof tests brings the PFD down, almost to the original level. But PFD rarely goes back to the initial value. Figure 3 illustrates this.

Figure 3

4.2 Types of proof tests

There are two types of proof tests:

- full proof tests;
- partial proof tests.

Full proof tests provide a Proof Test Coverage (PTC) close to 100%. They test the whole system under actual operating conditions to make sure it responds to hazardous conditions on demand. They represent the most comprehensive type of proof tests since they are designed to detect all potentially dangerous undetected failures (DU) in safety instrumented systems. On the other hand, partial proof tests only prove some failure modes of a safety component. They are less comprehensive than full proof tests, but they are still important. Partial proof tests can be performed from a distance and are less time-consuming than full proof tests. They are commonly conducted when the components of a safety system have different dangerous undetected failure rate so that their PFD calculation does not line up with planned

process shutdowns. This is the case of ESD (Emergency ShutDown) valves that are usually subjected to partial proof tests in process plants. The frequency of both proof tests is based on the PFD_{AVG} calculation. Full proof tests bring the Probability of Failure on Demand close to its original level, while partial proof tests bring the PFD back to a percentage of its original level, usually not greater than 70%. Safety components with lower dangerous failure rates, such as sensors and logic solvers, require less frequent and invasive proof tests. Safety components with a lower level of reliability, such as ESD valves, need to be tested more often and with more impactful test methods.

4.3 Effects of imperfect proof tests

The implications of imperfect proof tests on the safety system can be significant since undetected failures can lead to the system not reacting on demand, with possible subsequent major accidents.

This can be mitigated by developing efficient test procedures that provide adequate details to ensure that proof tests are conducted properly before the safety system is placed back into service.

Proof tests should reveal every undetected failure and restore the system to an “as new condition”, but this rarely happens for several reasons that will be examined in the following. Imperfect proof tests result in a gradual increase in the Probability of Failure on Demand over time, which eventually leads the system not to match the PFD requirement. If the PFD_{AVG} value of the whole Safety Instrumented System (SIS) stays within the required SIL, no additional measure is required. However, if the PFD_{AVG} ends up in a SIL value lower than the required SIL, some additional measures are promptly required. Therefore, it is important to conduct proof tests according to the specified test interval to ensure that the safety system maintains its reliability in achieving functional safety.

4.4 Proof test effectiveness

The effectiveness of a periodic proof test is measured by the Proof Test Coverage (PTC) which indicates the percentage of dangerous failures detected by the test. If effectiveness is lower than 100%, the proof test is considered imperfect since it is not able to bring the probability of failure of the system back to zero.

Therefore, PFD_{AVG} progressively increases over time. In this case, the system does not always maintain the original SIL level throughout its lifetime.

The formula for calculating PFD_{AVG} when PTC is smaller than 100% is shown in the following:

$$PFD_{AVG} = \frac{1}{2} \lambda_{DU} \cdot T_p \cdot PTC + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_{DU} \cdot T_L (1 - PTC) \quad (5)$$

where T_L is the system lifetime, assumed equal to the time until the system is proof tested or replaced. Figure 4 shows this.

Figure 4

4.5 Developing efficient proof test procedures

When developing a proof test procedure, several factors must be considered to ensure accuracy and effectiveness of the proof tests.

- Since predictive maintenance is very rarely used in the context of functional safety, adopt a Reliability-Based Maintenance (RBM) to evaluate the system reliability properly. A miscalculation of the system reliability leads to a false sense of safety or brings to overly conservative safety measures.
- Consider human errors. Operating personnel can introduce errors, leading to an inaccurate assessment of the system's reliability over time. To minimize these errors, enhance training programs for operating personnel [4].
- Pay attention to the variability in the proof test interval. The more frequently a proof test is run and the more extensive the test is, the greater the safety integrity level will be. However, frequent tests can be time-consuming and expensive. To reach a balance, choose the largest proof test interval that allows meeting the required SIL.
- Keep records of the proof test results. Make sure that the proof tests are conducted thoroughly, accurately, regularly, and that the results are carefully analysed and documented to identify potential opportunities for improvement. By addressing these factors, it is possible to develop proof test procedures that contribute to the continuous improvement of the maintenance culture.
- Think about performing additional tests. Full proof tests may not detect failures, due to loose connections or corrosion, that result in delayed operations of the actuators or leakages in closed positions of the ESD valves. To mitigate this risk, perform partial proof tests in addition to full proof tests. Figure 5 illustrates this.
- Improve maintenance culture. The quality of the proof tests is heavily influenced by the plant maintenance culture. To ensure the accuracy of the proof tests, make sure the proof tests are integrated into the site maintenance policy. To ensure the effectiveness of the proof tests, review and update the proof test procedures to reflect changes in the system design and operation.

Figure 5

5 Conclusions

The new version of the standard IEC 61508 analyses the imperfection of proof tests since it can fail safety instrumented systems at any time in their lifetime. At first, the paper points out the necessity of proof tests and their impact on the probability of failure for safety instrumented systems. Then, the influence of the imperfection of proof tests on system performance is deeply analyzed. IEC 61508 assumes that a Proof Test Coverage (PTC) equal to 100% is not reasonable. To consider the effects of imperfect proof testing, the paper calculates the probability of failure for safety instrumented systems by adopting a PTC smaller than 100%.

Finally, the paper describes several factors that must be considered to ensure accuracy and effectiveness when developing a proof test procedure, including: Adoption of Reliability-Based Maintenance (RBM); Consideration of the human errors; Variability in the proof test interval; Recording the proof test results; Performing additional tests; Improving maintenance culture. These issues should be particularly considered in the context of the Seveso process establishments, analysing them during the SMS inspections.

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The integration of information and operational technologies and the emerging risks for Seveso establishments

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Abstract

OT and IT systems, in process industries, were traditionally operated in isolation, with separate technologies, protocols, and units. In the last decade with the digital transition, OT and IT are increasingly integrated, with advantages for profitability, reliability and efficiency. This integration, however, induces new risk related to possible cyber incidents, both intentional and unintentional. At Seveso sites, a possible cyber event not only compromises data integrity and confidentiality, but could also affect control and regulation systems, with loss of containment, release of hazardous materials and accident scenarios. Even if no "major" incidents due to cyber causes have been reported at Seveso sites, there are many minor incidents, near misses and anomalies, which should be studied as early warnings of emerging risks, to promote awareness among duty-holders, control bodies and regulators. Thus, the reports of recent inspections, conducted throughout Italy, have been scrutinized and about sixty events have been found and analysed, exploiting machine learning methods, a few vulnerabilities emerged in both OT and IT. The obtained results show that there is too low attention on the protection of IT and OT systems, even though, at now, most problems are due to unintentional incidents.

1. Background and Objectives

1.1 Importance of the "cyber layer" for major accident prevention

Software is increasingly used to control critical functions in industries, and errors in these systems can directly contribute to accidents. In the establishments under the EU Directive Seveso III for major accident prevention, these errors can result in severe consequences for assets, humans and environment. Software, or better the cyber layer that include hardware and software, is essential to organize all safety related activities in the establishment, including document and training management, maintenance planning, warehouse management and safety reporting. Even more important is the software installed on board the electronic regulation and control systems, distributed in the plant. The robustness of software systems is no less important for safety than the integrity of primary containment systems, the functionality of rotating machinery, the reliability of electrical and electronic control systems and the adequacy of human and organizational factors. Unlike other systems, software is not subject to forms of physical degradation, but can be subject to misconfigurations, design and implementation defects that might emerge also after a long time, to misuses for poorly designed or poorly documented user interfaces and to obsolescence, due to the inability to adapt to changes in the external context. Physical degradation is possible for hardware parts, but it is usually neglected, as obsolescence is much faster. Increasing complexity and interdependencies make it possible for attacks by malicious software agents that are usually introduced intentionally. Software with internal defects, poorly documented, badly used and not protected from external agents can be the root cause of prolonged operational interruptions and even containment losses with severe consequences for humans and environment. The problem of flawed software as cause of accidents in process and other industries is well known from past investigations. Wong et al. (2009) provided the operator with a lot of useful suggestions to avoid software related accidents, based on the experience of a number of major accidents triggered by software failures. Today, with the digitization of all activities, the issue of software vulnerability must be approached in more general terms, thinking about the "cyber layer", which is a much broader term and includes the hardware part that supports the software. For the control of major accident hazard, "cyber layer" is no less important than chemical, mechanical, electrical and management components, on which all attention of practitioners is still focused.

1.2 Information Technology and Operating Technology

The term "cyber layer" is a very general term, and it is an "umbrella" that include Information Technology (IT) and Operational technology (OT). Operational technology systems (OT) refer to the hardware and software used to monitor, manage and control operations like distributed control systems DCS, programmable logic controllers PLC, SCADA, sensors, and robotics. On the other side, Information Technology systems (IT) are the technological infrastructure handling an organization's data and information-related functions like Communication, Purchasing, Sell, Finance, and Human Resources. Safety of Seveso establishments is assured by technical and organizational systems, which act as

"barriers" to prevent containment losses and mitigate consequences. Most "technical barriers" trust on operational technology OTs. The "organizational barriers" trust on Information Technology (IT), which manages procedures functions and document. As technical and management systems are equally important for major accident prevention, both OT and IT must be considered essential resources for safety. OT and IT systems in the process industries, were traditionally operated in insulation with separate technology, protocols and organizational units. In the last decade, however, with the Fourth Industrial Revolution and increases in industrial internet of thing (IIoT), OT and IT are integrating more and more. That is assumed to provide large benefits for the profitability, reliability and safety (Ansaldi et al. 2018). Unfortunately, the tight integration between OT and IT introduces new risks related to, but not limited to, cybersecurity aspects. In the process industries, these issues are not only about the loss of valuable data or the disclosure of confidential information but can also compromise control and regulation systems and potentially lead to losses of containment, with release of hazardous substances and related consequences workers, environment and asset. The scope of Seveso does not only include large refineries or petrochemical plants, which are operated by large organizations, capable of ensuring particularly high-quality software. Many Seveso sites are minor chemical plants, operated by small and medium sized enterprises SME, which cannot access high-end software vendors and are, therefore, more prone to software vulnerability issue.

1.3 State of the art

The risk related to the weaknesses of the cyber layer, including both IT and OT, is an emerging risk for Seveso industries and it is therefore important to have more numerous and reliable data to monitor the scenario and understand the true extent of the phenomenon in order to define concrete indications to manage the risk well in advance. The relevance of cybersecurity for IT system has been globally recognised as emphasised by the vast number of studies on the topic and by several legislative initiative as, for example, the EU NIS2 directive (EU, 2022). However, only recently there is a specific focus on cybersecurity OT due to some episodes as the 10-days stop of the largest oil pipeline in US (Beerman et al., 2023). However, at the moment there is still little data available for cyber risk at Seveso plant, in fact just early warnings rather than clear evidence, but it is important to collect this data, organize the information and extract knowledge that can be useful for those who have to make decisions. In the scientific literature there are some reviews, here are two that have appeared recently: the first (Stergiopoulos et al. 2020) concerns only oil & gas 42 events, between upstream, midstream and downstream. Half with severe consequences. Most frequent attacks: Malware and external phishing; Injection Internal. Impact on control logic, availability and property. 10 cascade consequences with major losses. The second review (Iaianni et al. 2021) covers various industries and covers 82 cases: 35 events are accidental, 47 intentional. In (Ylonen et al., 2022) it is stressed that in the last 20 years, about 27% of recorded security incidents had cyber-related causes and, except for a peak between 2000 and 2004, they showed an almost constant time trend, stressing the ongoing nature of the issue despite the increasing awareness of cyber-risks. Briefly, it can be said that a good assessment of cyber risk is nowadays a matter of paramount importance for process industries (Nobili et al. 2023) and for the Seveso establishments. The data available in the literature always refer to events with major consequences, while it is much more difficult to find data on minor incidents or near misses. In the literature there is a higher interest for intentional events, but the impact of unintentional event cannot be ignored. In this regard, it is relevant the incident of July 19, 2024, caused by a trivial error in CrowdStrike software, distributed by Microsoft. The event impacted 8 million of users, causing 5 billion USD damages and severe disruption on critical entities, including flights, health services, banking and retail around the world (Santos-Reyes, 2025). Even though process industries were less impacted, this was a clear signal for the higher and higher degree of interconnection cyber layers and, consequently, of the importance of increasing the software robustness.

1.4 Objectives

The aim of this work is to collect concrete data on the risks related to the vulnerability of the cyber layer, including both OT and IT, without having to wait for major incidents. Most recorded events are unintentional. It is a matter of understanding the weak signals coming out of the Seveso sector can help to understand the emergence of this new risk in advance, to better control it. The article is organized as follows, the second chapter is dedicated to the data available in Italy and abroad, the third to the analysis methods used, the fourth to the results obtained by working on the available data. In the last chapter a critical discussion of the results and some practical suggestions for stakeholders, plant operators and competent authorities.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Sources of data

For this purpose, it is important to continuously gather data about anomalies, near-misses and minor accidents that occur in the operation of the plants and related with cyber events. A reliable source of information comes from INAIL/EsOpIA, a repository containing over six thousand reports of accidents and near misses diligently collected in the last twenty years during inspections at the approximately one thousand Seveso plants in Italy.

Seveso inspectors insist on reporting near misses because they believe it is an important opportunity to learn from experience. Thus, in INAIL/EsOpIA you can also find a lot of information on the corrective actions taken by the company to avoid the recurrence of failures, which can be useful to the entire Seveso community. In this archive some 6000 events are collected (Ansaldi et al. 2021). Exploiting such unique repository, we can investigate how many events can be traced back to cyber problems. The study discriminates accidents due to hostile intentions and unintentional ones. Among the latter, criticalities are due to the poor quality of the software, the unreliability of the hardware, the inadequate management of access, the negligence of the operators and the sloppiness of the operators.

The documents available in the INAIL/EsOpIA repository are of different quality and the causal relationship is not always well described, but the use of machine learning methods makes it possible to extract information that is not so evident to a direct reading. In this way it is possible to build a credible causal model of potential cyber triggered incidents (Simone et al. 2023). For a broader comparison, incidents and accidents reported in another accident databases, including the French Barpi/ARIA and the European eMars.

2.2 Methods

Two methods have been used to explore the above-mentioned accident repositories. The first one is aimed at finding the occurred failures and understanding causes and consequences. The second one is a bit more advanced and is aimed the actual role of software in accident dynamic.

2.2.1 Search by keywords

The first goal is to find in the incident databases (ARIA or ESOPIA) the events, incidents or near misses, which was caused by any problem in cyber layer, including software failures and cyberattacks. To do that, as a first step, a few keywords was selected and looked for in the many events recorded in the databases. The searched keywords include “software” “cyber” “malware” and “virus”. The term “software” is common and often it is present in the text, but it is not related to the accident. The event was included only if a software failure was present the reported causes.

2.2.2 Search by Model

As EsOpIA has the capability to find the causal relations hidden in the document, it is important to have a model defined a priori to address the automatic analysis. For this purpose, the bow-tie method was chosen, according to the definitions of the ISO 31010 standard (ISO, 2019). The bowtie puts the top event in the centre, on the left side the barriers that prevent the top event from occurring, on the right the barriers that mitigate the consequences when the top event occurs. The top event can be the loss of containment or the interruption of service, which in some cases can be no less important. Our analysis is focused on the cyber layer, bringing together OT and IT. Other barriers were not investigated, as out of the scope of the paper. Figure 1 summarizes in a single picture, the importance of cyber layer, according to the bow-tie schema. At the very centre, there is the top event. On the left there are the protective systems, more external the IT systems that support the procedural and organizational part, more inside the OT part that presides over the direct control of the process and prevention (e.g. interlocks). On the right, inside, there is the OT part, which presides over the various protection systems (e.g. automatic deluge systems), externally, there is the IT part, which presides over emergency management (e.g. emergency telecommunications systems). IT and OT as you understand are essential at every level.

Figure 1. bow-tie model for cyber preventive and protective safety barriers.

3. Results

3.1 Operating experience in Italy

3.1.1 Failure modes and consequences

In EsOpIA there are 65 events recorded in the interval 2007-2022. No events clearly connected to intentional attacks, but most of them are due to coding errors in the software in the OT systems. The plausible causes of errors include software inadequate specifications and developers' negligence. In several cases the errors occurred as a particular situation was not considered; in this case the classification "software design error" was adopted, to distinguish these cases from errors in software implementation. There are also a few of events classified as "software crash". These are cases briefly described, and it is not possible to understand if they are errors or defects in the software or the presence of any viruses or other malicious software. The term "software misuse" was used for the events originated by an improper use of the software. The causes of that includes a poor user interface or an inadequate training. There are also intriguing cases due to software with outdated or incompatible versions, which have been classified as "software obsolescence". Faults in IT systems, classified as "IT software failure" do not impact directly on physical systems, but they can jeopardize safety procedures becoming a remote cause for loss of materials.

As mentioned no cyberattacks have been found in EsOpIA. This does not mean that there are no cyber-attacks in the Italian Seveso plants, but rather that these, fortunately, did not have consequences involving hazardous materials and, consequently, there is no obligation to report them to the Seveso inspectors.

The consequences have grouped in five types of increasing severity. No consequences were assigned when the reported event was not a near miss, but just a potentially dangerous situation. Operation discontinuity means that operation was interrupted for a time interval, usually a few hours, the worst a couple of day. Loss of containment means that there was a form of release of hazardous materials (e.g. leakage) without other consequence for humans, assets and environment. Damaged equipment means that a direct or indirect consequence of the software failure was a damage, usually repairable. Fire means a fire was caused directly or indirectly by a software failure, without further consequences. Environmental consequences were not reported. In Table 1 show failure mode of the software and relate consequences, as fine in EsOpIA. It is important to add that all events reported are related to chemical plants and most of them are small batch plants.

Table 1. Table 1 Cyber Failure Modes and effects source EsOpIA.

Consequences→ ↓ Failure Mode	no consequences	operation discontinuity	loss of containment	damaged equipment	fire
OT software failure (coding error)	5	13	10	1	2
OT software Obsolescence		3			
OT software failure (design error)	3	6	5	1	1
OT Software misuse		2	1		
OT software failure (system error)		5			
IT software failure	4	2	1		
TOTALS	12	31	17	2	3

3.1.2 Bow-tie analysis.

Analysing in the detail the content of the reports, the impact of cyber events on different safety barriers have been investigated, according to the bow-tie schema outlined in chapter 3. Results have been summarized in Table 2. The table is organized as follows: the first row represents the failures of the barriers that occurred in the accident sequence, in the second row the successes of the barriers that stopped the succession that would have led to the major accident. The first four columns represent preventive barriers, the last four protective barriers. Between preventive and protective barriers, the top event, i.e. the loss of containment. From the second line of the table, in 36 cases manual intervention stopped the consequences of the failure, in 7 cases it was a mechanical system, rupture disc or valve that stopped the sequence. Only in 12 cases did the top event come and the emergency procedures avoided major consequences.

Table 2. Cyber Failure Modes and effects source EsOpIA.

	Preventive Barriers				Top Event	Protective Barriers			
	Organization Procedures IT	automated controls OT	manual intervention	Physical Systems		Physical System	Automated controls OT	manual intervention	IT Protection system
Failed Barriers	7	53	2	4	12	0	0	0	0
Success Barriers	2	0	36	7		1	0	1	11

3.2 Operating experience in other European Countries

3.2.1 Accidents in France

A valuable source of information about accident is the BARPI/ARIA, which covers events that are reported in France and overseas¹. Among the thousands of accidents, which have been reported for years, some containment losses are beginning to appear that have a cyber event in the causes. In 2019, an alert was published with four cases: a wastewater treatment plant hit by cryptocurrency malware; an alert system failure; a sensor failure caused by an obsolete circuit and an incorrectly programmed PLC. In the following years, other episodes took place, which, although not collected, can be found directly in the database, which is “open access”. The same keywords as in paragraph 3.1 were used in the search. At the present, in the data base you can find 12 events due to cyber-attacks, 1 with major consequences. The records found in the database are very concise and the only distinction was between attacks at the OT level and attacks at the IT level. There are also 12 events due to software malfunction, 3 with severe consequences for workers. For software failures, the same classification as in Table 1 was used. It is important to note that all industrial sectors have been considered. Unlike EsOpIA, of the 24 events considered, only 11 concern chemical plants; 4 concern waste management plants, 3 wind plants, 3 gas plants and the rest is divided between explosives, hydroelectric and cement

¹ <https://www.aria.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/the-barpi/the-aria-database/?lang=en>
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plants. The same as in Table 1 were used for the failure modes, with the addition of two cyberattack modes for IT systems and for OT systems.

Table 3. Cyber Failure Modes and effects source BARPI/ARIA

Consequences→ ↓ Failure Mode	no consequences	operation discontinuity	loss of containment	damaged equipment	fire
OT Software Failure			4	2	3
OT software Obsolescence			1		
OT software misuse			1		
IT software failure			1		
OT Cyber Attack	2	3	1		
IT Cyber Attack	4	2			
TOTALS	6	5	8	2	3

3.2.2 Major Accidents in Europe

The Seveso Directive requires the National Authorities to upload a detailed report of any major accident in the eMars database, a database managed by the JRC Joint research centre of EU Commission ². At the present there are no accident is related to cyber-attacks. There are just a few events where the software inadequacy was included in the causes. In table 4 the 6 events occurred during the period 2010 -2021 are summarized, according to the schema “failure mode and consequences” used for table and table 3. It must be stressed that in eMars there are just accidents with very severe consequences and most software related events have consequences below the limits required for reporting in eMars. Obviously, there are no events without consequences and even operation discontinuity is not relevant. Unfortunately, in two cases, the consequences included the loss of human life. Of the considered events 3 occurred in oil and gas industry, 2 in chemical industry and 1 in metal.

Table 4. Cyber Failure Modes and effects source eMARS

Consequences→ ↓ Failure Mode	loss of containment	damaged asset	fire	casualties
OT software failure (coding)	1			
OT software Obsolescence	1		1	1
OT software failure (design error)	1		1	1
OT Software misuse	2			
IT software failure	1			
TOTALS	6		2	2

4. Discussion and Conclusions

4.1 Emerging issues

Figure 2 summarizes the 95 cases considered, 65 from EsOplA, 24 from ARIA, 6 from eMars. The unintentional failure modes are the same in the three distinct groups, but intentional cyber-attacks are present only in ARIA. In addition, In EsOplA and in eMars software failure caused by coding errors are distinguished from those caused by design errors and system errors, while in ARIA there is no such distinction. Thus, there is a larger slice “SW failure”, including the three subtypes coding, design, and system error. With these caveats in mind, the chart can be useful for an overview of the different software failure modes. The following parameters discuss the various failure modes with details and insights.

² <https://emars.jrc.ec.europa.eu/en/emars/accident/search>
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Figure 2. Distribution of the different modes of failure of the software.

4.1.1 OT Software Quality Issues

In the documents analysed, both in EsOpIA and in the other sources, it is evident that software design and development errors are the cause of more than half of the incidents in the cyber layer. At the end two thirds of the recorded events are due to errors in one or more phases of the software development (design, coding and testing). More than half of the errors are due to coding error, the so called "bugs". It is interesting to stress that software failures are recurrent in small and medium sized plant, which have less bargaining power in relations with software suppliers. In batch plants, in particular, slightly different situations arise every time and sometimes things go wrong because there is just one silly error in the OT software. In EsOpIA we find, for example, an unexpected exothermic reaction that, without the manual intervention of the operator, could led to a "runaway". An investigation of the event revealed that the cause was an error in the software that calculated the mass of loaded product based on the flow data. The offending piece of software only came into operation in the event of a malfunction of the weight cells and had never been tested.

4.1.2 OT software update issues

Five percent of the considered events is related to failure to update or to an update made in a careless or untimely manner. In the case of 19 July 2024, cited in the paragraph, large electricity, water and gas infrastructures were not affected, because they, as a rule, never make automatic updates (Sowby et al. 2025). A similar approach is followed even in the larger establishments and only in the smallest factories are these mistakes made. Even in EsOpIA there is a similar case, with less consequences. An updated version of DCS control software, just uploaded, caused abnormal behaviour of the thermoregulation systems, with the unwanted heating of three reactors, as well as the rupture of a serpentine.

4.1.3 User Interface and Training Issues

The user interface of OT software can be more challenging than that of popular software. This can be a cause of the frequent errors reported, together with the little or no training that is done on the use of the software. About 6% of the events considered are due to these causes. In an EsOpIA event, for example, the supervisor, following the blocking of a single computer, ignoring the interoperability of the various computers in the control room, stopped all reactors that could still be managed by other computers in the control room. That is, a security solution, such as interoperability, was thwarted by the lack of training.

4.1.4 Importance of IT Software

The management software in the Seveso plants involves many aspects of safety: maintenance, training, loading and unloading. In the end, at least ten percent of the recorded events are due to problems with the management software that produce serious effects on security. In EsOpIA, for example, problems related to product labels are reported. There

is one case of data reversal in product labels and another case of labels without the name. In both cases, the errors were intercepted, but we let you imagine that there would have been severe consequences otherwise.

4.1.5 Cyber attack

Since the evidence collected, the problem seems still limited. Many Seveso establishments, in fact, are not attractive business for criminals. In ARIA, waste treatment and wind farms are the most involved plants, for the presence of eco-activists who target them. In a further case the victim of the attack was a pharmaceutical plant, under fire because it participated in the production of Covid-19 vaccines, which at the time were the object of aversion.

4.1.6 Manual interventions

The ESOPIA data are unique because they highlight even the chain of interventions that ensured that a failure did not result in an accident. The analysis of the bowtie (§3.1.2) shows that in many cases automatic controls often require a manual switch. This is quite common in small chemical plants that work in batches and that also seem to be the most prone to software defects. In other cases, valves and rupture discs prevent loss of containment.

4.2 Remarks and Suggestions

In conclusion, from the operational experience reported in EsOplA, the high degree of digitalization of processes appears, leading, as an undesired side effects, to the vulnerability of the software (both IT and OT) that can be the cause of losses and injuries. The examples given refer to process industries where digitization has taken place in diverse ways, based on company size, internationalization and economic investment capacity. Thus, there is a substantial difference between larger companies and SMEs, where the resources dedicated to software development and maintenance are lower. One of the purposes of the study of near misses is also to identify emerging problems, which now manifest themselves as minor facts, but which can evolve over time and lead to severe consequences. Software-related events are a novelty that cannot be underestimated. In the risk analysis the reliability of the instrumentation is always considered, but it would also be necessary to include the reliability of the software as an origin of an accident chain. In plants subject to the European Seveso III Directive incidents due to cyber factors (intentional or unintentional) have never had consequences as severe as to be classified as "major accident" within the meaning of Annex VI of the same Directive. However, these are not good reasons to underestimate the risk, which according to the data analysed, seems to be growing, both in Italy and in France.

4.2.1 Suggestions for operators

Taking these aspects into account, considerations can be made that are of help to the operators who have implemented these systems, updating the suggestions provided many years by Wong et al. (2006). Operators who choose to manage and monitor processes and equipment through dedicated software must use products customized to the company reality. In the design, developers must have complete knowledge of the entire system, of the risks inherent in those activities and of the procedures. Customization must take place with the constant presence and advice of people who are experts in the processes and equipment on which the software acts. The tests prior to the production of such software or platforms must be passed without criticality and where critical issues arise, they must be carefully analysed, understood and resolved. They must always provide consoles for the continuous verification of correct operation to which personnel adequately trained to interpret any signs of anomaly in procedures or surveys must be dedicated. It is also important to have modularity and independence of some critical parts so that errors or malfunctions do not contaminate other procedures as well. You should never overlook signs of anomalies by trying to identify what the origin is if it is due to a problem in the software or if it depends on a deviation of the process from its normal operation.

4.2.2 Suggestions for control bodies

Similarly, auditors and control bodies that go to verify the safety of the plants will have to add to the normal feedback lists those elements of in-depth analysis of the IT and OT systems implemented in the company to verify that everything is "under control". It will be useful, for example, to ask how many and what maintenance interventions, or interruptions, in the use of software systems, there have been in a given period and if the extent of the damage to which they could lead has been assessed and understood. It is also necessary to verify the adequate preparation of the console operators in detecting deviations in the parameters that could cause problems. The aspects of "independence" of the processes from the reference software platforms should also be investigated if there are "bugs" that compromise their correct functioning.

4.2.3 Suggestions for regulators

This study aims to provide useful insights even for a regulatory updating. While waiting for an update of the Seveso legislation that explicitly considers the risks deriving from the interference between cyber risks and process risks, it is useful that cyber factors are now considered in the identification and analysis of risks in the safety reports. The bowtie model proposed in the present paper could be a good basis to include cyber factors in formal analysis method. In the current practice of Seveso safety reports, much of the attention is still paid to the reliability of physical barriers and to a lesser extent to organizational and procedural barriers. Attention on the vulnerability of cyber barriers is still very scarce, even if the issue, as shown by the data reported in the article, is increasing more and more. The introduction of artificial intelligence in software development does not promise to reduce the problem but rather opens new fronts. The OECD observatory for AI policy has recently reported an incident of a commercial AI-based glucose wearable control system that is leading to errors with serious effects for people's health (OECD.AI 2025). One can imagine that something like that could happen in the process industry too. Even the policy for the prevention of major incidents MAPP should also include explicit references to the cyber issues. The safety management system should include procedures and operating instructions to prevent errors or intentional acts in the cyber field from having repercussions on process safety. It is hoped that these suggestions will be accepted by the European legislator, which can give a binding character to the assessment of cyber vulnerabilities in the Seveso area. The fact that many Seveso sites are also subject to the CER Directive for the protection of critical entities can give further motivation to push in this direction.

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List of abbreviations and definitions

AI Artificial Intelligence

ARIA Analysis, Research and Information on Accident. It is a database managed by BARPI.

CER Critical Entities Resilience. It is a Directive of EU for the protection of Critical Infrastructures.

BARPI Bureau for Analysis of Industrial Risks and Pollutions of the French Ministry of Environment.

DCS Direct Control System. A digital system that controls industrial processes and operate plants and processes in real time.

EsOpIA Operational Experiences and Artificial Intelligence. It is a database managed by INAIL.

IIoT Industrial Internet of Things. The use in industrial applications of the Internet of Things technology, to machines, devices, and sensors.

INAIL Italian Institute for Assurance against Accident at Work.

IT Information Technology The technology (hardware and software) used for the storage, transmission and processing of data and information.

JRC Joint Research Centre. It is the European Commission's internal scientific service.

MAPP Major Accident Prevention Policy, mandatory at Seveso sites.

OECD Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development. It is an organization that connects over 100 countries worldwide.

OT Operating Technology. The technology (hardware and software) used to control and monitor physical processes, infrastructure, and devices.

PLC Programmable Logical Controller. A device designed to monitor and regulate machines and production processes in industrial environments, using automation technologies.

SCADA Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition. A system that uses hardware and software to monitor and control industrial processes. SCADA systems can operate locally or remotely.

SME Small Medium Sized Enterprises

SW Abbreviation for Software.

Towards a Maturity Framework for Gender Awareness of Business Process Management

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Abstract

Traditional Business Process Management (BPM) has historically emphasized efficiency, focusing on reducing costs, optimizing time, and minimizing errors. However, the advent of Industry 5.0 signals a paradigm shift, one that embraces human-centric values such as social equity, sustainability, and resilience as integral components of organizational processes. In response to this evolution, this paper introduces the first structured Maturity Framework for Gender Awareness in BPM. The framework addresses a critical gap in existing BPM methodologies by providing a comprehensive tool for assessing and enhancing gender equity across business processes. It features a staged model, ranging from gender blindness to full gender awareness, accompanied by measurable indicators and actionable guidance. At the core of the framework is the Maturity Canvas for Gender Awareness in Business Process Management, a conceptual tool that facilitates practical implementation. The framework's utility is demonstrated through a case study focused on solar panel installation, showcasing its potential to reengineer traditional processes toward greater inclusivity and social sustainability.

1. Introduction

Business Process Management has traditionally focused on improving performance by optimizing operational efficiency, lowering costs, and streamlining workflows. While these objectives remain important, the emergence of Industry 5.0 is reshaping priorities by promoting a more holistic and human-centric vision. This new paradigm emphasizes values such as inclusivity, social responsibility, and environmental sustainability alongside technological advancement. Unlike Industry 4.0's often technology-driven focus, Industry 5.0 highlights the irreplaceable value of human intelligence, creativity, and contextual judgment. This shift entails fostering deeper collaboration between humans and technologies (Patriarca et al., 2021), such as collaborative robots (cobots), artificial intelligence (AI), and the Internet of Things (IoT), not only to augment human capabilities but also to make processes more equitable and inclusive.

In this context, gender equity becomes a crucial dimension of inclusivity (De Nicola & D'Agostino, 2021) (Guariglia Migliore et al., 2025). Without intentional consideration of gender dynamics, organizations risk reinforcing existing inequalities and missing out on the full potential of a diverse workforce. Therefore, embedding a gender perspective in BPM is not merely a question of fairness. It is essential to designing industrial processes that are resilient (De Nicola et al., 2023) (D'Agostino & De Nicola, 2025) (De Nicola et al., 2025), adaptive, and genuinely human-centered. As such, advancing gender-aware BPM practices is key to realizing the full promise of Industry 5.0.

This paper presents a novel maturity framework specifically designed to address this gap in the current understanding and implementation of Business Process Management within the evolving landscape of Industry 5.0. Recognizing that traditional BPM methodologies often overlook or inadequately integrate gender awareness and inclusivity, this framework offers a structured, multi-level model. By delineating distinct stages of maturity, ranging from initial awareness to advanced integration, the framework guides organizations in evaluating their current gender awareness practices across various phases of their process lifecycle. This includes process design, execution, monitoring, and improvement. Furthermore, it provides concrete and actionable pathways toward achieving a more inclusive process management approach. A case study on solar panel installation is also presented to demonstrate the applicability of the framework.

The rest of the paper is organized as it follows. Section 2 describes the Maturity Canvas for Gender Awareness in Business Process Management. Section 3 provides the case study on solar panel installation. Finally, Section 4 presents conclusions.

2. Maturity Canvas for Gender Awareness in Business Process Management

The Maturity Canvas for Gender Awareness in BPM (see Figure 1) serves as the operational heart of the proposed framework. It enables organizations to assess their maturity in addressing gender equity within business processes and

offers a roadmap for continuous improvement. It includes four sections named, respectively, progressive maturity model, assessment criteria, guidance for improvement, and supporting tools. These are presented in the following.

Figure 13. Maturity Canvas for Gender Awareness in Business Process Management

PROGRESSIVE MATURITY MODEL		ASSESSMENT CRITERIA	
<p>Gender Blind: no recognition of gender differences or inequalities.</p> <p>Gender Neutral: gender is acknowledged but treated as irrelevant.</p> <p>Gender Sensitive: awareness of gender differences exists. Initial efforts to collect gender-disaggregated data and reduce barriers to inclusion begin.</p> <p>Gender Aware: gender awareness is fully integrated into all aspects of process management. Continuous monitoring and innovation support gender equity, and systemic change.</p>	Dimension	Indicators (examples)	
	Governance	Existence of gender equity policy	
	Workforce	Gender-sensitive recruitment and promotion practices	
	Data	Availability of gender-disaggregated data	
	Process management	Application of gender principles in workflows	
	Training and awareness	Staff training on gender equity, awareness programs and diversity initiatives	
Impact evaluation	Metrics tracking gender-specific outcomes		
GUIDANCE FOR IMPROVEMENT			
From level to level		Actions	
From Gender Blind to Gender Neutral		Raise awareness about gender equity Identify where gender bias may exist	
From Gender Neutral to Gender Sensitive		Begin gender data collection Establish basic gender equity goals	
From Gender Sensitive to Gender Aware		Embed gender-awareness indicators into BPM lifecycle Foster continuous innovation to support equity	
SUPPORTING TOOLS			
<p>Gender-Disaggregated Dashboards</p> <p>Large Language Models for gender analysis in process documents</p> <p>Inclusive Process Simulation Tools</p>			

In the section concerning the progressive maturity model, the canvas outlines a developmental pathway that spans from gender blindness, where organizations fail to recognize gender dynamics entirely, to full gender awareness, where equity principles are embedded in every aspect of process design, execution, and evaluation. At intermediate stages, organizations may exhibit gender neutrality, treating gender as irrelevant, or demonstrate gender sensitivity by acknowledging differences and beginning to address barriers to inclusion.

To guide evaluation, the section concerning the assessment criteria of the canvas incorporates specific dimensions such as governance, workforce, data management, process design, training, and impact evaluation and related indicators. For example, governance reflects whether policies promoting gender equity exist, while workforce indicators focus on recruitment and advancement practices. Data is assessed in terms of its gender-disaggregation, and impact evaluation considers how outcomes differ across genders.

The canvas not only outlines the characteristics of each maturity level but also provides crucial guidance for organizations aiming to transition between them in the section guidance for improvement, as shown in the guidance for improvement section. Moving from a **gender-blind** stage, where gender is largely ignored or considered irrelevant

in process design and execution, to a **gender-neutral** level necessitates building basic awareness of gender-related issues and proactively identifying areas where implicit biases might exist within current processes. This initial phase often involves training and workshops to sensitize employees, as well as preliminary audits of existing processes to uncover potential disparities in outcomes or experiences based on gender. Progressing from a gender-neutral stance to a **gender-sensitive** level requires a more active and deliberate approach. This involves initiating the systematic collection and analysis of gender-disaggregated data across key process metrics to understand how different genders are affected. Simultaneously, organizations at this stage begin policy development and implementation aimed at addressing identified gender imbalances and promoting equal opportunities within process-related activities. This might include adjustments to communication strategies, training materials, and even process steps to ensure inclusivity. Reaching the stage of **full gender awareness** demands a comprehensive and deeply integrated approach. This involves the systematic embedding of gender equity indicators and considerations across the entire Business Process Management lifecycle, from initial design and modelling through execution, monitoring, and optimization. Achieving this level also requires a commitment to continuous innovation, driven by ongoing feedback mechanisms from diverse stakeholders and rigorous monitoring of gender-related outcomes. Organizations at this stage actively seek to challenge existing norms, adapt processes based on evolving understandings of gender dynamics, and foster a truly inclusive and equitable process management environment where gender is proactively considered and positively valued. This mature stage signifies a fundamental shift in organizational culture, where gender equity is not just a policy but an ingrained principle guiding all process-related decisions and actions.

Supporting tools assist organizations in operationalizing these improvements and are shown in the supporting tools section. They include, for instance, gender-disaggregated dashboards, large language model-based analysis of process documentation (De Nicola et al., 2024), and inclusive simulation tools.

3. Solar Panel Installation Process Case Study

To test the usability and practical relevance of the maturity framework, it was applied to the reengineering of a solar panel installation process. The aim of this case study is to illustrate how it can be applied to reengineer processes for greater inclusivity and social sustainability.

3.1 Process Description

The original solar panel installation process is structured around a traditional business process management (BPM) approach, with a primary focus on operational efficiency, including time optimization, cost reduction, and error minimization. The process consists of sequential phases: initial customer consultation, site assessment, system design, permitting, material procurement, installation, inspection, grid connection, and post-installation support. While functionally effective, this process does not consider social factors such as gender equity or inclusivity in its design or execution.

No mechanisms were in place to assess the involvement of diverse stakeholders, ensure inclusive participation in decision-making, or adapt workflows and communication strategies to reflect gender-specific needs. As such, the process was evaluated as gender-blind, aligning with the first level of the proposed maturity framework.

3.2 Application of the Maturity Framework

To evaluate and improve the process, the Maturity Framework for Gender Awareness in Industrial Process Management was applied. As mentioned, this framework consists of four progressive levels, from gender-blind to gender-aware, and includes assessment criteria such as governance, participation, data usage, design inclusivity, and evaluation practices.

The process was assessed across these dimensions, using a combination of expert and large language model (LLM)-supported analysis (De Nicola et al., 2024) to test its usability and identify gaps. The assessment revealed a lack of gender-disaggregated data, absence of inclusive training or policies, and no application of gender-equity principles in the process design.

Based on these findings, targeted actions are proposed using the framework's guidance for improvement, aiming to move the process from gender-blind to gender-aware.

3.3 Reengineered Process Description

The reengineered solar panel installation process integrates gender equity as a core design principle. Key modifications include the implementation of inclusive customer engagement practices, gender-sensitive recruitment and training for technical staff, and the introduction of gender-disaggregated performance indicators.

The process now ensures active participation of all genders in consultations, accommodates flexible scheduling, and provides inclusive safety equipment and communication strategies. Furthermore, ongoing monitoring and evaluation are guided by gender-awareness indicators, and feedback mechanisms are in place to support continuous improvement.

This transformation aligns the process with the highest maturity level, promoting not only operational excellence but also social sustainability and resilience in line with the principles of Industry 5.0.

4. Conclusions

This paper presents the first structured attempt to integrate gender equity considerations into Business Process Management through a maturity-based framework. Rooted in conceptual modelling and supported by advanced digital tools, the framework provides a pathway for organizations to assess, plan, and evolve their BPM practices toward greater inclusivity. The Maturity Canvas acts as both a diagnostic and developmental tool, making abstract principles actionable.

The solar panel installation case study highlights the framework's practical relevance, illustrating how even traditionally efficiency-focused processes can be redesigned to promote social sustainability. This transformation aligns with the goals of Industry 5.0 by embedding inclusivity, collaboration, and ethical innovation into industrial practices.

Future work will focus on refining the framework, expanding its applicability across industries, and exploring the role of artificial intelligence in supporting gender-aware BPM. Broader adoption of such frameworks can serve as a catalyst for building resilient and equitable industrial ecosystems for the future.

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List of abbreviations and definitions

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BPM	Business Process Management
IoT	Internet of Things
LLM	Large Language Model

Algorithmic management and digital technologies for improving safety at hazardous workplace: a state of the art

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Abstract

The adoption of Artificial intelligence (AI), that is the field of computer science that designs machines to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence, and in particular, algorithmic management practices, defined as autonomous data-driven decision making in people's management by adoption of self-learning algorithms and artificial intelligence, are spreading in several contexts and sectors. Existing literature presents many applications for human resources management, delivery planning, warehouse management, financial services, etc. Also, application in risk assessment and safety and health sector is increasing, for supporting and improving the performance of these processes. A positive impact is highlighted about the use of AI technologies, in terms of improvement of efficiency, performance, productivity, reduction of risk and hazards that could create dangerous situations on workplace and for workers. The aim of the study is to define a state of the art of the present literature for this topic, focusing on examples of AI system for risk assessment and tools such as smart personal protective equipment and other AI applications that have been developed to improve workers' safety and health. The use of these solutions modifies work methods, increases complexity of production processes and introduces high dynamism into the working environments. For this reason, a critical aspect is underlined in the overview presented: it's important to consider AI-systems in terms of risk and hazards that could lead to workers that are directly involved in their use.

1. INTRODUCTION

Digitalisation, use of artificial intelligence, machine learning, big data and prevalence of remote and hybrid work, is changing how organizations manage human resources (Kinowska e Sienkiewicz 2023). Based on research by the European Commission (2021), the European Parliamentary Research Service (2020), the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (2019a) and EU-OSHA (2019), Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based Worker Management (AIWM) is an umbrella term that refers to a worker management system that collects data, often in real time, on the workspace, workers, the activities that they carry out and the (digital) tools they use for their work, which is then fed into an AI-based model that makes automated or semi-automated decisions or provides information for decision makers on worker management-related questions (EU-OSHA, 2022). The use of the "Algorithmic Management" is increasing and it's spreading the use of algorithms in managerial processes, including HRM and decision making (Kinowska & Sienkiewicz 2023). Lee et al. (2015) first used the term "algorithmic, data-driven management" to describe new practices of assigning work, providing informational support and assessment of performance of drivers in the ridesharing industry. An algorithm is a computational formula that autonomously makes decisions based on statistical models or decision rules without explicit human intervention (Eurofound, 2018). Duggan et al. (2020) define algorithmic management as a system of control where self-learning algorithms are given the responsibility for making and executing decisions affecting labour, thereby limiting human involvement and oversight of the labour process. Algorithmic management automates HR-related duties and functions usually undertaken by human managers (Duggan et al., 2020).

Algorithmic management is changing the workplace and the relationships between workers, managers, and algorithmic systems. Three key trends have aided the rise of algorithmic management. First, shifting norms of what constitutes work (e.g. project-centric work arrangements, platform work, and nonstandard contracts); second, the expanding technical capabilities of machine-learning based algorithms to replace discrete managerial tasks (Khan et al., 2019); and third, wide-scale micro-instances of organizational choice to use algorithmic management due to local economic and strategic goals. While intelligent systems continue to reshape our conceptions of work knowledge, boundaries, power structures, and overall organization, self-learning algorithms have the potential to chip away at several foundational notions of work and organization. For example, the deployment of intelligent systems will usher in new work systems with different divisions of work between machines and humans (where more mundane and data-centric tasks are assigned to

machines while humans engage in tasks requiring social intelligence, tacit understanding, or imagination). Moreover, new roles will be defined for managers as being strategic and creative thinkers rather than only coordinators of organizational transactions. While public concerns today focus on machines taking jobs from humans, care and concern is also needed around how these machines will contribute to the management of human actions (Jarrahi et al.2021).

The aim of the study is to define a state of the art about the use of these innovative technologies focusing in particular on a specific field, where their use is significantly increasing; the specific scope is the risk assessment processes and the safety and health management processes. The paper is organized as follows: after a brief introduction shown in section 1 of what are AI system and algorithmic management, how are introduced for improving process management or human resources management and why are increasing the diffusion of their use, it's presented and summarized, in section 2, the application of this innovative tool for supporting the risk assessment and the safety and health processes and, consequently, the benefits obtainable; then, deepening this literature analysis, a quick overview about a non-trivial aspect emerged is exposed in section 3, and regards the health and safety of workers who use AI systems. Finally, discussion and conclusion are presented in section 4.

2. AI FOR SUPPORTING RISK ASSESSMENT AND SAFETY AND HEALTH

In the workplace, AI-enabled systems can identify hazards, evaluate risks, and specify control measures (Yazdi et al. 2024). In addition, AI-enabled systems can automate repetitive workplace tasks, (Maheshwari, 2024) enhance the operational reliability of industrial processes, (Tamascelli et al., 2024) and enable the digital functioning of smart personal protective equipment (Shah & Mishra, 2024). Through the use of AI-enabled advanced sensor technologies, hazardous exposures can be continuously assessed and effectively managed (Howard et al., 2021) (El-Helaly, 2024). Adopting these systems for workplace risk assessment often provide “insights” to managers and technicians for supporting their decision-making process about risk assessment and control. AI-enabled systems are currently adopted for:

- Security and risk assessment: predicting employee likelihood to quit their job; predicting employee likelihood to engage in fraudulent activities; flagging potentially fraudulent activities or high-risk transactions; analysing employee sentiment to identify “toxic workers,” “toxic managers,” disgruntled workers, or potential union organizers; also monitoring worker social media activities for brand management;
- Health and wellness monitoring: predicting employee health costs, potential hospitalizations and emergency rooms visits, risk of developing health conditions (Kresge, 2020).

Technology developers design risk assessment algorithms to support firms pre-empt potential scenarios that might incur costs or negative outcomes for their brand. The design focus for these algorithms is to reduce or avoid costs and liability due to fraud, employee turnover, worker organizing, negative public perception of company, higher health insurance premiums related to poor employee health, or lower productivity due to lost work related to illness. Fraud detection systems are one example of risk assessment algorithms (Seidler, 2018)(Ryerson, 2017)(Speights, 2018). These applications use learning algorithms to analyze data from employee transactions and interactions in order to identify relationships and patterns in the data. Once the algorithms learn the normal relationships in the data, the system can analyze incoming data to detect abnormal patterns or outliers and then flag the activity or send an alert to managers. Other algorithms used for risk assessment can detect employee burnout or negative comments about the company by analyzing data from emails, internal messaging systems, or social media (Waddell, 2016)(Heires, 2015)(Charney, 2017). These systems can detect employee sentiment (negative, positive, neutral tone) in the context of discussion among employees by using natural language processing algorithms trained to recognize predefined themes or words in the text.

AIWM can provide potential avenues by improving workers' OSH, for example, providing tools for better monitoring of hazards and the mental health of workers, improving workers' engagement and job satisfaction, helping to design and conduct safety training, etc. (EU-OSHA, 2022). Applications designed to decrease employee health risks and related costs are another example of risk assessment systems (Ajunwa et al., 2023) Several companies incorporate wearable electronic fitness trackers into their workplace wellness programs in an effort to reduce health care costs and increase productivity. These trackers often include algorithms that analyze employee physical activity data and nudge employees to engage in physical activity to improve health outcomes, and in some cases reward them for doing so (Rowland, 2019). One goal of introducing fitness trackers may be to encourage employees to track their health activities and improve

their health, but employers may also receive monetary benefits from insurance companies and third-party vendors by sharing the employee health data collected (Olson,2014) (Shemkus 2015).

There are two types of applications that use algorithms to address health and safety risks in the workplace and these are:

- Worker behaviour monitoring: identifying poor ergonomics or employee fatigue;
- Workplace environmental health and safety hazard prevention: identifying hazardous situations, toxic fumes, high temperatures; and locating employees in at-risk environments.

Some of these technologies adopt wearable sensors and learning algorithms to detect and predict injury. For example, one company, StrongArm Technologies (<https://info.strongarmtech.com/safety-ergonomic-wearables-system-strongarm-technologies>), has developed a system that uses wearable sensors to monitor and collect data on employee movements and then processes this data with a machine learning algorithm to generate an injury risk score for each worker, based on the alignment of the employee's movements with proper ergonomic principles. Thanks to this risk score the system can send haptic feedback (i.e. the sensor buzzes) to the employees if they are not conforming to proper ergonomic practices. The employer can access a wide range of data analytics including safety behaviour data for each employee (Kresge, 2020). Other technologies use sensors embedded in location tracking devices (e.g., wearables with radio frequency identification (RFID) chips) to enable machines to track workers within or outside of the workplace. The Enseo Madesafe panic button (<https://enseo.com/madesafe/#>) is an instance, as it aims to provide hotel workers and other service workers a means to alert security in threatening situations. The technology includes a handheld device embedded with a location tracking sensor and a small panic button along with network receivers and a computer monitor for building security. When an employee presses the panic button, it emits a radio signal that triggers an algorithm to notify security of the worker's location. The Enseo system allows to enable real-time monitoring and data analytics reports for each worker's device, but, at the same time, it offers the option for maintaining worker privacy by only showing the worker location if they activate the panic button (Kudialis,2018). Some construction and mining companies use machine perception algorithms (e.g., computer vision) that monitor workers and the workplace environment for safety reasons. For instance, one construction company uses computer vision to analyze job site photos, scan them to identify safety hazards (e.g., workers not wearing protective equipment), and correlate the images with the company's accident records (Woyke, 2018). Other technologies combine computer vision algorithms designed to interpret the workplace environment with location tracking sensors embedded in wearable devices (e.g., helmets, jackets, tool belts, wristbands, etc.) to locate workers within that context. An example of this type of system is Toolbox Spotter. This is an algorithmic system designed to increase safety in industrial settings with heavy equipment, such as in construction, rail, logistics, mining, and manufacturing. The system uses video cameras attached to equipment to collect visual data on the worksite. Computer vision and deep learning algorithms process the visual data to identify objects or people in the blind spot of heavy equipment operators (<https://www.presien.com/>)(Ai Group, 2019). In particular, the system tracks the speed at which a person is walking and predicts the likelihood the equipment and person will intersect (Quarry Magazine, 2018). If the system determines that there's a hazard, it alerts the person at risk of getting hit as well as the equipment operator. Each worker will receive a notification through vibrations in a wristband along with flashing lights at the worksite. The technology can also automatically disable the equipment to avoid injuring the person (Kresge, 2020).

3. EMERGING RISKS FOR WORKER BY USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES SYSTEMS: A QUICK OVERVIEW

Another aspect important to introduce is the evaluation of the risk for workers that use Artificial Intelligence Systems, as the introduction of them into the workplace may modify the division of labour between what a worker does and what a machine does. This evolution in the control of work processes and the selection of job tasks create a new kind of human-machine relationship that requires a new approach to workplace safety and health (Cebulla et al. 2023a) (Cebulla et al. 2023b). In fact, AI systems are one of the recent developments in the workplace that presents opportunities but also risks and challenges for workers' safety and health (European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, 2022). These changes can lead to threats to workers' identity (Mirbabaie et al., 2022) and to workers' feeling of diminished value in the workplace (Koeszegi, 2024). The findings indicate that the use of AI to manage workers poses numerous risks to OSH (Bernhardt et al., 2023), including, but not limited to, workers losing control over their jobs, increased work intensity and performance pressure, decreased social support from managers, individualisation and

dehumanisation of workers, creating an unhealthy competitive environment, a lack of transparency and a loss of power for workers and their representatives, mistrust, limited worker participation, blurring work–life balance, and more. These risks in turn might lead to numerous negative consequences for workers’ physical and psychosocial wellbeing, such as musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs), cardiovascular disorders, fatigue, stress, anxiety and burnout (European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, 2022). Workers facing increased automation in the workplace can experience loss of meaningfulness in their work (Bankins & Formosa, 2023) (Michaelson et al., 2014), leading to adverse health outcomes (Nazareno & Schiff, 2021). The expanding capabilities of AI-enabled systems can lead to fears of job insecurity (Acemoglu et al., 2023)(Kelly,2024). Howard & Schulte (2024) synthesize these risks as in Table 1.

Table 1 Hazards identification for workers that use AI Systems (Howard & Schulte 2024)

Hazard	Description
<i>Adverse effects of human–machine hybridization and human–nonhuman ensembles</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Unintended consequences may arise from human machine hybridization ▪ Impact on self-identity.
<i>Bias and discrimination/opportunity loss/impact on health equity</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Use of biased data can result in discrimination in hiring and evaluations for promotions. ▪ Profiling from AI can lead to disparate treatment of workers.
<i>Complexity and lack of transparency</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Inability of workers to protect themselves from AI due to lack of knowledge about it.
<i>Deskilling, job loss, job precarity</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reduction of decision-making skills due to reliance on AI. ▪ AI can cause extensive job loss.
<i>Effects on workers and economic mobility</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Significant amounts of work on platforms are not compensated. ▪ Platform labour for AI utilizes unpaid labour globally. ▪ Down ward pressure on wages. ▪ Many workers all need to change occupations.
<i>Intrusive or constant monitoring</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Algorithmic and biomonitoring of sentiment, intention, activity, attention. ▪ Intrude on personal privacy. ▪ Can lead to discrimination. ▪ Selective exploitation of workers’ behaviours.
<i>Loss of autonomy, dignity, and meaningfulness of work</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reduced ability of worker to make own decisions. ▪ Loss of meaningful work. ▪ Diminished sense of value. ▪ Feelings of reduced self-efficacy. ▪ Greater work alienation.
<i>Malfunctions of AI</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Workers possibly endangered by inaccurate information from AI system. ▪ Algorithmic choices subject “to severe problems due to partial or incomplete data, inadequate modelling, and problematic objectives (Koeszegi,2024).”
<i>Loss of privacy</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Data about workers used without their control or acknowledgment.
<i>Psychosocial hazards/worker identity threat/job stress</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Precarious work due to threat of job loss; anxiety from technostress. ▪ Social deprivation. ▪ Loneliness. ▪ Diminished status. ▪ Job insecurity.
<i>Threats to health and well-being</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Hazard to health and safety. ▪ Emotional debilitation due to screening toxic images. ▪ High injury rates in warehouse workers.
<i>Work/home boundary pressures</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Limited ability to disconnect from work. ▪ Intrusion of AI and automated decision-making into personal life. ▪ Role ambiguity. ▪ Excessive alcohol use. ▪ Insomnia.
<i>Work intensification</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Automated management can lead to increased number of tasks in shorter workhours.

Hazard	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can cause stress, anxiety, fatigue, burnout.

Note: Hazards identified on the basis of empirical, discursive and hypotheses-generating studies.

Recently, the European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (2022) analyses in detail all potential types of risks for workers that use AI systems. An example of some of these are in Table 2 :

Table 2 Some of Risks of AIWM for workers' safety and health analyzed in EU-OSHA (2022)

Hazard	Description
Intensification of work:	To increase productivity, organisations might implement AI systems that direct workers to work without mini-breaks, minimise the time for certain procedures and force them to work at high speed. An example could be in warehouse operations: to speed up work, AI system is used for tracking order completion time as well as workers' movements, mistakes and breaks, in order to eliminate time lags. It is also important to underline that such direction systems, according to some authors, could be used to improve safety (Halawa et al., 2020). However, according to Mulholland and Stewart (2013), workers' safety and health is rarely a priority as it comes after lean logistics and the speed of work. High speed in delivering goods has become so important that, for example, in some warehouses workers are rewarded if they manage their tasks within half the time required and are thus able to complete more orders during their shifts.
Loss of job control and autonomy:	Some AIWM systems can take over the control of work (e.g. content, pace, schedule) through, for example, worker direction, and little will be left to be decided by the worker (Curchod et al., 2020; Kellogg et al., 2020; Saithibvongsa & Yu, 2018). Also, most algorithmic and AI based systems dictate how to perform work or tasks to the worker and this can result in a loss of control over their work (Curchod et al., 2020; Kellogg et al., 2020). The usage of AIWM systems that heavily control workers might also take away the margin of manoeuvre from workers. Margin of manoeuvre, according to Durand et al. (2016), is the possibility that a worker may develop different ways of working in order to meet production targets, without having adverse effects on their health. The loss of job control and autonomy is frequently associated with high levels of stress, and also lead to lower productivity, poor performance and increased levels of sickness absence (HSE, 2017).
Dehumanisation of workers:	Active use of AIWM systems, such as through excessive worker direction, evaluation or discipline, might lead to dehumanising workers and, in the long run, force them to behave as machines (Carr, 2014; Danaher, 2018; EU-OSHA, 2018; Heaven, 2020), which could then lead to decreased cognitive and intellectual capacities, decrease of creative thinking, a loss of autonomy, shortness of independence of thought and so on. While AIWM systems are expected to be able to inform workers and employers about risks (e.g. probability of fatigue and burnout), they might also lead to dehumanisation of workers as they might become dependent on the warning system created by AI and possibly lose their own ability to recognise hazards once something goes wrong. In turn, this might lead to ill health or work-related accidents.
Worker discrimination and use of private and sensitive data	Usage of AIWM systems can lead to worker discrimination, as intrusive monitoring can involve collecting private and sensitive data (Ravid et al., 2020), which can in turn be used to make automated or semi-automated decisions about the worker. This can result in favouring certain workers and discriminating against others (i.e. the stages of hiring or appraising/promoting workers). Even though AIWM systems may offer accuracy when looking at the desired profile of candidates in a selection process, they may make assumptions on candidates based on their characteristics (i.e. gender, ethnicity, nationality, age, sexual orientation, gender identity) and then make decisions resulting in some form of worker discrimination (EU-OSHA, 2018; Fernández-Martínez & Fernández, 2020), especially when AIWM systems are designed incorporating a bias.
Risky and unsafe worker behaviours	If the performance pressure is created by AI system, such as through algorithmic direction that increases the speed of work, or through evaluation algorithms that rate workers and force them to work more, this creates a tendency for unsafe behaviours as workers may need to choose between following directions and being productive or staying safe and healthy. For instance, workers may decide to remove the safety guard of a machine in order to complete the work procedure in a shorter time or take a faster or more dangerous route to deliver goods to the consumer. Excessive control can also lead to a low safety culture as workers start to favour productivity over safety, as well as have less time to communicate with their peers and thereby transfer their OSH knowledge (EU-OSHA, 2018).

<p>Repetitive movements, awkward postures and ergonomic issues:</p>	<p>The push to work faster can also lead to a higher number of repetitive movements, awkward postures due to rushing, and less attention paid to a worker's body and limb position and ergonomics. The repetitive movements, a fast pace and high quantity of work are especially hazardous, as the worker has no time to recover in the short periods of time between the motions. In the long run, the body needs more effort to perform the task and recovery time becomes even more important. Hence, the faster the pace, the less time is available for recovery, and the higher the risk for MSDs (Descatha et al., 2020; Finneran & O'Sullivan, 2010).</p>
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4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The integration of AI system in workplace for managing processes such as human resources, for supporting and improving performance of specific process, such as, warehouse management, safety and health aspects or risk assessment, is becoming a crucial topic for the research, as these technologies will play an important role in the future of the work. In this overview has emerged how many benefits provide the use of algorithmic management, AI system in several contests, how can improve the productivity and the efficiency of different sectors, such as logistics, delivery companies, warehouse management for the organization, and the benefit in term of human resources management simplifications for HR managers. For the risk assessment processes and also for the safety and health processes, the integration of AI technologies in methods or procedures could help to reduce hazard, risk, reducing dangerous situations that could lead to accidents or injuries. However, it has emerged that the integration of AI technologies with human work, in addition to bringing benefits to be highlighted, it is necessary to identify, analyse and quantify the impact that AI systems have on the health and safety of workers who use these technologies. At the moment, several risks have been identified in literature for workers in contact with AI systems, but they are the result of studies, discussions and hypotheses considered valid and true for the working reality. Practical methods are essential that will help in effectively identifying and managing the new AI hazards and risks. Therefore, future research should focus on AI risk management approaches that could integrate and categorize the several kinds of AI systems used in companies of each specific business for assuring worker safety, health and wellbeing, which is a key issue for the research, in order to guarantee a fair balance between risks and benefits for the use of these AI technologies.

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Business Continuity of University – Aspects of Organisational Reliability

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1. Introduction

One of the most important challenges facing the modern university today is to adapt to modern digital tools. This is also a chance to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of management of processes implemented in the university environment.

The fundamental aspect of the digital transformation of universities is access to information. Digital transformation affects many aspects of the university's operations, including [3]: teaching and learning methodology, assessment and evaluation of the teaching process, access to education, conducting scientific research and international academic cooperation, joint actions with business and local community, and management of the university's administrative processes.

In this context, issues of security of networks and information systems determine particular challenges to the digital transformation of universities. Figure 1 provides a good illustration of the scale of the IT security challenges facing the university system.

Fig. 1. Network traffic coming into the university network

where:

- red color - traffic blocked by the firewall, e.g. connection attempts to prohibited ports or IP addresses,
- green color - traffic allowed by the firewall, i.e. compliant with the rules,
- count axis - number of connections generated from external IP addresses to IP addresses of Wrocław Tech.

The formal way to deal with these challenges is defined by the NIS2 Directive (Network and Information Security Directive) EU 2022/2555 of 14 December 2022. The NIS2 Directive is an update of the earlier directive introduced in 2016. NIS 2 Directive [1] “lays down measures that aim to achieve a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, with a view to improving the functioning of the internal market”. The expected date of the NIS2 implementation in national law is the turn of 2024/2025 year. Universities are subject to the provisions of the directive because they belong to high criticality sector as a “public administration entities of central governments” [1]. Moreover, the organizational structure of Wrocław Tech includes WCSS (Wrocław Centre for Networking and Supercomputing), which acts as an electronic communications provider.

Thus, NIS2 Directive imposes new obligations on universities:

- implementation of risk analysis and risk management solutions in the area of cybersecurity,
- development of a business continuity plan,
- implementation of incident management procedures, vulnerability management,
- implementation of cyber hygiene practices through training and dissemination of knowledge about cyber threats, phishing and social engineering techniques.

2. Business continuity measure

The definition of security of networks and information systems refers to [2] “the ability of information systems to resist, at a given level of confidence, any event that could compromise the availability, authenticity, integrity or confidentiality of stored, transmitted or processed data, or of services offered by, or accessible via, those network and information systems”. Therefore, cybersecurity risk management takes into account the physical and environmental security of network and information systems against system failure, human error, malicious acts or natural phenomena.

The characteristic of organization that describes the degree of implementation of these postulates is business continuity. Business continuity is defined as [4] “capability of an organization to continue the delivery of products and services within acceptable time frames at predefined capacity during a disruption”. Wherein a disruption is understood as a predicted or unexpected event that causes an unplanned, negative deviation from the expected delivery of products and services in line with the organization's objectives.

The implementation of the requirements formulated in the NIS 2 directive requires the development of business continuity plan which is [4] a “documented information that guides an organization to respond to a disruption and resume, recover and restore the delivery of products and services consistent with its business continuity objectives”. Thus, the requirements concerning organizations business continuity are focused on: protection against disruptions, reducing the probability of disruptions occurrence, preparing to withstand an undesirable event, responding to them and recovering the ability to act after

their occurrence. While business continuity should be monitored and measured it is necessary, among other things, to develop a method of BC calculating.

This paper attempts to link the BC measure with measures describing undesirable events – failures, known from reliability engineering. The concept is illustrated in Figure 2 using the Sheffie profile [5].

Fig. 2. The Sheffie's profile [6]

The markings in Fig. 2 refer to: PoF - probability of failure, PoM – probability of repair (maintenance), CoF – consequences of failure. Generalizing the concept of failure to a disruptive / undesirable event and understanding: PoF as a measure of “protection against disruptions, reducing the probability of disruptions occurrence”, CoF as a measure of “preparing to withstand an undesirable event” and PoM as a measure of “responding to them and recovering the ability to act after their occurrence”, it is proposed to use the ReMaCo model [5] for evaluation business continuity measure.

The model was defined by 3 dimensions characterizing the failure of the object (fig. 3):

the ability of the object to function correctly without being interrupted by failure: reliability (PoF - probability of failure);

- the ability of the object to maintain or restore a state in given operating conditions in which it can perform

the required functions: maintainability (PoM - probability of repair (maintenance));

- the effects of failure measured by the impact of the object failure on the functioning of objects/systems in the environment of the operating system: (CoF - consequences of failure).

Thus, the event of object failure U can be described by the triple:

$$U = (PoF(t), PoM(t), CoF(t))$$

where individual characteristics are functions of the object's operating time, which is not obvious in the case of the description of damage effects.

Fig. 3. ReMaCo model [5]

Therefore, ReMaCo models can be classified as (fig. 4):

- one-dimensional models: reliability, maintainability and consequences,
- two-dimensional models: availability (combining the reliability and maintainability characteristics), safety (relating to reliability and consequences) and resilience (taking into account the effects of failure and maintainability).

Fig. 4. Measures of business continuity concept

Three-dimensional model takes into account the parameters analysed before: PoF(t), PoM(t), CoF(t). This allows, in a simplified way, to define the concept of continuity, particularly while we need to develop continuity measures or indicators.

For example, Continuity Priority Number CPN may be estimated. This approach bases on the metric known as Risk Priority Number analysed in risk management method – FMEA:

$$CPN = PoF \times PoM \times CoF$$

where: PoF, PoM, CoF measures are determined subjectively by experts on a scale of 1 to 5.

3. Case study

The example of CPN index estimation is based on data from the catastrophic flood that occurred in Central Europe in September 2024. Events calendar for the city of Wrocław:

- 15.09.2025 – announcement of a flood alert for the city,
- 18-20.09.2025 – the peak wave flows through the city,
- 25.09 – cancellation of the flood alert.

Fig. 5. Scheme of the location of Wrocław Tech buildings at risk of flooding and an example of protecting the building against flooding [7]

Due to the risk of flooding of buildings, some actions were taken to secure the IT infrastructure located on level 0:

- 17.09: dismantling in building H-5;
- 18.09: dismantling in buildings L-1, L-2, L-3.

Re-establishing to functioning the IT infrastructure took longer:

- 22.09 - 23.09: restoring to operation in building L-1;
- 23.09: restoring to operation in buildings L-2, L-3;
- 24.09: troubleshooting building L-1;
- 25.09: further corrections in building L-1, restoring VoIP operation.

The opportunity was used to replace worn-out infrastructure components with new devices. It can be assumed that by 25.09.2024 all faults were repaired and the Wrocław Tech network was working in a standard manner.

According to the network traffic graph, it can be seen that the impact of the flood situation on incoming and outgoing traffic from the Wrocław Tech network was practically imperceptible. Only the number of VPN logins during the week of 16-21.09 increased, which is probably due to the greater demand for remote work for employees. In the next week of 23-28.09, the number of logins decreased and returned to the pre-flood norm.

In order to calculate the CPN index it was assumed that:

- PoF = 2 - low probability of occurrence (the flood in 1997 caused the inundation of part of the marked area; an increase in the frequency of flood threats should be expected but at the same time effective protection works are being carried out against the effects of such a phenomena);
- PoM = 1 - almost certain that repair will be completed within an acceptable time frame (technically

standard work related to maintaining the infrastructure in up-state);

- CoF = 1 - the user will probably not feel dissatisfaction.

Thus CPN = $1 \times 1 \times 2 = 2$ and value of CPN (against the CPN range (1 – 125)) indicates the high ability of the university to maintain continuity of operations in flood hazard situations.

4. Conclusions

The problem of assessing the continuity of university operations, especially in the area of IT processes, is poorly recognized and scientifically promising. Cooperation in this area is needed between universities e.g. on: developing a common continuity assessment methodology in the context of cyber threats at the university level, identifying key cyber threats and their potential effects on the functioning of the university (e.g. interruption of operations, data breach), creating joint research projects and initiatives aimed at raising the level of cybersecurity in the academic environment.

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**UNIVERSITÀ
DEL SALENTO**

ESReDA

European Safety, Reliability &
Data Association

Annex 1 - Seminar Programme

66th ESReDA Seminar

Transformative safety and resilience models in a smart digital and sustainable world

May 22th - 23th, 2025

University of Salento, Lecce (Italy)

Day 1- Thursday 22 May	
8.30	Registration
9.00	Welcome: - ESReDA - University of Salento
9.30-10.15	Key Note 1 Resilience as a framework to manage Emergent Risks By Prof. Roberto Setola
10.15-11.00	Session 1- Digital technologies for supporting quantitative risk assessment
10.15	A framework for evaluating intralogistics safety through Discrete-Event Simulation By Leonardo Leoni, Filippo De Carlo, Mario Tucci
10.30	Bijjective Mapping of Probabilistic Discrete Variables to Support Decision Making – A case study By Mohamed EID
10.45	Risk identification in logistic cyber-social-technical systems By Agnieszka Tubis
11.00	<i>Coffee break</i>
11.30- 12.15	Key note speaker 2 Graphing the whispers: Weak signal insights via advanced knowledge modelling and reasoning By prof. Riccardo Patriarca
12.15-13.00	Session 2- Digital safety in the process industry
12.15	Soft Sensor For The Prediction of the composition of the Atmosphere in the flammable liquid tank By Gabriele Baldissone, Micaela Demichela, Davide Fissore, Salvina Murè
12.30	Towards the adoption of a systemic perspective for safe inspections at industrial sites By Elena Stefana, Giulio Di Gravio, Riccardo Patriarca
12.45	Effectiveness of safety measures in urban development adject to transport routes of hazardous materials By Shahid Suddle, Ben Ale
13.00-14.00	Lunch
14.00- 14.45	<i>Key note speaker 3</i> Integrity Inspections at Industrial sites in the time of digital transition By dr. Paolo Bragatto
	Session 3- Collaborative intelligence and human in the loop for the future of safety critical systems. A human centered perspective.

14.45- 16.30	<i>Session introduction: Human AI teaming & Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical Systems</i> By Micaela Demichela, Maria Chiara Leva, Ammar Abbas
15.00	Analysing" Human-in-the-Loop" for Advances in Process Safety: Key Factors and Lessons Learned in control room scenario By Chidera Winifred Amazu, Joseph Mietkiewicz, Ammar N. Abbas, Andres Alonso Perez, Houda Briwa,
15.15	Evaluating the Impact of Collaborative Intelligence Technologies on Worker Wellbeing in the EU Manufacturing Landscape By Naira López Cañellas
15.30	Enhancing Human Capabilities in Painting Defect Detection in automation and decision support system for anomaly detection By Carlos Albarrán Morillo, Doaa Almhaitawi, Devesh Jawla
15.45	Using physiological signal to provide insight into mental workload and operators engagement. Use of ML for helping to move towards real time EEG signal feedback By Milos Pusica
16.00	Title: Exploring Adaptive Human-Robot Collaboration: collaborative intelligence for cobotics and telerobotics By Carlo Caiazzo (co-written with Marija Savkovic, Milos Pusica, Nastasija Nikolic, Ivan Macuzic and Marko Djapan), Aayush Jain Shakra Mehak, Ines Filipa Ramos
16.15	Engaging end user in collaborative intelligence: what are the strength and weakness and opportunities for future applications and research by Loredana Bucseneau, Maria Chiara Leva, Ammar Abbas, Micaela Demichela
16.30- 18.00	ESREDA General Assembly
20.00	Gala Dinner, courtesy of ESREDA organization
Day 2- Friday 23 May	
9.00	Participants welcome
9.15- 10.00	Key note 4 Human-Centered Extended Reality and AI Assistants for Safer Operations: Real-Time Risk Mitigation through Smart Support By Javier Sordo
10.00-11.00	Session 4 Digitalization for preventing industrial accidents
10.00	Safety and security issues in the consideration of the HMI for the management of the Seveso sites By Romualdo Marrazzo , Domenico Barone
10.15	Baseline reports in IED installations: a reference model for data elaboration By Alessandro Stracqualursi, Francesca Mauro
10.30	Proof testing according to IEC 61508: an efficient tool to deal with the aging of safety-related systems in process plants By Francesco Nigri, Fausta Delli Quadri, Romualdo Marrazzo, Fabrizio Vazzana
10.45	The integration of information and operational technologies and the emerging risks for Seveso establishments. By Paolo Bragatto, Patrizia Agnello, Silvia M. Ansaldi, Roberto Setola
11.00-11.30	Coffee break

11.30-12.45	Session 5- Digitalization and Human centric applications in the Safety domain
11.30	Algorithmic management for improving safety at hazardous workplace: a state of the art By Serena Andriulo , Maria Grazia Gnoni, Fabiana Tornese, Marta Menci
11.45	Towards a Maturity Framework for Gender Awareness of Business Process Management By Maria Guariglia Migliore, Antonio De Nicola
12.00	Risk Management Ontology to Action (O2A): Bridging Uncertainty and Execution to Improve Resilience By Ali Aghazadeh Ardebili , Syrine Yousfi , Antonella Longo, Elio Padoano
12.15	Business Continuity of University – Aspects of Organisational Reliability By Tomasz Nowakowski
12.30	AI, human factor, legislation By Sever Paul
<i>End of technical sessions</i>	
13.00	Lunch